

Studii Europene

nr. 13

Chişinău
2019

Studii Europene

13

European Studies

**Chisinau
2019**

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Publisher:
ECSA Moldova

Gesis-SSOAR

ISSN 2345-1041
ISSN-L 2345-1041

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Association Agreement – the Unique International Treaty with the Exceptional Character

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Abstract. Association Agreement is the International Treaty of Georgia of rare and exceptional character. Its uniqueness is conditioned and determined by the political context, at the same time, by legal nature. The article reviews those juridical features of the Association Agreement, understanding of which gives the possibility of systemic cognition of the AA, as well as proves and strengthens the consideration about its exclusiveness.

Keywords: Association Agreement, international treaty, Georgia, exceptional character.

Abbreviations:

AA – Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and Georgia, of the other part (Association Agreement)

DCFTA – Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area

SPS – Sanitary and Phytosanitary (food safety)

FTA – Free Trade Agreement

EURATOM – European Atomic Energy Community

TEU – Treaty on European Union (Maastricht Treaty)

TFEU – Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (Lisbon Treaty)

CJEU – Court of Justice of the European Union

OSCE – Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe

UN – United Nations

Introduction

In 2014, the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and Georgia, of the other part, signed the Association Agreement.¹ Henceforth, EU integration policy in Georgia has been transmitted to a qualitatively different format and now on, we can freely call it *European Association process*. An association is hereby established between the European Union and Georgia² and new opportunities for greater and enhanced economic integration have emerged.

The Association Agreement covers:

- Political part;
- DCFTA part;
- Sectoral part;
- Institutional provisions;
- Four protocols;
- 34 Annexes.

The Association Agreement is the international treaty of the monopolistic nature inasmuch as it ensures regulation of almost all public relations' fields. The text of the treaty exceeds 1 000 pages and the Annexes provide more than 300 EU legal acts (names of the regulations, directives, decisions and recommendations) requiring transposition into the national legislation of Georgia, implementation and enforcement. The EU officials have deemed the Association Agreement as an ambitious treaty of the new generation signed by Georgia, Ukraine, and Moldova within the *Eastern Partnership Initiative*.

The Association Agreement entails the necessity of the political, economic and legal reforms to be undertaken by Georgia. The process is complicated, reforming and in some cases painful, though legal

¹ The Parliament of Georgia ratified the Association Agreement on July 18, 2014, Georgian version on <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/2496959> (accessed 12 April 2019); English version on [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:22014A0830\(02\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:22014A0830(02)) (accessed 12 April 2019).

² Article 1.1, Association Agreement.

approximation shall result in the benefits for the country and Georgian people, such as economic progress, increased welfare, social progress, safety, and security. The Association Agreement became fully effective on July 1, 2016, though certain parts of the agreement have been subject to provisional application, which is certified in the EU notification to Georgia.³ Hence, DCFTA and other titles/chapters have been enacted as from September 1, 2014.

Georgia, being the subject of the international law, has concluded the numerous international agreements but the Association Agreement is of the rare and exceptional nature. Its uniqueness is conditioned and determined by the political context, at the same time, by legal nature. The article reviews those juridical features of the Association Agreement, understanding of which gives the possibility of systemic cognition of the AA, as well as proves and strengthens the consideration about its exclusiveness. This would be valuable for the field of the International Treaty Law, on the one hand, and for the European Association process, on the other hand.

Parties to the Association Agreement, Structure and Key Legal Provisions

1. Parties to the Association Agreement

The title of the Association Agreement provides multiple parties. The Agreement has been concluded by the European Union, the EURATOM, their Member States, of the one part, and Georgia, of the other part. Not only the EU as the supranational entity but 28 EU Member States and EURATOM are the contracting parties to Georgia. Multiplicity of the parties is conditioned with the factors as follows:

³ Council Decision (2014/494/EU) of 16 June 2014 on the signing, on behalf of the European Union, and provisional application of the Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and Georgia, of the other part, http://www.parliament.ge/ge/ajax/downloadFile/34754/AA_ENG (accessed 12 April 2019).

a) EURATOM was established in 1957 by the founder countries of the European Communities⁴ on the basis of the Treaty on European Atomic Energy Community.⁵ The agreement is of the sectoral nature and regulates the aspects related to the atomic energy distribution market in Europe. The treaty has established the international organization – EURATOM, which is, in a legal manner, dissociated from the EU, however, EURATOM is composed of the same countries as the EU and at the same time, EURATOM is managed by the same institutions as of the EU; the Treaty establishing EURATOM is the source of the EU primary legislation. Pursuant to paragraph 1 of Article 429 of the Association Agreement: “This Agreement shall apply, of the one part, to the territories in which the Treaty on European Union, the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union and the Treaty establishing the European Atomic Energy Community are applied and under the conditions laid down in those Treaties, and of the other part, to the territory of Georgia”. *Inasmuch as the Association Agreement covers all the issues attributed to the interest and regulation sphere of EURATOM and inasmuch as EURATOM is the part of the EU policy and law, it entailed necessity of its participation in conclusion of the Association Agreement.*

b) As mentioned hereof, paragraph 1 of Article 429 of the Association Agreement underlines TEU and TFEU. TEU is the Treaty establishing the

⁴ European Communities, such are European Coal and Steel Community and European Economic Community, have been established in 1951 and 1957 by the following states: Belgium, the Netherlands, Luxembourg, France, Italy and Germany. In 1965, the executive bodies of three European Communities (European Economic Community/EEC, European Coal and Steel Community and EURATOM) were combined and they were together known as European Community. In 1993, the Treaty on European Union/TEU (Maastricht Treaty) established the European Union and the first pillar of the EU consisted of the European Communities. The Treaty on European Coal and Steel Community was concluded for a period of 50 years. It expired on 23 July 2002 and is no longer valid today. The Rome Treaty of 1957 on European Economic Community and the Rome Treaty of 1957 on European Atomic Energy Community establishing the EEC and EURATOM are still valid. The Treaty on EEC is now fully integrated in the Lisbon Treaty – TFEU.

⁵ Consolidated version of the Treaty Establishing the European Atomic Energy Community, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:12016A/TXT&from=EN> (accessed 12 April 2019).

European Union, and TFEU⁶ is the revision of the treaty of 1957 on the European Economic Community. The treaty of 1957 was re-entitled into the Treaty on Functioning of the European Union/TFEU. This treaty organizes the functioning of the EU and determines the areas of EU competences. The both treaties (TEU, TFEU) constitute the Treaties on which the Union is founded and they have same legal value.⁷ *Treaties consider the spheres of exclusive competence of EU as follows:*

- customs union;
- establishing of the competition rules necessary for the functioning of the internal market;
- monetary policy for the Member States whose currency is the Euro;
- conservation of marine biological resources under the common fisheries policy;
- common commercial policy;
- conclusion of an international agreement when its conclusion is provided for in a legislative act of the Union or is necessary to enable the Union to exercise its internal competence, or in so far as its conclusion may affect common rules or alter their scope.⁸

EU as well has shared competence with Member States:

- internal market;
- social policy, for the aspects defined in this Treaty;
- economic, social and territorial cohesion;
- agriculture and fisheries, excluding the conservation of marine biological resources;
- environment;
- consumer protection;
- transport;

⁶ Consolidated version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:12016E/TXT&from=EN> (accessed 12 April 2019).

⁷ *Ibid.*, Article 1.

⁸ *Ibid.*, Article 3

- trans-European networks;
- energy;
- area of freedom, security, and justice;
- common safety concerns in public health matters, for the aspects defined in this Treaty;
- research and technological development;
- development in cooperation and humanitarian aid sphere.⁹

EU has the supportive and coordinating competences in the spheres as follows:

- protection and improvement of human health;
- industry;
- culture;
- tourism;
- education, vocational training, youth, and sport;
- civil protection;
- administrative cooperation.

The types of hereof competences are associated with the division of decision-making at the EU and national levels in the field of law-making and other policies. When the treaties confer on the Union exclusive competence in a specific area, only the Union may legislate and adopt legally binding acts.¹⁰ The acts adopted by the EU are binding for all Member States. When the Treaties confer on the Union a competence shared with the Member States in a specific area, the Union and the Member States may legislate and adopt legally binding acts in that area.¹¹ Legally binding acts of the Union adopted on the basis of the provisions of the Treaties relating to sphere of supportive competences, these areas shall not entail harmonisation of Member States' laws or regulations.¹² *Inasmuch as the issues regulated under the Association Agreement have gone beyond the exclusive*

⁹ *Ibid.*, Article 4.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, Article 2.1.

¹¹ *Ibid.*, Article 2.2.

¹² *Ibid.*, Article 2.5.

competences of the EU and the treaty has covered the issues attributed to the competences of the EU Member States (share and support competences), conclusion of the Association Agreement appeared to require consent of not only the EU but the EU Member States and their participation in conclusion of the AA.

2. Structure of the Association Agreement

The Association Agreement consists of 8 titles, 34 Annexes and 4 Protocols. 8 Titles of the AA generally are divided into three directions: political part, trade relations part (DCFTA) and the sectoral part. All titles provide the goals and objectives to be reached. Annexes of the AA are connected to these titles and provide certain measures to be undertaken in view of achievement of the objectives of each title, namely, the annexes provide the list of the EU legal acts – *directives, regulations, decisions and recommendations* and concrete timetable for the approximation thereto. The Protocols to AA define the terms and specify the conditions necessary for implementation of some of the titles.

2.1. Political Part

The Political Part of the AA consists of 3 titles, in total 21 Articles: title I – General Principles; title II – Political Dialogue and Reform; Cooperation in the Field of Foreign and Security Policy; title III – Freedom, Security, and Justice. The following are the spheres of the AA Political Part: human rights, good governance, democracy, rule of law, countering corruption, combating terrorism, stability, security, peaceful resolution of conflict, crisis management, personal data protection, migration and asylum, readmission, illicit drugs, money laundering and terrorism financing, etc. It is noteworthy that the *Political Part has no annexes* (the only exception is the personal data protection), which means that the EU, in political part does not require Georgia to approximate to EU legislation. It is to be stressed that the spheres of the *AA Political Part are not attributed to exclusive EU competences and not the EU but the Member States draw the*

legislation in these spheres. Taking into consideration this essence characteristic to the EU, the political part of the AA requests Georgia to fulfill the obligations originated from Georgia's membership to various international organizations (UN, CoE, OSCE, etc.). This feature of the AA is extremely noteworthy in terms of cognition of the Agreement and realization of its priorities. *It is crystal clear that European integration does not require approximation to the EU legislation in the political part.*

European integration and/or EU membership is inadmissible without fulfillment of the *acquis communautaire*, which constitutes the compendium of the legislative acts and the case law, which in aggregation formulate the EU law. None of the European states is capable to access to EU without legal approximation and reflection of the standards of the EU law in the national legislation and practice. This is the very feature making EU drastically different from other international organizations. *Hence, the assessment index of fulfillment of the I, II and III titles (Political Part) of the AA, would be the evaluation of the progress of Georgia by the UN, OSCE, CoE and other international organizations on fulfillment of the commitments under membership framework.* Thus, the nature of the EU and its approach to the Political Association Process with the EU is clearly revealed. Even without the AA, Georgia shall fulfill the commitments assumed towards the international community in the fields of democracy, human rights protection, security, peace-building, defense, etc. Thus, the logical question is: *what are the priorities of the European integration and what European integration means for Georgia.* As mentioned above, European integration and membership are feasible by means of legal approximation, which means that Georgia, even meeting the EU political criterion, cannot still be deemed, brought closer directly to the EU law. Therefore, it is important to identify the fields for legal approximation which should be done by Georgia to achieve tangible outcomes and real European integration. Georgia for a long time strives to integrate into the EU internal market. The legislation regulating the internal market and the trade is the field where Georgia shall

undertake the wide-scale process of legal approximation of the national legislation with the EU law.

*The above-mentioned concludes that European integration is productive and real when legal approximation is ensured with the fields in which the EU holds the exclusive competences and draws the legislation, namely the legislation regulating the internal market functioning. This consideration does not decline the value of the AA political part, though the scarcity of the AA political part (21 Articles out of 432), absence of the annexes and the content of the political part clarify the legal nature of European integration.*¹³

2.2. Trade Relations Part

The title IV – “Trade and Trade-related Matters” regulates the EU-Georgia trade relations. This part is called DCFTA. DCFTA concludes the articles 22-276, and is enclosed with the most of the annexes of the AA and two protocols (protocols I and II); DCFTA is the largest part of the AA, which consists of the chapters as follows:

- Market access for goods;
- Trade remedies;
- Technical barriers to trade, standardization, metrology, accreditation and conformity assessment;
- Sanitary and phytosanitary measures;
- Customs and trade facilitation;
- Establishment, trade in services and electronic commerce;
- Current payments and movement of capital;
- Public Procurement;
- Intellectual Property Rights;
- Competition;
- Trade-related Energy Provisions;
- Trade and Sustainable Development;

¹³ Ekaterine Kardava, “Value of DCFTA in European Association Process,” *Herald of the Caucasus University*, N12, Tbilisi (2017): 31-39.

- Etc.

In view of implementation of each and every chapter of DCFTA, the annexes to the AA provide hundreds of the EU legal acts – the sources of the EU secondary legislation,¹⁴ without implementation of which Georgia cannot integrate to the EU internal market. EU-Georgia enjoy the long political, cultural and economic cooperation, though *the EU internal market is only open to Georgia upon meeting of DCFTA requirements*: Article 419 of the AA provides that *“If the Parties agree that necessary measures covered by Title IV (Trade and Trade-related Matters) of this Agreement have been implemented and are being enforced, the Association Council¹⁵ shall decide on further market opening where provided for in Title IV (Trade and Trade-related Matters) of this Agreement”*.

DCFTA aims at achievement of the outcomes such are increased investments, intensification of exchanged relations, enlargement of production, development of the small and medium business, freedom of movement of goods and services, import of more goods into the EU internal market, healthy competition, increased capital – all hereof aspects to have the effective impact on the economic and financial capacity of the state. Under hereof conditions, the state is capable to effectively meet the AA commitments, such are productive and full employment, decent work, social

¹⁴ The EU law structure is as follows: the sources of the primary legislation are the agreements currently represented under the TFEU of 2007 (Lisbon Treaty) and the TEU of 1992 (Maastricht Treaty). The sources of the secondary legislation comply with the sources of the primary legislation. The sources of the secondary legislation are the directives, regulations, decisions binding for the EU Member States. The regulation is of the direct effect and needs no transposition to the legislation of the Member States but automatically becomes the part of the national legislation. The directive is rarely of the direct effect and mostly needs to be incorporated in the legislation of the Member States. The Member States enjoy the established terms. The form of incorporation is free, it is the national law, by-law or other. The decision is directed to the EU Member States or individuals. The recommendations are as well attributed to the secondary legislation source, though are not binding.

¹⁵ The AA stipulates the format of the official political dialogue between EU and Georgia in capacity of the Association Council the decisions of which are binding. See articles 404, 405 and 406 of AA.

progress, human rights protection, enhancement of state institutions, good governance, security, etc. History of the formation and development of the EU itself as of the single political, economic and legal entity is the path from the common trade, economic policy, single market project to peace, welfare and social progress outcomes. Thus, implementation of DCFTA for Georgia is the guarantee for not only achievement of the trade objectives but for the successful implementation of the political and sectoral parts of the AA. *It is essential to share and study from the historical lesson of EU and when interpreting the DCFTA provisions the EU development context shall be taken into account. It will serve to the due cognition of the AA, on the one hand, and, on the other hand, determination of the effective tactics of the implementation thereof.*

DCFTA allows Georgia becoming the regional hub and enjoying the advantages towards the countries which have not concluded the free trade agreements with the EU. DCFTA requires Europeanization of the market rules on the territory of Georgia, among them, integration of the social and environmental objectives into the trade policy; DCFTA requires formation of the safe and protected market. For the counterweight: a) *goods completely originated in Georgia* are to enter the EU internal market with the zero or preferential customs tariff; b) *goods originated on the territory of other countries imported and ultimately processed in Georgia shall be converted into the goods originated in Georgia,*¹⁶ which in its turn, shall enter the EU internal market with the zero or preferential customs tariff. Georgia can at some extent “make” the neighboring or partner states without FTA or DCFTA with the EU, express interest in the AA advantages and transfer own production to Georgia. Implementation of DCFTA allows Georgia importing up to 9 000 types of products to the EU internal market:

¹⁶ If the goods imported to Georgia composed of the material not completely produced in Georgia but processed-recycled, upon meeting the AA requirements are converted into the goods produced in Georgia, for instance: swine and boar bristle, imported to Georgia from the foreign country and subject to further procedures in Georgia – cleaning, disinfection, classification and correction – shall be deemed as “produced in Georgia” and enter the EU market without the customs taxes.

- Export of 220 tons of garlic (fresh and frozen) without the customs duties to the EU;

- Export of vegetable and fruit (28 types in total): tomato, cucumber, tangerine, apricot, table grapes, lemon, grape juice, sweet orange, zucchini, apple, pear, sour cherry, peach, plum, etc. to the EU market exempted from the ad valorem component;

- Export of 4 400 tons of beef, pork and mutton, 550 tons of poultry meat, 1 650 tons of dairy, 330 tons of eggs and albumin, 220 tons of mushrooms, 200 000 tons of Poaceae, siftings, bran etc. – 2 200 tons, sweet corn 1 500 tons, 6 000 tons of processed sugar, 500 tons of cigarettes etc. to the EU without the customs duties;

- Export of the goods to the EU fully or sufficiently processed in Georgia (originated in Georgia).¹⁷

Unlike the Political Part, DCFTA requires legal approximation in every field. In the trade part, European integration is directly associated with legal approximation. Trade relations field is the part of the competence in which the EU draws the secondary legislation. Timely and due implementation of title IV of the AA conditions real success of association policy with the EU and achievement of not only trade-economic but political and social objectives.

2.3. Sectoral Part

The sectoral part of the AA consists of titles V and VI. Title V (Articles 277-291) regulates economic cooperation, namely the public finances, taxation/tax policy and the statistic data. Hereof title is enclosed with two annexes. Title VI (Articles 292-382) regulates other fields of cooperation, namely:

- Transport;
- Energy;
- Environment;
- Climate-related activities;
- Industrial and enterprise policy and mining;

¹⁷ Title IV, Annex II-A, Annex II-B, Annex II-C, Protocol I, Association Agreement.

- Company law, accounting, and auditing and corporate governance;
- Financial services;
- Cooperation in the field of information society;
- Tourism;
- Agriculture and rural development;
- Fisheries and maritime governance;
- Cooperation in research, technological development, and demonstration;
- Consumer policy;
- Employment, social policy, and equal opportunities;
- Public health;
- Education, training, and youth;
- Cooperation in the cultural field;
- Cooperation in the audiovisual and media fields;
- Cooperation in the field of sport and physical activity;
- Civil society cooperation;
- Regional development;
- Civil protection;
- Participation in European Union agencies and programmes.

Title VI is enclosed with 13 annexes and III Protocols.

Upon implementing the tasks and objectives of Title VI, it is paramount to ensure assessment, measurement and analysis of efficiency of implementation of the commitments stipulated under the hereof title in the context of DCFTA, namely in terms of correspondence with the sustainable development policy goals. Pursuant to DCFTA, sustainable development policy is feasible if trade, labor and environmental fields are deemed as of equal value and are being developed without prejudice to each other. Thus, consideration of titles VI and IV in correlation is vital. The commitments of title VI requiring Europeanization of the environmental and social policies, which is quite delicate and costly as for the state, so for the business – shall be implemented in the manner to represent the outcome of implementation

*of the commitments of title IV. At that, implementing title VI shall be ensured without prejudice to the balance of equal value between the trade, environmental and social objectives.*¹⁸

2.4. Other Titles, Annexes, and Protocols of the Association Agreement

Title VII of the AA consists of the provisions concerning the financial aid, countering fraud, and control, which are regulated under the Articles 383-402. It is enclosed with one annex and the Protocol IV. Title VIII, namely the Articles 403-432 consist of the institutional, general, and final provisions.

34 Annexes and four Protocols constitute the integral parts of the Agreement. The annexes provide the sources of the EU secondary legislation. Georgia is committed to approximate to the EU legislation provided in the annexes. All four Protocols provide the definitions and detalization of the number of issues, namely:

- Protocol I – Concerning the definition of the concept of ‘Originating products’ and methods of administrative cooperation, replaced with the “Regional Convention on pan-Euro-Mediterranean preferential rules of origin” on the basis of the decision of the Sub-Committee on Customs;¹⁹

- Protocol II – on Mutual Administrative Assistance in Customs Matters;

- Protocol III – on a framework Agreement between the European Union and Georgia on the general principles for the participation of Georgia in Union programmes;

- Protocol IV – Definitions.

¹⁸ Ekaterine Kardava, “Georgian Labour Law Reform in the context of European Integration and Association Agreement” (Dissertation, 2018), 30-32.

¹⁹ The Decision of the EU-Georgia Sub-Committee on Customs N1/2018, on replacement of the Protocol I on “Concerning the definition of the concept of ‘Originating products’ and methods of administrative cooperation” between at one part Georgia, and at the other part EU and European Atomic Energy Community and Member States, March 20, 2018, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/4116909> (accessed 12 April 2019).

3. Special and Exceptional Features of the Association Agreement

Complex and system cognition of the Association Agreement requires identification of the features and characteristics converting the Agreement into the special and unique international treaty of the new type in political and legal terms.

3.1. Effective Date and Enactment Aspects

On July 25, 2014, Georgia submitted the AA ratification instrument to the General Secretariat of the Council of the European Union.²⁰ On the basis of this pursuant to paragraph 4 of Article 431 of the Agreement, the provisional application effective date of the Agreement is defined as September 1, 2014. The EU delivered the notification defining titles, chapters and annexes of the Agreement setting the effective date prior to full enactment of the Agreement.²¹ This aspect is of particular importance

²⁰ Council of the European Union is one of the EU political bodies equipped with the legislative powers and alongside the European Parliament adopts the EU legal acts.

²¹ Pending its entry into force, in accordance with Article 431 of the Agreement and subject to the notifications provided for therein, the following parts of the Agreement shall be applied provisionally between the Union and Georgia, but only to the extent that they cover matters falling within the Union's competence, including matters falling within the Union's competence to define and implement a common foreign and security policy:

(a) Title I;

(b) Title II: Articles 3 and 4 and Articles 7 to 9;

(c) Title III: Articles 13 and 16;

(d) Title IV (with the exception of Article 151, to the extent that it concerns criminal enforcement of intellectual property rights; and with the exception of Articles 223 and 224, to the extent that they apply to administrative proceedings and review and appeal at Member State level);

(e) Title V: Articles 285 and 291;

(f) Title VI: Chapter 1 (with the exception of point (a) of Article 293, point (e) of Article 293, points (a) and (b) of Article 294(2)), Chapter 2 (with the exception of point (k) of Article 298), Chapter 3 (with the exception of Article 302(1)), Chapters 7 and 10 (with the exception of point (i) of Article 333), Chapter 11 (with the exception of point (b) of Article 338 and Article 339), Chapters 13, 20 and 23, as well as Articles 312, 319, 327, 354 and 357;

(g) Title VII;

(h) Title VIII (with the exception of Article 423(1), to the extent that the provisions of that Title are limited to the purpose of ensuring the provisional application of the Agreement as defined in this paragraph);

for the gradual and timely implementation of the Association Agreement and the monitoring of implementation. The term of fulfillment of the commitments provided in the notification shall be calculated as from September 1, 2014; the term of fulfillment of the remaining commitments of the AA shall be calculated as from July 1, 2016 (full effective date).

Inasmuch as the major part of the AA and especially DCFTA have been enacted in 2014, the supplementary documents on the AA implementation as follows have been legislated and approved:

- The first Association Agenda for 2014-2016;²²
- The National Annual Plans of the AA and Association Agenda Implementation for 2014,²³ 2015²⁴ and 2016;²⁵
- Action Plan on DCFTA Implementation for 2014-2017.²⁶

3.2. Validity Period

The AA leaves the agreement term open. Pursuant to Article 427, *“This Agreement is concluded for an unlimited period”*. However, hereof record cannot be construed in the manner that the term is infinite and the period for fulfillment of commitments is unlimited. The annexes to the AA indicate to certain terms for certain commitments.

(i) Annexes II to XXXI and Annex XXXIV, as well as Protocols I to IV.

²² Association Agenda between European Union and Georgia, http://eeas.europa.eu/archives/delegations/georgia/documents/eap_aa/associationagenda_2014_en.pdf (accessed 12 April 2019).

²³ The Governmental Ordinance of September 3, 2014, N1516 on approval of the National Action Plan on Implementation of the Association Agreement and Association Agenda for 2014, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/2496190> (accessed 12 April 2019).

²⁴ The Governmental Ordinance of January 26, 2015, N59 on approval of the National Action Plan on Implementation of the Association Agreement and Association Agenda for 2015, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/2702520> (accessed 12 April 2019).

²⁵ The Governmental Ordinance of March 7, 2016, N382 on approval of the National Action Plan on Implementation of the Association Agreement and Association Agenda for 2016, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/3222307> (accessed 12 April 2019).

²⁶ Action Plan of Georgia on DCFTA Implementation for 2014-2017, http://www.dcfta.gov.ge/public/filemanager/implimentation/2014-2017%20%E1%83%A1%E1%83%90%E1%83%9B%E1%83%9D%E1%83%A5%E1%83%9B%E1%83%94%E1%83%93%E1%83%9D_%E1%83%92%E1%83%94%E1%83%92%E1%83%9B%E1%83%90.pdf (accessed 12 April 2019).

3.3. European Perspective (Membership Prospects)

The Association Agreement fails to provide the norm regarding membership prospect. Pursuant to Article 49 of TEU,²⁷ *any European State can apply to become a member of the Union*. Pursuant to the AA, Georgia is recognized not as European but the *Eastern European state*.²⁸

3.4. Territorial Application

Article 429 of the AA concerns territorial application of the Agreement. It stresses the state of the de jure and de facto control of the occupied territories of Georgia by the Government of Georgia. On the one hand, it recognizes the territorial integrity of Georgia, and on the other hand, restricts commencement of application of the Agreement or Title IV thereof in regards with Abkhazia and Tskhinvali region/South Ossetia inasmuch as the Government of Georgia is deprived to ensure an effective control on hereof territories. Commencement of application of the Association Agreement or Title IV on the occupied territories is reconciled, namely: *“The application of this Agreement, or of Title IV (Trade and Trade-related Matters) thereof, in relation to Georgia’s regions of Abkhazia and Tskhinvali region/South Ossetia over which the Government of Georgia does not exercise effective control, shall commence once Georgia ensures the full implementation and enforcement of this Agreement, or of Title IV (Trade and Trade-related Matters) thereof, respectively, on its entire territory.”* *“The Association Council shall adopt a decision on when the full implementation and enforcement of this Agreement, or of Title IV (Trade and Trade-related Matters) thereof, on the entire territory of Georgia, is ensured.”*

Pursuant to the hereof provisions, the Association Agreement shall be applied in Abkhazia and Tskhinvali region when the Government of Georgia enjoys the effective control on hereof territories, and at the same time, has the opportunity of full implementation of the Agreement. This fact is subject

²⁷ Consolidated Version of the Treaty on European Union, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:12016M/TXT&from=EN> (accessed 12 April 2019).

²⁸ Preamble, Association Agreement.

to be approved by the Association Council. The Association Council shall as well make the respective decision.

3.5. Legal Approximation

Chapter 2 of title VIII (Institutional, General and Final Provisions) of the Association Agreement) stipulates two key principles of legal approximation of the legislation of Georgia with the EU law – *gradual approximation and dynamic approximation.*

Article 417 of the Association Agreement provides the elucidation of the gradual approximation as follows: *“Georgia shall carry out gradual approximation of its legislation to EU law as referred to in the Annexes to this Agreement, based on commitments identified in this Agreement, and in accordance with the provisions of those Annexes.”* The essence of the gradual approximation lies in the fact that Georgia shall fulfill the commitments solely prescribed under the annexes and within the terms established therein.

Article 418 of the Association Agreement provides the elucidation of the dynamic approximation as follows: *“In line with the goal of gradual approximation by Georgia to EU law, the Association Council shall periodically revise and update annexes to this Agreement, including in order to reflect the evolution of EU law and applicable standards set out in international instruments deemed relevant by the Parties, and following the completion of the respective internal procedures of the Parties, as appropriate”.* The essence of the dynamic approximation lies in the fact that if the EU laws envisaged under the annexes are declared void and the EU adopts new acts, Georgia shall carry out legal approximation with the legal norms prevailing in the EU. In this view the annexes of the Association Agreement may be revised and amended.

Legal approximation is subject to monitoring as by Georgia so by the EU. Pursuant to Article 419 of the Association Agreement, *“Monitoring shall mean the continuous appraisal of progress in implementing and enforcing measures covered by this Agreement”.* Pursuant to the norm, monitoring

*shall cover the results of the legal approximation – implementation and enforcement of the European norms integrated into the normative space of Georgia. Otherwise, monitoring of approximation loses every sense inasmuch as it is ineffective and vain to assess the norms solely reflected in the national legislation which have not been enacted yet in practice. It is crucial to stress the matters as article 419 of the AA, along with articles 417 and 418 provides the opportunity of cognition of the concept of legal approximation, at the same time, serving for transparency of the process: it is not enough for legal approximation to outline the EU standards in the national legislation and official publication thereof but legal approximation requires enactment of the acts the term of which shall coincide with the terms stipulated under the annexes to the AA. For instance, if the annex of the AA provides that the directive N92/58 on the Maternity Leave²⁹ shall be implemented within the term of three years, it means that the date of fulfillment of the commitment shall be calculated as from September 1, 2014; the provisions of hereof Directive should be integrated into the legislation of Georgia before 2017; the European standards reflected in the national legislation should be effective in practice in 2017. Legal approximation – reflection of the European standards in the legislation and practice of Georgia implies the policy conduct which would have the impact the national practice and at the market. However, *legal approximation excludes the impact at the extent which cannot ensure achievement of the outlined goals and bring the desired outcomes.**

3.6. Special Field of Legal Approximation

Article 55 of Chapter 4 of Title IV (DCFTA) of the AA³⁰ indicates to the *principles and procedures* of the legal measures subject to be undertaken by Georgia in view of gradual approximation in the field of *sanitary*,

²⁹ The Directive 92/85/EEC of the Council of October 19, 1992 concerning protection of the health and safety of women in the workplace when pregnant or after they have recently given birth and women who are breastfeeding (the 10th individual Directive 89/391/EEC in the context of the Article 16(1) of the Directive).

³⁰ Article 55, gradual approximation, AA.

*phytosanitary and animal welfare (food safety) field. Pursuant to the article, no later than six months after the entry into force the Agreement, Georgia shall submit a list to the EU of sanitary and phytosanitary, animal welfare and other legislative measures (SPS legislative list). On hereof basis, the field of food safety, which is one of the most costly and delicate spheres, has been subject to the special regulation regime. The AA does not provide the EU law by Georgia to carry out legal approximation. The AA is flexible in regulation of the food safety field as it gave opportunity to Georgia establish the legal list (out of the AA) and communicate it later with the EU. The SPS legislative list has been approved in March 2017³¹ in three years upon conclusion of the Association Agreement. The list covers more than 100 EU directives, regulations and decisions and certain terms for enforcement thereof. *The list has been approved by the Sanitary and Phytosanitary Subcommittee. SPS legislative list has become an integral part of the Association Agreement at the extent that no direct integration/reflection thereof to the AA was necessary.**

3.7. Amending the Annexes without Ratification

Pursuant to paragraph 2 of article 65 of the AA, the SPS Subcommittee shall have the following functions: *(c) to review the Annexes IV to XII of the Agreement; (d) to modify by means of an endorsement decision Annexes IV to XII to the Agreement.* Pursuant to Article 418, *In line with the goal of gradual approximation by Georgia to EU law, the Association Council shall periodically revise and update Annexes to this Agreement.* Issuing from these provisions, the AA grants the power of revision to the SPS Subcommittee.

Pursuant to paragraph 6, article 20 of the Organic Law of Georgia on Normative Acts, *amendments to a normative act shall be prepared, adopted*

³¹ The Decision of the Sub-Committee on Sanitary and Phytosanitary of March 7, 2017, N1/2017 on Amendments to the Annex XI-B to the Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and Georgia, of the other part, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/3650833> (accessed 12 April 2019).

(issued) and entered into force under the procedure determined for the preparation, adoption (issuance) and entering into force of the act which is amended. This is fundamental norm for the legislative process in Georgia. The amendments are introduced to normative acts in the form as they have been adopted. Hence, changes/amendments to international agreements fall under this procedure. The ratification has been defined as the form of expression of approval for mandatory recognition of the Association Agreement. Pursuant to the Organic law of Georgia on Normative Acts, the changes thereto shall be introduced by means of ratification. However, as noted, the Association Agreement has established the different regime and the exceptional rule.

In regards with the abovementioned, it is paramount to answer the question why it appeared necessary for revision of the annexes to establish the special regime? Pursuant to Article 431 of the AA, *“the Parties shall ratify or approve this agreement in accordance with their own procedures. The instruments of ratification or approval shall be deposited with the General Secretariat of the Council of the European Union. This Agreement shall enter into force on the first day of the second month following the date of the deposit of the last instrument of ratification or approval”*. It was stressed above that the parties of the AA are the EU, its Member States and EURATOM. Hence, entry of the AA into force required ratification instrument of all 28 EU states, like Georgia. This procedure took two years until the final ratification instrument has been deposited to the General Secretariat of the Council of the European Union. The procedure was commenced in 2014 and accomplished in 2016. *It is clear that multiplicity of the AA parties, complicated and long procedure of entry of the AA into force, undertaking the same procedures for introduction of the changes thereto would be the disproportional mechanism to the decision-making, on the one hand, and hindering to the fulfillment of the AA, on the other hand. Thus, the AA has established the legally flexible rule allowing rapid decision-making and timely implementation.*

3.8. Incorporation of the Commitments of the Association Agreement in the National Legislation

The structure of the Association Agreement consists of the general provisions, annexes, and the protocols. *The annexes provide the titles and not the content/norms of the EU secondary legislation.* Legal approximation envisaged under the annexes is necessary for achievement of the objectives stipulated in general provisions of the AA. The annexes also provide the terms of implementation of the EU secondary legislation. Thus Georgia bears no obligation of approximation prior to accounting of determined timeframe. Recalling the abovementioned, the provisions of the AA and the EU legislation (directives, regulations, decisions and recommendations) cannot be recognized as the self-enforcing norms. Even in case of expire of the terms and not-fulfillment of obligations, the EU legal acts cannot be used directly by Courts or other state bodies. Based on the sense of the legal approximation, European norms/standards should be written in Georgian legislation and implemented in practice. *Hence, fully entering into force of the AA does not mean the opportunity of application of the AA provisions and AA annexes by Georgian citizens or the state agencies. EU legislation needs to be incorporated in the national legislation.*

3.9. Significance of Translation of EU Legislation

The annexes as well as the SPS legislative list provide hundreds of the EU legal acts not yet translated into Georgian language. Neither the content thereof is scrutinized and analyzed. Reflection of the standards defined by EU secondary legislation in Georgian legislation could not be carried out without study of the content of them. It is characteristic for legal approximation. *Hence, the content of the EU legal acts becomes important for the governmental agencies of Georgia upon approximation. Commencement of legal approximation enables cognition of the content of the EU legal act and identification of the range of concrete obligation.* Upon transposition of the EU standards, it is not excluded that Georgia, without adaptation, reflects the provisions of the EU secondary legislation to the

national legislation. It is of rare nature and mostly occurs upon adoption of regulations (especially in the field of food and product safety), basically, transposition of the EU legal acts in the national legislation, the national practice and specification conditions methods of formulation, style of administration and determination of liability measures. In both cases, the EU legal acts shall be mandatorily translated into Georgian.

The AA stresses the importance of the translation, namely: *The EU acts shall serve as a basis for preparation of a table of correspondence. To this end, the version in force at the time of approximation shall be used. Particular attention shall be paid to precise translation into the national language, as linguistic imprecisions may lead to misinterpretation, in particular, if they concern the scope of the law.* On the basis of the AA, the Government of Georgia on February 7, 2014, adopted the ordinance N186 *Concerning the Measures to be undertaken in view of Effective Implementation of the Georgia-EU Association Agreement including the Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Agreement.*³² Pursuant to the Ordinance: *the LEPL Legislative Herald of Georgia at the Ministry of Justice of Georgia shall translate the respective EU law.*

3.10. Value of the Definitions of the European Court of Justice

Application of the EU law shall be regulated on the basis of Article 355 of TFEU. The decisions of the Court of Justice of the European Union shall cover the territories envisaged under TFEU. The EU law and CJEU case law shall not apply to Georgia. However, pursuant to the AA, in exceptional cases, penetration of the CJEU is admissible the legal space of Georgia. The AA, namely DCFTA regulates the dispute resolution procedures. The dispute shall be resolved amicably by the parties. In case of failure the dispute shall be directed to the arbitration panel. It is underlined: *Where a dispute raises a question of interpretation of a provision of Union law the arbitration panel shall not decide the question, but request the Court of Justice of the European Union to give a ruling on the question. In such cases, the deadlines*

³² <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/2250269> (accessed 12 April 2019).

*applying to the rulings of the arbitration panel shall be suspended until the Court of Justice of the European Union has given its ruling.*³³ The decision of the latter is of the mandatory nature for the arbitration panel.

3.11. Association Agreement – Politically Valuable and Prevailing International Treaty

Taking the legal order into account, all international agreements bear the equal legal force. Hence, none of the international agreements concluded by Georgia shall prevail. However, considering the nature and the characteristics of the AA, it should be regarded as politically prevailing and privileged treaty expressed in legal context. It is important to use the AA as the assessment criterion and the object of comparison upon conclusion of other international agreements by Georgia. It shall bear the dominant legal position and other international agreements shall not come in confrontation thereto. As mentioned above, legal approximation serves as the driving force for European integration; legal approximation is required in the spheres of the EU Law regulating the functioning of the EU internal market; thus, AA objectives can be achieved solely through the establishment of the EU market standards in Georgia. If the AA standards are not taking into account upon conclusion of other international agreements and if Georgia attempts to develop own internal market by various approaches other than the EU standards – it will delay the implementation of the AA/DCFTA. Even one single precedent of conclusion of other international agreements by Georgia approaching other than the AA attitudes, it will be enough to make the AA as the void act. *As initially mentioned the Association Agreement is of the monopolistic nature and leaves none of the fields of public relations beyond regulation. Georgia expressed its will to regulate every field in line with European standards. If Georgia concludes other international agreements the regulation spheres of which come under coverage of the AA scope, Georgia shall make the AA prevailing and in the angle of the assumed commitments, restrict the freedom of the content of agreement.*

³³ Article 267, Referrals to the Court of Justice of the European Union, AA.

4. Formats of Political Dialogue and Institutional Matters

The Governments of Georgia and the EU bear the responsibility for implementation of the Association Agreement. Taking the dimension of the AA into account, the agreement stipulates various formats of the political dialogue between the parties, namely establishment of the institutions with the decision-making power.

The *Association Council* is the highest body of the political dialogue composed of the Ministers from Georgia and the EU (in any configuration). It is convened on a regular basis once per annum. The Association Council is entitled to make the decisions binding for the parties and amend the annexes of the AA without prejudice to any provision of title IV (Trade and Trade-related Matters).³⁴

The *Association Committee* is assigned to render assistance to the Association Council in exercise of its functions and duties. It is composed of the high officials of both parties. The Association Council is empowered to delegate any authority to the Associate Committee, including the power to make the binding decisions. The AA stipulates establishment of the Association Committee of the special configuration, namely the Association Committee on Trade and Trade-related Matters. The issue of set-up of other Committees shall be reviewed by the Association Council.³⁵

The *Association Sub-Committees* are set up and established within the requirements of title IV (DCFTA) of the AA. These Sub-Committees are as follows:

- Sanitary and Phytosanitary Sub-Committee (SPS Sub-Committee);³⁶
- Trade and Sustainable Development Sub-Committee;³⁷
- Customs Sub-Committee;³⁸

³⁴ Articles 403-406, AA.

³⁵ Articles 407-409, AA.

³⁶ Article 65, AA.

³⁷ Articles 240-243, AA.

³⁸ Article 74, AA.

- Geographical Indications Sub-Committee.³⁹

The Sub-Committees are accountable to the Trade and Trade-related Association Sub-Committee. The Sub-Committees are entitled to make the decisions in every case stipulated under the Agreement. The Association Committee is as well authorized to set up other Sub-Committees in view of summarizing of the progress achieved within the regular dialogues envisaged under title V (Economic Cooperation) and Title VI (Other Fields of Cooperation) of the AA.⁴⁰

The *Parliamentary Association Committee* (PAC) constitutes the *forum* for the meetings of the MPs of the European Parliament and Georgian Parliament for exchange of the opinions. The functions of the PAC are limited mostly with the issue of the recommendations to the Association Council.⁴¹ Scarcity of the role of the Parliament is conditioned, on the one hand, with the fact that the mostly the responsibility for the implementation of the AA is imposed on the executive authority/Government and, on the other hand, with the fact that the European Parliament historically is characterized with limited authority – to adopt the individual/independent binding legal acts on the EU affairs and policy.

The *Civil Society Platform* is established by the civil society of the EU and Georgia. The AA is unique in terms as well that it regulates not only the format of the Governmental and Parliamentary cooperation but the role of the civil society in AA implementation. The Civil Society Platform shall be informed about the decisions of the Association Council. It is entitled to issue the recommendations to the Association Council. The Association Committee and the PAC shall ensure regular communication with the civil society representatives to hear their opinion about achievement of the AA objectives.⁴²

³⁹ Article 179, AA.

⁴⁰ Article 409, AA.

⁴¹ Articles 410-411, AA.

⁴² Article 413, AA.

Conclusion

Taking the format and the capacity of the article into account, all the legal peculiarities and characteristics have been outlined making the AA as the international treaty of the special and unique nature. It is paramount to get cognizant with the AA and interpret its provisions within the EU historical processes, policy, formation and development of the law. Such a method of understanding of the AA serves as the guarantee for effective application and implementation thereof. Hence, study of the features and characteristics of the AA bears the legal, as well as the practical value.

As the final recommendation, the AA shall be conferred with special status in the political and legal space of Georgia. By force of the customary law, it shall become the legally dominant in regards with other international agreements of Georgia.

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The Governmental Ordinance of September 3, 2014, N1516 on approval of the National Action Plan on Implementation of the Association Agreement and Association Agenda for 2014.

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Comparative Assessment of Social Indicators of Azerbaijan Republic as a Reflection of Sustainable Development Policy

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the assessing the state of implementation of sustainable development goals in the Republic of Azerbaijan based on the analysis of social indicators. The indicators of the development of social sphere such as the level of poverty, the elimination of differences in income and consumption, as well as gender differences have been analyzed. The assessment of the state in these areas was carried out on the basis of the indicators such as poverty level, Gini index, Quintile ratio, as well as indicators of women's education as a factor forming gender development indices. Studies have shown that poverty in the Republic of Azerbaijan has been reduced and is at a low level, comparable to the indicators of economically developed countries, implementing a successful social policy. Also successful can be considered a policy in the area of eliminating sharp differences in income distribution among the population. The analysis also showed that the level of education among women in Azerbaijan is high and this indicator is higher than in some countries, members of G 7, the European Union. These data indicate the success of national social policies aimed at meeting the goals of sustainable development.

Keywords: sustainable development, sustainable development goals, Gini index, poverty alleviation, gender equality.

Sustainable development and its inclusiveness is the most important task in the modern public administration¹. The importance of this direction has increased due to the fact that significant economic problems transforming into social contradictions and conflicts arose in a global world.

¹ http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Forum_Ingrowths_2018.pdf (accessed 27.02.2018).

First of all, this concerns the negative tendencies, which are characterized by international development institutions, such as “development without a future”, “development without equality” and “development with technology gap”². A similar situation is reflected in the fact that levels of economic development, and, accordingly, the difference in incomes and consumption in different countries, expressed as GDP per capita, can differ tens and sometimes hundreds of times. World Bank reports on economic and social indicators of developed and developing countries testify to this³. Inequality in income distribution among various segments of the population is also quite large in a number of countries. According to the UN, in some countries of Latin America and Africa, the average incomes of 20 percent of the richest in the country can exceed the average income of the poorest 20 percent by tenfold⁴.

Under these conditions, the 70th Anniversary Session of the United Nations, held in New York in September 2015, adopted a Sustainable Development Agenda and approved sustainable development goals that countries and world society as a whole are yet to be achieved by 2030. Solution of social problems such as eliminating hunger and poverty, reducing inequality, including gender inequality, are essential components of sustainable development goals. Meeting these challenges at the national and regional levels are also key objectives for inclusive development⁵. This paper provides data characterizing the reduction of poverty and the elimination of sharp differences in incomes and rate of consumption in the Republic of Azerbaijan and comparative assessment of these indicators with the countries of the region.

² U. K. Alakbarov, *Fundamentals of Inclusive Development Management* (Baku: Tehsil, 2018); Azerbaijan Human Development Report, UNDP, 1996.

³ <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.PP.KD?locations=KE> (accessed 20.02.2018).

⁴ http://hdr.undp.org/sites/default/files/2016_human_development_report.pdf (accessed 15.03.2019).

⁵ http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Forum_Ingrowths_2018.pdf (accessed 27.02.2018).

Among the sustainable development goals, a significant place is also given to the issues of eliminating gender disparities. Analysis of the characteristics of eliminating gender disparities in Azerbaijan and in the countries of the region is also the subject of this paper. This analysis is based on statistics and official reports of international development institutions, including the UN and World Bank.

Less than three decades have passed since the Republic of Azerbaijan regained its independence. The first years of independence were spent in difficult political, economic and social conditions, aggravated by the occupation by Armenia of 20 percent of the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the presence in the country of one million refugees and internally displaced persons. This led to the fact that there was a high level of poverty in the country. Therefore, the priority task in the field of national development and ensuring the sustainability of this process was poverty alleviation. Special poverty alleviation programs with participation of national and international organizations has been implemented in the country⁶. As a result of the lead works the level of poverty in the country has been significantly reduced. According to the World Bank, the poverty rate in the country was 49 percent in 2000⁷. Currently, the poverty rate in the country is significantly reduced and is 5 percent (Figure 1). An analysis of the reducing the level of poverty in the Republic of Azerbaijan showed that this process became particularly intense after 2003, when over the next five years the poverty level was reduced from 44.7 percent to 13.2 percent, i.e. more than three times. In subsequent years, the rate of decline of poverty has kept the high pace and currently this rate is at 5 percent (Figure 1).

⁶ M. Efendiyev, "Impact of the United Nations Development Program on Sustainable Development of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Report 1: Shifting from emergency assistance to development programs," In *Public Administration: Theory and Practice*, The Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Baku, № 2, 58 (2017): 227-233.

⁷ From Salvation to Progress, Report of the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2018, 642.

Figure 1. The dynamics of poverty alleviation in the Republic of Azerbaijan, the percentage of the population⁸

A comparative assessment showed that the indicated low level of poverty is characteristic for highly developed countries which implement successful social policy. In accordance with the statistics of the Organization for Economic Development and Cooperation, this level of poverty is characteristic for countries belonging to this group and implementing successful policy. The indicated level of poverty is characteristic for economically developed countries of Northern and Central Europe⁹. Structural reforms carried out in the Republic of Azerbaijan also played a significant role in the implementation of this task¹⁰.

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ <https://databank.worldbank.org/data/reports.aspx?source=2&series=SI.POV.NAHC&country=> (accessed 20.02.2018).

¹⁰ Good Governance through Civil Service Reform, Project Document, United Nations Development Program Office in Azerbaijan, Baku, 2011.

One of the important requirements that have been formed for sustainable development is the elimination of the sharp differences in income and consumption observed in different regions and within individual countries. In compliance with the requirements of the international standards, the assessment of the nature of the distribution of income among the population is carried out on the basis of indicators such as the Gini index, Quintile ratio, and Palma index¹¹. Of these indicators, characterizing the features of income distribution among the population, the Gini index is most often used. Low scores of this index are considered as positive indicators of successful social policy and the absence of sharp differences in income distribution among the population.

The analysis showed that projects in the field of sustainable development implemented in the Republic of Azerbaijan, while reducing poverty, has also led to the decline in the Gini index. A comparative analysis showed that the Gini Index in the Republic of Azerbaijan is lower than that of the representatives of the “Group of seven” (G-7) such as the United States, Canada, France and Japan, as well as the averages for this group of countries¹².

The Republic of Azerbaijan is also a regional leader in terms of quintile analysis (Figure 2).

The data shown in Figure 2 show that the Republic of Azerbaijan, along with Kazakhstan, are leaders in this region in the implementation of that part of social policy, which is associated with the exclusion of sharp differences in income and consumption within one country. Analysis of other indicators characterizing the distribution of income among the population, also confirmed this pattern. This, in particular, was found in

¹¹ http://hdr.undp.org/sites/default/files/2018_human_development_statistical_update_ru.pdf (accessed 20.02.2018).

¹² U. K. Alakbarov, J. E. Lawrence, “Energy efficiency as an indicator of sustainable development policy: the Azerbaijan experience,” *Journal of Sustainable Development* (Canada, ISSN 1913-9071), v. 10, №3 (2017): 187-193.

comparing the social policy indicators such as the Quintile ratio and the Palma indicator¹³.

Figure 2. Quintile ratio indices of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the countries of the region¹⁴

In achieving the goals of sustainable development, the great importance attached to the elimination of gender differences. The analysis showed that in the Republic of Azerbaijan, gender development indices and parameters defining it exceed global and regional averages¹⁵. This is also confirmed in the gender development indicator like the proportion of women with at least secondary education (Figure 3).

¹³ http://hdr.undp.org/sites/default/files/2016_human_development_report.pdf (accessed 15.03.2019).

¹⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵ http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Forum_Ingrowths_2018.pdf (accessed 27.02.2018).

Education and the elimination of differences in this field are the most important conditions for sustainable development goals. In this regard, the indicator of the level of education of women is the most important condition for achieving the goals of sustainable development.

The data presented in Figure 3 show that the policy pursued in the Azerbaijan Republic in the field of gender development meets modern requirements.

Figure 3. Women with at least secondary education in the Azerbaijan and selected countries of Europe¹⁶

Comparison of the level of education of women in the countries of the region and Southern European states, as the most important factor in eliminating gender disparities, testify to this (Figure 3). As a result, according to UN data published in 2018, human development indices, calculated on the basis of a gender factor in the Republic of Azerbaijan meet modern requirements. The high mark of the country's achievements in the field of inclusive development testifies to this.

¹⁶ Ibid.; U. K. Alakbarov, *Op. cit.*

Thus, the conducted studies have shown that the policy implemented in the Republic of Azerbaijan in the area of eliminating differences, including gender, leads to significant progress in the implementation of sustainable development goals and the formation of sustainable developing society¹⁷.

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¹⁷ http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Forum_Ingrowths_2018.pdf (accessed 27.02.2018); U. K. Alakbarov, *Op. cit.*

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Cooperation of Uzbekistan with Regional Organizations in the Field of Women's Rights Promotion and Protection

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the issues of the development of regional cooperation of Uzbekistan in the field of women's rights protection. International cooperation of Uzbekistan on women's rights issues is mainly developing within the UN with UN treaty bodies and specialized agencies, funds and programs. Cooperation of Uzbekistan on women's rights within regional organizations is not so intensive. However, Uzbekistan develops cooperation on women's rights with OSCE, EU, SCO, ADB and OIC as well. Manly the cooperation is carried out in the form of projects and events as well as research and publications. There are no regional documents on human rights or women's rights ratified by Uzbekistan. Some efforts and initiatives are taken to form Asian system on human rights. One of such kind of initiatives was the Asian forum on human rights organized in 2018 in Uzbekistan which resulted in the adoption of Samarkand Declaration on Human Rights, which pays special attention to women's rights as well.

Keywords: regional cooperation, women's rights, Asian system on human rights, Asian forum on human rights, Samarkand Declaration on human rights.

Introduction

The modern period of historical development is marked by the fact that women's rights occupy a special place in the complex of human rights. The recognition by the international community of the importance of women's rights is evidenced by the fact that over two thirds of the states of the world are parties to the 1979 Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women.¹ Ensuring women's rights is one of the main goals in the Agenda for Sustainable Development till 2030. This agenda includes 17 goals and 169 objectives. In particular, the goal of sustainable

¹ To 2019, the Convention is ratified by 197 states.

development 5 sounds like “Ensuring gender equality and the empowerment of all women and girls”.

Today issues of ensuring the rights of women are reflected in the constitutions of almost all states of the world are enshrined in their legislation and occupy an important place in national development plans. The realization by states that the rights of women are an integral part of human rights leads to a new understanding of the content of women’s rights, an awareness of the need to ensure them with all states and the definition of mechanisms for the protection of women’s rights.²

This issue is of particular importance for Uzbekistan. Over the past years, the Republic of Uzbekistan acceded to 80 main international documents in the field of ensuring human rights, including the 1979 UN Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women. The equal rights of women and men are enshrined in the Basic Law of the country – the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted in 1992. A significant amount of legislation has been passed in order to ensure human rights, where special attention is paid to women’s rights. An institutional environment has been created in the republic for the implementation of the constitutional principle of equality between women and men. Thus, in 1991, the Women’s Committee of Uzbekistan was established which serves as the national mechanism for the advancement of women.

It is also important to note that in the Uzbekistan’s Action Strategy for 2017-2021 special attention is drawn to women’s issues.³ The fourth direction of the Strategy provides for the adoption of measures for the further implementation of comprehensive measures to improve family health, protect mothers and children, expand the access of mothers and children to quality medical services, provide them with specialized and

² I. E. Rubina, “International Protection of Women’s Rights” (Dissertation abstract for PhD Degree, Petrozavodsk: Petrozavodsk State University, 2001).

³ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017, No. UP-4947 “On the Strategy of Actions in Five Priority Directions of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021”, <http://www.lex.uz/ru/docs/3107042> (accessed 18.04.2019).

high-tech medical care, reduce infant and child mortality, and increase the socio-political activity of women, strengthening their role in government and society, ensuring the employment of women, graduates of professional colleges, their widespread involvement in business, further strengthening the foundations of the family. In addition, it should be noted that, based on the global Sustainable Development Goals, national sustainable development goals and targets for the period up to 2030 have been adopted.⁴

Considering that domestic mechanisms for the protection of human rights are complemented by international legal forms of ensuring them, it is important to study the international legal protection of human rights.⁵ This determines the necessity of the further development and expansion of international legal cooperation in this area.

Uzbekistan's international cooperation in the field of ensuring women's rights is developing mainly within the UN. In particular, cooperation with treaty bodies and UN specialized agencies, such as ILO, WHO and UNESCO, as well as UN funds and programs (UNFPA, UNICEF, UNDP) is developing. The forms of cooperation are diverse – from participation in international treaties to the implementation of projects aimed at solving specific problems.

The most important task in the field of cooperation within the UN is to improve the quality of the national reports submitted by Uzbekistan. To this end, it is important to develop quantitative and qualitative indicators for assessing the implementation of the provisions of the Convention and to consolidate the legal obligation of state bodies to keep records and ensure data collection taking into account these indicators. The presence of such indicators will provide more specific comments on States, which will improve the quality of the implementation of the concluding observations.

⁴ Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of October 20, 2018, No. 841 "On Measures for Implementing National Goals and Objectives in the Field of Sustainable Development for the Period until 2030", <http://lex.uz/ru/docs/4013358> (accessed 20.04.2019).

⁵ E. Lukasheva (ed.), *Human Rights. Textbook for Universities* (Moscow: Norma-Infra, 1999), 4 [edited in Russian].

Another objective is to increase the efficiency of ongoing projects in the framework of cooperation with UN agencies.

Taking into account the provisions of the Uzbekistan's Action Strategy for 2017-2021 and the intention of Uzbekistan to be elected to the UN HRC, it is important to strengthen the representation of Uzbekistan in the relevant international structures, not only at the universal, but also at the regional level.

Cooperation with Regional Organizations in the Field of Human Rights

Less intensive cooperation in the field of women's rights is observed within the framework of interregional and regional organizations (OSCE, SCO, EU, ADB and OIC), as a rule, in the form of events, trainings, publications and implementation of projects aimed at solving specific problems. It determines necessity to study the possibilities of further development of cooperation with regional organizations in the field of women's rights.

Uzbekistan is not part of the existing regional human rights systems. This, in turn, to some extent explains the fact that Uzbekistan's cooperation in the field of women's rights is developing most actively and fruitfully within the UN framework, rather than at the regional level.

Despite the absence of an Asian regional system for the protection of human rights, Uzbekistan's cooperation in the field of human rights, including women's rights, is developing within a number of other regional and interregional organizations.

In particular, cooperation with the Asian Development Bank (ADB) can be noted.⁶ The joint programs and projects with ADB in Uzbekistan focus on 4 key areas: agriculture, promotion of private entrepreneurship, regional cooperation in transport and customs transit, and improvement of social services with a focus on protecting children and basic education. Periodically, the ADB conducts a gender assessment of the country, which

⁶ Uzbekistan is a member of ADB since 1995.

describes changes in the situation of women and men in Uzbekistan, as the country is rapidly moving from a state-controlled agricultural economy to a market system.

It is important to note the cooperation of Uzbekistan with the EU⁷ in this regard. The European Union is implementing the project “Promoting women’s rights through increased protection and involvement in the labor force” that will last two years.⁸ It will focus on strengthening the role of women’s non-governmental non-profit organizations, especially in rural areas, in promoting human rights, gender equality and effective governance. It is implemented by the Agency for Technical Cooperation and Development of France. In addition, in accordance with the “Action Strategy for the Further Development of Uzbekistan”, the project will contribute to job creation and the empowerment of women in rural areas. It is envisaged that it will also help prevent domestic violence by expanding opportunities and protecting women’s economic and social rights.⁹ The Women’s Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the French Agency for Technical Cooperation and Development (ACTED) launched a project to strengthen the role of women by protecting their rights and increasing their labor activity in Uzbekistan. The project is implemented with financial support from the European Union. In order to strengthen the role of women’s NGOs in promoting human rights, gender equality and effective governance in Uzbekistan, the project will focus on strengthening the capacity of civil society by expanding legal opportunities, protecting women’s economic and social interests, and preventing violations of their rights. It should be noted that, in accordance with the “Action Strategy for the Further Development of Uzbekistan 2017-2021”, the project will

⁷ The official representation of the European Union was accredited in Uzbekistan on May 31, 2011.

⁸ https://eeas.europa.eu/delegations/uzbekistan/48001/returning-path-promoting-access-human-rights-vulnerable-woman-and-men_ru (accessed 20.04.2019).

⁹ <https://podrobno.uz/cat/obchestvo/es-zaymetsya-razvitiem-grazhdanskogo-obshchestva-i-zashchitoy-prav-zhenshchin-v-uzbekistane/> (accessed 20.04.2019).

contribute to the creation of jobs and the empowerment of women in rural areas.¹⁰

Actively developing in the framework of interregional organizations, thus, regional cooperation in the field of women's rights is developing within the OSCE.¹¹ Cooperation with the Organization and its institutions is carried out at different levels and covers a wide range of issues and problems. OSCE projects implemented in Uzbekistan are aimed at providing technical assistance to institutions of the republic in the development of their institutional capacities in the areas of security, sustainable economic, environmental and social development.¹²

The OSCE recognizes that equality between women and men is a key prerequisite for consolidating peace, sustainable democracy and economic development. In co-operation with partners in the field, the OSCE develops and implements projects throughout the region for the empowerment of women and for building local capacities, including expert ones, on gender issues. It cooperates with government agencies in reviewing legislation and helps strengthen national mechanisms that ensure equal rights for women and men. In view of the above, the development of co-operation with the OSCE on the issues of ensuring women's rights can be a promising area of co-operation.

Another example in the framework of interregional cooperation is cooperation within the Shanghai Cooperation organization (SCO). Since 2017, an international congress of women of the SCO and BRICS countries has been held. The first International Congress of Women of the SCO and BRICS countries in 2017 was devoted to the theme "The role of women in modern society: cooperation in politics, economics, science, education and culture." The program of the Congress included discussions on supporting women's entrepreneurship, the role of women in strengthening humanitarian cooperation, and also in achieving global goals for sustainable

¹⁰ <https://www.uzdaily.uz/ru/post/37919> (accessed 20.04.2019).

¹¹ Uzbekistan is a member of the OSCE (CSCE) since February 26, 1992.

¹² <https://www.osce.org/ru/combating-human-trafficking> (accessed 20.04.2019).

development. Special attention will be paid to the role of women in the economic development of society. Within the framework of the Congress, a public-private dialogue “Women and the economy” was held, which will bring together representatives of business and government.¹³ More than 300 representatives of women’s organizations from India, Kazakhstan, China, Mongolia, Pakistan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, South Africa and other countries took part in the work of the Congress.

Cooperation with the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) deserves special attention and careful study.¹⁴ In recent years, a number of human rights instruments have been adopted within the framework of the OIC and at the stage of development and discussion. The activity and role of Uzbekistan within the framework of this organization, especially in the field of cooperation in ensuring human rights, is evidenced by the fact that Uzbekistan is represented in the OIC bodies for human rights. Uzbekistan has quite a solid experience of cooperation in the field of human rights and is able to make a real contribution to strengthening the activities of the OIC in the field of ensuring human rights. The development of cooperation with the OIC in this direction is of particular importance for Uzbekistan in connection with the role of the religious factor in ensuring human rights.

Development of Cooperation in the Field of Human Rights in the Asian Region or Formation of the Asian Human Rights System

The value of regional systems for the protection of human rights is undoubtedly great. Regional mechanisms for the protection of human rights are the foundation for the development of an international system for the protection of human rights. As an intermediary between the universal and

¹³ <https://uz.sputniknews.ru/world/20170628/5709919/kongress-jenshin-stran-shos-v-novo-sibirsk.html> (accessed 20.04.2019).

¹⁴ The Republic of Uzbekistan was admitted to the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) as an observer at an extraordinary meeting of the foreign ministers of the member states in New York in October 1995. Uzbekistan became a full member of the Organization on October 2, 1996. Since 2003 Uzbekistan has been a member of a specialized institution of the OIC – Islamic Development Bank.

national levels, regional systems limit the exclusive jurisdiction of states over their citizens,¹⁵ thereby drawing the attention of a specific geographic region to the occurrence of the violation. A number of researchers are inclined to believe that regional mechanisms for the protection of human rights not only complement the universal, but in some respects more effectively ensure the protection of fundamental human rights.¹⁶ Moreover, according to Ron K. M. Smith, they may be competing with the universal, thereby undermining its authority.¹⁷

The question of how many regional systems for the protection of human rights stand out today is rather controversial. The scientific community in this matter is divided into two groups.

Representatives of the first group believe that it is fair to speak only of the three regional systems that are fully functioning and have sufficient components to monitor and supervise the observance of the protection of human rights. As a rule, they consider only three regional systems that meet the above requirements – European, Inter-American and African.¹⁸ These researchers note, however, that other systems are still in the formative stage.

Another group of scientists, on the contrary, identifies six regional systems for the protection of human rights: European, inter-American, African, Arab, Asian, and the system existing within the CIS. Researchers put

¹⁵ F. Kidanemariam, *Enforcement of Human Rights under Regional Mechanisms: A Comparative Analysis. LLM Theses and Essays* (2006), 80.

¹⁶ O. Nebratenko, *Mechanisms to Protect the Rights and Freedoms of Man and Citizen in the Russian Federation* (Rostov, 2015), 153.

¹⁷ R. K. M. Smith, *Textbook on International Human Rights* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2003), 83.

¹⁸ V. P. Salnikov, V. V. Tsmay, "Modern System of Protection of Human Rights," *Jurisprudence*, No. 1 (1999): 82-98.; T. A. Vasilyeva et al., *Human Rights: Textbook* (Moscow: Norma-Infra, 2011).

all the regional systems without exception in one row, while, of course, speaking of the significant shortcomings of some of them.¹⁹

In fact, other systems (Arabic, Asian, and the CIS system) cannot meet the requirements for all systems. They do not have a judicial body that is fundamental to the functioning of any regional system, which means that they are indeed at the stage of formation. By the way, the beginning for the formation and development of these systems has already been made – in each of them there is a regional document reflecting the fundamental rights and freedoms of citizens.

It seems that in such regional systems there should be:

- a court of human rights that deals with specific cases concerning the applicants' complaints about the violation of their rights;
- a commission (in some cases a committee) called upon to monitor the fulfillment by member states of their obligations in the area of the realization of human rights;
- a document reflecting the fundamental rights and freedoms of citizens of the region and signed by the member countries of the regional system.

The creation of highly efficient regional systems, which are an intermediate link between the national level of protection of human rights and the universal (international), as well as the entry of all states without exception into one or another regional system – the whole world community should strive for. The regional system acts as an independent guarantor of the restoration of the violated rights of an individual who has exhausted all possibilities of legal protection in his state.

Thus, today the system of universal cooperation of states on human rights is complemented by various forms of regional cooperation. In some respects, the forms of such cooperation are more effective and provide better protection of fundamental human rights and freedoms.

¹⁹ A. Kh. Abashidze (ed.), *Regional Systems for the Protection of Human Rights: Studies* (Moscow: RUDN, 2012); K. Bekyashev, *International Law: A Textbook for Bachelors* (Moscow: Prospect, 2014).

Uzbekistan and the Formation of the Asian Human Rights System

Of particular importance to Uzbekistan is the formation of the Asian human rights system. As such, the Asian system for the protection of human rights does not exist. As Professor A. X. Saidov correctly notes, “one of the obvious reasons for such a situation is the absence of a regional political grouping of the type such as the FOG in America, the Council of Europe in Europe, etc.”²⁰

However, recently the question of the formation of the Asian human rights system has been actively discussed. The formation of a subregional system within ASEAN can be noted. In particular, a proposal is being made to establish an Asian Court of Human Rights. The foundation for creating the Asian Court of Human Rights was laid back in 2012 when the Asian Declaration of Human Rights was signed, which was signed on November 18, 2012, by the leaders of the countries of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN). The most interesting feature of the ASEAN document is the emphasis on the fact that human rights must “be considered in a regional and national context.” This thesis contradicts the UN statement about the “universality” of fundamental human rights and freedoms. In 1993, the World Conference on Human Rights proclaimed “indisputable” that rights and freedoms are common to all members of the international community. Therefore, an absolute majority of the States Parties to the Vienna Conference did not support the supporters of the “Asian” concept. In this context, the wording in the new Asian Declaration of Human Rights looks like a direct application for withdrawal from the Western legal system and the first step towards creating alternative institutions to protect the rights of citizens living in societies with a more traditional way of life.

The most interesting feature of the ASEAN document is the emphasis on the fact that human rights must “be considered in a regional and national

²⁰ A. Saidov, *International Human Rights Law* (Moscow, 2002), 159.

context.” This thesis contradicts the UN statement about the “universality” of fundamental human rights.²¹

The weakness of the Asian declaration in its current form is the fact that only ASEAN countries have signed it so far, including Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand and Vietnam. A more serious obstacle to the creation of the Asian court on Human Rights is the lack of an institution in Asia like the Council of Europe.

On July 20, 2009, the Statute on the ASEAN Intergovernmental Commission on Human Rights was adopted, and in October 2009, at the 15th ASEAN Summit, members of the Commission were appointed.

In this regard it is of importance to emphasize the importance of the initiative of Uzbekistan to hold the Asian Forum on Human Rights.²² The proposal to hold this forum was voiced by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly.²³ On November 22-23, 2018, the Asian Forum on Human Rights, dedicated to the 70th anniversary of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, was held in the city of Samarkand. During the Forum, it was noted that human rights are not only a product of Western civilization, but the result of the contribution of all civilizations of the world.

It is important to emphasize that the Samarkand Declaration, adopted at the end of the Asian Forum, pays special attention to protecting the rights of vulnerable groups of the population, including women.²⁴ In addition, during the Forum, a number of initiatives to promote regional cooperation to ensure women’s rights were discussed, in particular, it was

²¹ http://rapsinews.ru/international_publication/20150311/273311056.html (accessed 20.04.2019).

²² Official website of the Asian Forum on Human Rights, <https://asianforum.uz/> (accessed 20.04.2019).

²³ Speech by President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 72nd session of the General Assembly of the United Nations, New York, September 19, 2017, https://www.un.int/uzbekistan/statements_speeches/address-he-mr-shavkat-mirziyoyev-president-republic-uzbekistan-unga-72 (accessed 20.04.2019).

²⁴ The text of the draft Declaration is available at <https://asianforum.uz/en/menu/samar-kand-declaration> (accessed 20.04.2019).

proposed to create a Regional Alliance of Women's Committees of Central Asian countries.

Thus, the significance of the Forum is that it has created a platform for discussing the formation of the Asian human rights system. The Forum noted the feasibility of holding such forums regularly, for example, once every two years. It seems that this Forum can serve as the basis for the formation of the subsequent Asian human rights system.

Conclusion

Thus, along with the UN, Uzbekistan is developing regional cooperation in the field of ensuring human rights. Issues of ensuring human rights, including women's rights, can be a very promising direction for the development of regional cooperation. At the same time, given the heterogeneity of the countries participating in regional organizations in which Uzbekistan participates, it is advisable to develop cooperation in the form of projects aimed at solving specific tasks (for example, projects to protect vulnerable groups of women) rather than accepting regional treaties, since their adoption may be complicated due to heterogeneity of Asian countries, as well as differences in culture and level of economic development.

It is also important to take initiatives to strengthen cooperation at the regional and interregional levels. One of the first such initiatives was the holding of the Asian Forum for Human Rights on a regular basis. The initiative of Uzbekistan to hold the Asian Forum on Human Rights played a major role in this. It is assumed that this forum will initiate new initiatives and deepen cooperation among Asian countries in the field of human rights, including women's rights.

Further development of regional cooperation in the field of human rights will contribute to more efficiently ensuring women's rights, since it will provide an opportunity to discuss existing problems from a different perspective, find other approaches to solving these problems, complement

existing protection mechanisms with new ones, and create new forms of cooperation.

Regarding bilateral cooperation, it is important to develop cooperation also at the bilateral level, for example, through the conclusion of memorandums of cooperation between the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan and national mechanisms for the promotion of women of foreign countries.

It is also important to ensure the development and promotion by Uzbekistan of international initiatives of Uzbekistan in this area, to strengthen the representation of Uzbekistan in relevant international structures, including representation in the UN Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women.

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Vasilyeva, T. A., et al. *Human Rights: Textbook*. Moscow: Norma-Infra, 2011.

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Correlation of the Autonomy of the European Union with Its International Obligations

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Abstract. Inheritance of the European Union (EU) to the principles of international law was one of the cornerstones of its foundational treaties reiterated in the Treaty of Lisbon. International instruments in a range of cases concerning the association agreements conferring the rights upon individuals evidenced in *Rush Portuguesa*, *Kziber*, *Kupferberg*. However, in a range of other cases, the EU strived to maintain independent stance concerning the international treaties and international organizations, as seen in *Intertanko and Kadi* cases mitigating availing to the effect of international treaties. This raises the question concerning the position of the EU in the international plane, together with a more general question over the status of the EU as a subject of international law. Seemingly not straightforward approach of the EU is linked with the *sui generis* vision of the EU in based on cessation of competences evident in direct effect. From the position of international law it is not extraordinary and complies with the practice of states within the international organisations. However, the question is whether the EU by referring to the own rules of application of the treaty is replacing international legal order (new legal order in Van Gent case), whole Art 47 of TFEU on legal personality require to avails itself to the standards of old international legal order of international law.

Keywords: EU external relations, EU legal personality, EU international legal order, EU autonomy.

An inheritance of the EU to the principles of international law was evident across its constitutional treaties. Art 3 s5 of the Treaty of Lisbon (ToL) in setting the goals of the European Union in relation with the wider world, establishes that the “Union shall uphold and promote its values and interests... as well as to the strict observance and the development of international law, including respect for the principles of the United Nations

Charter”.¹ Consequently, Art 21 of the Treaty of European Union (TEU) in formulating principles and objectives that define foreign policy of the European Union recognizes its inheritance in international relations to the same principles, which inspired its creation, *inter alia* the principles of the United Nations Charter and international law. More specifically s2 of the Art 21 of TEU defines that the Union in declaring the purposes of pursuing the common policies and actions in s(b) defines “consolidating and supporting... the principles of international law.”²

The compliance of EU to the general framework of international law is seen in its establishment through the way in which the general international law reserved a space. The European Union as it has developed out of the European Communities has some of its legal origins in the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT). The post-WWII GATT endeavored to establish the multilateral legal framework for the international trade without barriers and discrimination, with its corollary of Most-Favored-Nation (MFN) principle, under the tenet that preferential treatment of the trade partners was essential to lay the ground to economic integration. With attention to the emergence of the EU, GATT allowed derogation from this standard for closer integration in the form of a customs union or a free trade area.³ Incentivized by the economic benefits the EEC has adopted the customs union as the most advanced form of integration, aiming at the formation of the ‘common market’ with the free movement of factors of production.⁴

However, the absolute continuity of the inner values of the European Union externally in light on article 3 of ToL in external policy may be negligible. Notably, the area of free movement of goods is subject to the

¹ Treaty of Lisbon amending the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty establishing the European Community, OJ C306/01, 2007.

² Treaty on European Union (Consolidated version 2016), OJ C 202, 2016.

³ The Legal Texts: The Results of the Uruguay Round of Multilateral Trade Negotiations (Cambridge, U.K.; New York, N.Y.: Cambridge University Press, 1999), Reserve K4600.A35 R473 2010, Art XXIV GATT, 2010.

⁴ Piet Eeckhout, *EU External Relations Law* (2 edn, OUP, 2011), 11.

legal provisions authorizing the Member States to hold protectionist policy and take anti-dumping measures. Similarly, with regard to the freedom of movement of individuals, EU made it clear that the freedom of movement without internal borders at the same time mean stronger regime for external borders. Specific measures enabled under the reasoned defense of the internal market from external factors as per art 36 TFEU may have a purely internal rationale, as public policy, public morality, and public health. This necessitates greater consistency of the external actions of the European Union with its objectives in the promotion of its values in the international plane.

The EU is originated and can be best understood within the framework of international law due to its creation by the treaty as its conventional legal instrument. Adoption of the foundational and subsequent treaties complies with the standard procedure of the treaty-making under the international law. The EU has been created according to the 'rules of change' that define the change (of rules by secondary legislation or 'rules about the rules') of public international law, as created by the international treaties.⁵ However, from the viewpoint of its distinctive features, the formation of the EU was a result of conferring part of the powers by the Member States.⁶ This, however, may not very much differ from the formation of international organizations. However, the essential difference between EU and international law is in a greater degree of sovereign power that Member States confer as a result of joining the EU. No one international organization is sharing such a degree of sovereignty, and one of the main reasons of that is in the ability of EU institutions to expand their competence, not lastly through the jurisprudence of CJEU.⁷

Conversely, the distinctiveness of the EU in comparison with international organizations may be in greater involvement of the Member States in the activities of the Union, bolstered by the representation of the

⁵ Gerard Conway, *EU Law* (Routledge, 2015), 29.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 28.

⁷ *Supra* note 5, 30.

Member States in the key European Union institutions. This evidenced in European Council consisting of heads of the Member States and the Council formed of representatives of the Member State governments of various configurations. In the Union, this superiority based on the equitable grounds, specifically on the powers that the Member States to willfully secede competences based on the principle of “subsidiarity” and its coronary the principle of “conferral,” contending that the competences not conferred upon the Union remain with the Member States.

International treaties negotiated by the Union under the powers conferred by the EU Treaties considered as sources of EU law. Treaties related to the original EU Treaties and which either amend or enlarge them are themselves sources of EU Law. Within this category of sources of law are the Merger Treaty, Single European Act, the Treaty on European Union, the Treaty of Amsterdam, the Treaty of Nice, Treaty of Lisbon, and Treaty on Stability, Coordination and Governance, and the Treaty of Accession.⁸ The Accession Treaties adopted in the enlargement of the Union are also within this range. The accession treaty that is paving the way to the EU for the member state has been held to confer directly enforceable rights on the individuals. In *Rush Portuguesa v Office National d’Immigration* (Case 113/89) where provisions of Art 48 of TEU on the free movement of workers within the Community applied with attention to the workers of Portugal located in France for the purposes compliant with the agreement.⁹

In *Kupferberg* (104/81), the CJEU held that Art 21 of the EEC-Portugal Association Agreement was directly enforceable in the national courts. The principle of direct enforceability of such agreements has enabled the nationals of the states that are party to such agreements to enforce the agreement’s provision against the Member States. In *Kziber* (C-18/90), the CJEU found parts of the EEC-Morocco Cooperation Agreement directly enforceable, similarly to *Yousfi v Belgium* (C-58/93) that entitled non-EU

⁸ John Fairhurst, *Law of the European Union* (11th edn, Pearson, 2016), 68.

⁹ Case C-113/89 *Rush Portuguesa v Office National d’Immigration*, ECR, 1990, 1417.

nationals for social security benefits under the agreement.¹⁰ A provision in the agreement concluded by the Union with third states must be regarded as directly applicable following the wording, purpose and the nature of the agreement itself, where the provision contains clear and precise obligation, not subject to implementation, or adoption of any subsequent measure. However, in *Demirel v Stadt (C-12/86)*, CJEU held that the provisions of Association Agreement that the national of the associated state claimed, does no more than imposing on the Contracting Parties the general obligation to cooperate.¹¹ The decision was further rationalized in connotation that to achieve the aims of the Agreement the Union cannot directly confer the rights of individuals which are not already vested in them by other provisions of Agreement.

The Art 47 of the TEU eliminated the controversy over the status of the Union in the international plane, unequivocally declaring that the European Union has its legal personality. This allowed the Union to act under its name in the international plane, entitling the European Union to act as a fully-fledged subject of international law with diplomatic and treaty-making powers. This provision explicitly implicates that it is the Union that is going to act on behalf of the Member States in international relations and in relation to the third states in the areas of conferred powers.

The stance of the European Union in the international plane according to the jurisprudence of CJEU suggests that the EU may be diverting from the line of conformity with international law, allegedly holding a non-subordinative position in relations to the international organizations and with attention to the sources of international law. From the viewpoint of international law, it may raise the question over the consistency of the European Union with the principles of international law, with the revival of the debatable question, whether the European Union is equal or *sui generis* in the international plane? The considered approach may be rationalized in a greater focus on the maintaining of its internal

¹⁰ *Yousfi v Belgium (Case C-58/93)* [1994] ECR I-1353.

¹¹ *Case C-12/86 Demirel v Stadt Schwäbisch Gmünd* [1987] ECR 3719.

order and freedoms, and to a lesser extent on the conformity with the external standards in international plane. The approach is transposable in relation to the international treaties as authoritative sources of international law. The jurisprudence on this subject is mostly a concern of the claims on clarification of whether the international instrument in question causes direct effect or not. Doctrinally, the situation of EU law being directly applicable does not guarantee its direct effect, that requires the provision to be clear and unconditional.

In *International Association of Independent Tanker Owners (Intertanko) and Others v Secretary of State for Transport (C-308/06)*,¹² the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) signed in 1982 by the Community and approved by the Decision 98/392,¹³ thereby binding upon the Union and the provisions of that Convention have accordingly formed an integral part of the Union's legal order. However, the lack of legal effect of UNCLOS in EU was associated with its character not establishing the rules intended to apply directly and immediately to individuals and to confer upon them rights or freedoms capable of being relied upon against the states, irrespective to the attitude of the ship's flag state. It follows that the nature and the broad logic of UNCLOS prevented the Court from being able to assess the validity of a Community measure in light the convention in question. This suggests presuming, that the source itself in the extent of clarity of rule of the treaty may be instrumental in the applicability of the measure as a source of EU law. However, the focus on the direct effect may have its importance in the case of application of the dispute initiated by the individual, eliminating attention to the clear and unconditional form of the provisions, in the case of the dispute among the third state and the EU.

¹² Case C-308/06 *International Association of Independent Tanker Owners (Intertanko) and Others v Secretary of State for Transport* (2008) ECR I-4057.

¹³ 98/392/EC: Council Decision of 23 March 1998 concerning the conclusion by the European Community of the United Nations Convention of 10 December 1982 on the Law of the Sea and the Agreement of 28 July 1994 relating to the implementation of Part XI thereof OJ L 179, 23.6.1998, 1-2.

In *Portugal v Council (C-149/96)*,¹⁴ that WTO rules do not give rise to a direct effect due to the optional character of the provisions. The rationale presented by the Union was an unwillingness to bind itself with the rule that was not obligatory to the Member States.¹⁵ In *Kadi v Commission (T-85/09)*, misapplication by the EU of the United Nation's asset freezing sanctions was reasoned by the Union's necessity to maintain its autonomy with attention to the protection of human rights.¹⁶ However, the question appears whether the European Union is attempting to replace the international legal order by its own legal framework, by the model national law with EU law, rather than national and international law? While there is no doubt in the presence of a single phenomenon of international legal order concerning all state formations. This can be a symbolism of the confederation approach, with attention to the power of an integrated group of states, united for better protection of their joint interests.

Following the peculiarities of EU legal order, no matter to the actual willingness, the possibility of EU to make avail itself to a particular international treaty may depend on the presence of the competence to conclude particular measure. In *AETR* case the lack of conferred powers of the Union to conclude international agreement relied on the competence concerning the transportation that was a shared competence with the Member States.¹⁷ Herewith, the courts denied invoking implied powers risking to abuse competence, ruling on the areas of expressly conferred competence. Consequently, whenever the Union abstained from negotiating an international agreement, this may connote that the competence to be party to it wholly or partially reserved on the Member States.

Concerning the agreements of Uruguay round of GATT of 1986 that lead to the establishment of WTO, the agreements were scrutinized by CJEU on the subject of the presence of competence based on the Common

¹⁴ Case C-149/96 Portugal v Council [1999] ECR I-8395.

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Case T-85/09 Kadi v Commission [2010] ECR II-5177.

¹⁷ Case 22/70 Commission v Council [1971] ECR 263.

Commercial Policy, Art 207 TFEU, resulted in not all GATT agreements fall within that area. Concerning the Commission's point that Union embargoes were adopted under the common commercial policy was not convincing to the Court. CJEU held that transportation measures were auxiliary to the trade measure and hence the transportation is still referred to the area of shared competence of the Union.¹⁸ Similarly, the scrutiny concerning the legal ground was exemplary in the Community's Generalized Tariff preferences (GSP system) adopted in 1970 under the auspices of UNCTAD. Since the measure was adopted without express reference to the legal grounds, CJEU annulled regulations, referring to the requirement for the measure to be adopted based on the objective factors amenable to the judicial review.¹⁹ Herewith, no matter to the express confirmation of legal personality, acting of the Union in the international plane is subject to the presence of exclusive or in certain instances shared competence.

The European Union tends to involve ever greater areas of international competence in its domain. However, the role of the Member States on this matter may not always be negligible. Regarding the UNCTAD's 'Integrated Program for Commodities' concerning International Agreement on Natural Rubber, the question emerged over the Commission's mandate to conduct negotiations that mean EU's competence to promote that objective. In Opinion 1/78 the CJEU recognized the power of the Union beyond the free trade agenda, finding that commercial contract as regulatory measures of the trade.²⁰ The line has taken under the rationale of furthering regulatory goals in international trade, justified by the impossibility to carry out this objective without having elaborate means and mechanisms of regulation. With this regard, the article 207 of TFEU was construed in a nonrestrictive way, not limiting to the specific measures as quantitative restrictions or customs duties.²¹ Herewith, Opinion 1/78 CJEU

¹⁸ Piet Eeckhout, *Op. cit.*, 32.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, 22.

²⁰ International Agreement on Natural Rubber, Opinion 1/78, [1979] ECR 2871.

²¹ Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, OJ C 115/47, 2008.

recognized the extended powers of the European Union to conclude international agreements.²² Although the difference between the measure that entails establishing the buffering fund, in Opinion 1/75 that impose the cap on export credit expenditures was substantial, which led to recognizing the role of the Member States in contribution to this fund. This gave an idea on the necessity to cope with the third dimension of this relation which are the Member States.

Concerning the conflict of laws, it is notable to see that EU law is often reserved a dimension equivalent to the position of international law in respect to the national law. In ICSID case *Ioan Micula v Romania* the question appeared on the possibility of Sweden-Romania bilateral investment treaty (BIT) to be *lex specialis* in relation to EU law, due to overlapping areas of regulation and falling within the area of Common Commercial Policy. This gave a potential possibility for an international treaty with Member State to override EU constitutional treaties. Although the situation was seemingly clear from the position of international law, the issue, however, was far from acceptable from the EU counterpart. The European Commission as *amicus curiae* made submissions in favor of Romania clarifying that EU law would be more specific than BIT. The dispute went to a shortcut through finding the state violation under the grounds of failing to comply with the obligations under the BIT that predate obligation under the EU law.²³ Since the tribunal's decision was vindicated by the side matter, the question on the relation of constitutional treaties and international treaties retains its importance. In the case, if BIT would be found more specific, the question on the essence of conflict of international law with EU law would be presented in a quintessential form. It presents importance to check the alignment of this situation with the position EU, disregarding the existence of the competing treaties on the same matter. While there is a substantial similarity of EU law with international law from the viewpoint of treaty standards, there are distinctions in the rules defining

²² Piet Eeckhout, *Op. cit.*, 20.

²³ Ioan Micula and others v Romania, ICSID Case No. ARB/05/20.

customary international law not allowing derogation, while the treaty may still reserve a room for derogation and going out of it, as defined in Art 50 of ToL, reserving the right of withdrawal enabled in Brexit.

Beyond the outlined considerations, the effect of the instrument towards the EU, concerning the questions of the sources of EU law, may depend on the way how the source of international law was adopted in the EU level. With this regard, it is interesting to note a range of international agreements not subject to the direct applicability due to adoption in an unconventional way to the standard procedure. The agreements taken in Edinburgh Summit following Denmark's rejection of the TEU in the referendum is the example of such non-legally enforceable agreement. The Council did not take the decisions and declaration on Denmark at the noted summit according to the conventional lawmaking procedure under the EU law. This gave an insight on associating Edinburgh Summit agreement with an ordinary international agreement not forming part of the Union's legal system.²⁴

At this point, the European Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR) can be exemplary, drafted under the auspices of Council of Europe that intended to uphold the common political traditions of individual civil liberties and the rule of law. Notably, all EU Member States are signatories to ECHR, however, not EU itself. Its implications seen in the claims under ECHR brought in the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) in Strasbourg, however, not CJEU in Luxembourg. Herewith, in comparative outlook, the distinction of international structures created by ECHR from supranational institutions of EU seen in non-binding nature of the decisions of ECtHR in Strasbourg on national courts (although they may be taken into account by these courts), while decisions of CJEU in Luxembourg does have that effect.

The adoption of the treaty is subject to the ratification process required for the treaties after the acceptance of the measure by the Union, where the Member States adopt it based on the respective constitutional

²⁴ John Fairhurst, *Op. cit.*, 62.

requirements. The distinctions of the dualist and monist states that require the formal incorporation in the national law or not make an important difference with this regard. Notably, the EU secondary legislation comes in a more advantaged position, and according to the self-executing law concept (mainly with attention to regulations), taking its effect without implementing measures (Art 288 TFEU).²⁵

In Opinion 1/91 of the Draft Agreement between the EEC and EFTA CJEU states that EEC Treaty (currently TFEU),²⁶ even if concluded in the form of international agreement, nonetheless constitutes the Constitutional Charter of the Community (currently Union). The basis of *sui generis* nature of EU was referred in *Van Gend en Loos v Netherlands case*, that the treaties established new legal order for the benefit of which the States had limited their sovereign rights, in ever limited fields, and the subject of which comprised not only the Member States but also their nationals.²⁷ The TEU and the TFEU form the 'constitution' of the European Union. Although they do not purport to create the constitution of a federal state, in some respect they do have that effect.²⁸ The essential characteristic of the Union's legal order is in its primacy over the law of the Member States and the direct effect of a whole series of provisions applicable to their nationals and the Member States themselves.

The question regarding the place that the European Union reserves itself in the international plane, and the place it allocates to the sources of international law, can be instrumental via the cases concerning the conflict of the European Union law with its international treaties, where the Member States and the Union are the parties to the treaty. International instruments can be directly applicable, however, CJEU limiting the creation of its direct effect, not only on the grounds of noncompliance with the standards of direct effect but also by an unwillingness to bind itself with the

²⁵ Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, OJ C 115/47, 2008.

²⁶ Opinion of the Court of 14 December 1991, European Court Reports 1991 I-06079.

²⁷ C-26/62, NV Algemene Transport – en Expeditie Onderneming van Gend & Loos v Netherlands Inland Revenue Administration [1963] ECR 1.

²⁸ John Fairhurst, *Op. cit.*, 57.

order that the Member States are not bound. However, the question appears, whether it should be a principal difference with international instrument adopted or not adopted by the Member States, as normally the adoption by the EU should preclude its adoption by the Member States under Art 47 of TFEU.²⁹ Presumably, the adoption of the international instrument by the Member State adds credibility to the measure from the viewpoint of the European Union. Although, the possibility of both the EU and the Member States as a party to the treaty is possible concerning the treaties that predate 1958 (Art 351 TFEU).³⁰ Nevertheless, arguably the potential instances where such a prerogative is not necessary by virtue of the international treaty adopted by the Member States may not be conflicting with the EU law, also not devoid of reasonableness.

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Educational Policies for Researcher Problem-Solving Skills Development during Professional Culture Formation

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Abstract. Postgraduate study is a crucial stage of personality development resulting in new cognitive formations standing out as the components of professional culture. Professional culture is an integrative term denoting the level of creativity exhibited in a scientist's problem-solving skills. Problem-solving during FL studies is based on the use of authentic cinema and creolized texts containing professional and scientific situations. A situation arouses an intellectual difficulty for scientists, which leads to their individual and group problem-solving telling upon their professional culture development positively.

Keywords: professional culture, educational space, professional situation, problem-solving, scientific staff, frame, authentic cinema text, creolized text.

Introduction

Educational space as a sphere of human activity, where purposeful sociocultural development of a person as a specialist is carried out, provides scientific staff professional culture formation. Educational system based on the principles of unified educational policy and activity acts as an organizational structure meeting modern challenges¹. Educational policy and activity, system are closely interrelated with the term "culture", which is due to the fact that scientific personnel professional culture level determines progress in any field of activity and society overall. Enhancing the professionalism of scientific personnel, the formation and development of their culture, in particular, is most critical in educational policy.

¹ Ю. Н. Кулюткин, *Ценностно-смысловые ориентиры современного образования: проблемные очерки* (СПб, 2002).

It should be noted that postgraduate study is one of the most crucial stages of personality development. That's when the existing attitudes, life position, attitude to reality, in general, and to profession activity, in particular, are re-evaluated, transformed or modified into new personality cognitive formations, which stand out as the components of a scientist's professional competence and, eventually, professional culture. Therefore, the underlying educational principles of scientific personnel training should contain the ideas of pedagogical anthropology², sociology, and philosophy in their unity. Values and norms of culture, art, morality, all the spiritual attainments should be addressed to the personality of a scientist, enter all the structures of pedagogical activity and ensure its focus on scientific personnel personal development. The ends of the work are supposed to cover scientist comprehensive training for professional activity within changing social conditions.

Professional culture formation

"Professional culture" as a term became relevant in psychology and pedagogy in the 80s of the 20th century in connection with the development of a cultural approach (in the mainstream of the approach various philosophical, sociocultural processes and phenomena are considered). The term "professional culture" determines the consideration of culture as a specific activity of a scientist and reveals the subject content of culture, determined by the distinctive features of professional and scientific activities of professional community.

Professional culture as an integrative concept reflects the achieved level of skill and denotes creative attitude to work, the ability to work out decisions and evaluate them simultaneously from specifically technological and socio-cultural standpoints. Professional culture is formed on the basis of

² В. И. Слободчиков, "Антропология образования," *Новые ценности образования*, Вып. 5, 24 (2005): 13-16.

a constructive association of subject-professional and scientific competence³.

Professional culture, on the one hand, is a unique combination of norms, rules and behavioral patterns of a scientist, on the other hand, it is a relatively confined system characterized by common features of people's activities in a particular professional sphere. Professional culture contains a conservative (previous experience, serving as the basis for the reproduction of new experience) and creative (creating new or improving existing experience) basis.

The professional culture of a scientist includes a set of special theoretical knowledge and practical skills associated with performance. It is formed under the influence of internal and external factors. The role of external factors (government policy, the specifics of social and professional relations, aspects of social stratification of society) is the key to determining the internal factors of scientific personnel professional culture formation. The internal factors include the socio-cultural environment of a profession, which creates certain limitations or opportunities, the specifics of relations with adjacent specialties; aspects of information and communication activities of a team; individual professional experience⁴. The formation of a specialist professional culture is also influenced by both the peculiarities of a profession itself and the objective factors: global trends in education, and the quality of educational services, the culture of an educational institution, the prestige of a profession in society; subjective factors: general culture, motivation of an individual to receive education, predisposition to labour.

In our study we focus on the development of scientist professional culture during FL teaching. This process is innovative since it is closely connected with the formation of FL competences. This innovative approach

³ Дж. Равен, *Компетентность в современном обществе: выявление, развитие и реализация* (Москва, 2002).

⁴ Л. М. Спенсер, *Компетенции на работе: модели максимальной эффективности работы* (Москва, 2005).

calls for changing the content and structure of both professional and FL scientific personnel training.

Innovation activity involves the design of educational systems at any hierarchical level. Designing activities for scientist professional culture formation presupposes working out methodological grounds, disclosing the mechanism, stages and methods of managing the development of educational space.

Scientific staff as a system

Education is a process of consistent changes in relations between the subjects of educational space. Therefore, the subject of project activities is relationships, their shifts and evolvement. We have dwelt upon the evolutionary synergetic paradigm as the methodological basis for projecting. In synergetics there are universal models for the development of complex systems, so educational systems stand out as a kind of their variation. Any change in the structure of educational space leads to, therefore, changes in the relations between its subjects. Any change is of evolutionary nature and, in accordance with synergy, it turns pedagogical activity into a non-linear process. Universal models of synergetics make you knowledgeable of what is happening in various systems, enable a specialist to determine the advancement of the system currently.

Due to the increase of the social functions performed by a specialist in micro- and macro-society scientific personnel can be regarded as a system. A. I. Zhuk⁵ suggests that a system proves to be efficient, provided that activity coordination of all members is ensured. A group of scientists can be seen as a system on account of the conceptual foundations of professional culture and culture as a whole: culture manifests itself in the ability to function in professional community. Thus, the success of solving professional problems, tasks and situations is determined by the reflexive-positional contour of an individual scientist and a group of scientists overall.

⁵ А. И. Жук, *Активные методы обучения в системе повышения квалификации педагогов: учеб.-метод. пособие* (Минск, 2004).

We have singled out the following criteria of the reflexive-positional contour of a scientific group in general which allow us to consider it as a system⁶. They include: 1) adoption and acknowledgement of the goals, objectives of activity; 2) subordination and communication between scientists specializing in a certain subject of activity; 3) coherence; 4) independence, autonomy of each participant; 5) generating the “bank of ideas” and sharing the “community resources”; 6) intercommunity of values; 7) achieving results, obtaining the product of joint activity.

Scientist professional culture formation mechanism

The mechanism of scientist professional culture formation during FL studies is based on the use of authentic cinema and creolized texts that perform cognitive, educational, emotional, aesthetic, therapeutic, compensatory, recreational, cathartic functions; a model that contains certain principles, methods and tools, pedagogical conditions.

An authentic cinema text is a fragment of a FL film featuring various professional situations, ensuring a scientist’s entry into tailored quasi scientific and professional reality. A creolized text is a complex textual formation, the unity of verbal and iconic elements making up a visual, structural-semantic and functional whole, aimed at shaping a recipient’s professional culture. Creolized texts are represented in newspapers and scientific-technical texts, guidelines, manuals, illustrated literary texts, advertising discourse and etc.

Designing the development of educational space on the basis of synergetics calls for describing the pedagogical conditions for scientist professional culture formation during FL studies. Pedagogical conditions appear to be a necessary prerequisite for the development of a system. We have identified common and special pedagogical conditions as a factor of enhancing the readiness of scientific personnel for problem-solving.

⁶ Н. А. Егорова, “Профессиональная культура как способность будущего специалиста к принятию решений,” *Психология обучения*, № 1 (2012): 95-105.

The core of the common conditions is the teacher's readiness for scientist professional culture formation during FL studies, educational and methodological organization, and diagnostic services support of developing the ability to effectively handle scientific and professional situations. The teacher's readiness to form professional culture includes "knowledge" and "ability" components.

The basis of the "knowledge" component is the concept of professional culture standing out as a factor of a scientist's personality development, a system that includes a set of interrelated components, a process and a result of professional culture formation, its components; mastering the basic psychological and pedagogical provisions of the theory, methodology of education.

The "ability" component acts as a result of mastering the methods of shaping scientific staff professional culture process during FL study. This component includes: a) ways relating to forming professional culture; b) methods of organizing and reorganizing activities.

The integrity of the "knowledge" and "ability" components forms a stable integrative quality – a teacher's readiness to develop professional culture by means of authentic cinema and creolized texts, which predetermines potential to solve professional situations in educational environment by researchers.

Projecting scientific staff professional culture formation presupposes some stages in accordance with the universal models of complex system development.

The first stage (diagnostic support of researcher professional culture development) includes: 1) study on the expertise of culture formation in various types of educational institutions; 2) creation of a model aimed at scientist professional culture formation by means of authentic cinema and creolized texts; 3) elaboration of criteria and markers of scientist professional culture formation during learning FL study; 5) creation of educational and methodological tools aimed at developing the scientist's

ability to cope with professional situations; 6) comparison of the initial and final levels of researcher professional culture formation.

The task of the second stage (the formative stage), which consists of propaedeutic and basic sub-stages, is to develop the specialists' ability to creatively approach professional situations.

The propaedeutic stage provides researcher professional culture formation itself, and it involves the design of the program and academic and professional activity motivation enhancing.

The task of the main stage is to accumulate the experience of solving professional tasks, dealing with situations. It includes sub-stages: introductory, informative, immersive, problem-activity, evaluative and productive, variable-creative.

The interaction of the subjects of educational activity on the main stage leads to the formation of the "environment of collaboration and partnership". It is a system-forming sign. This interaction stands out as a factor for a new quality system appearance.

The assessment of the new quality, in particular, the ability to solve professional situations, occurs on the third stage. The third stage (monitoring) provides the estimation of the effectiveness of scientific personnel professional culture formation model during FL study.

Thus, the creative nature of scientific and professional activity is its most important objective characteristic and professional guidelines for scientific personnel training. The highest results in professional activity are associated with overcoming professional obstacles and barriers, broadening the philosophical, methodological and socio-cultural outlook of researchers. The content and organization of work can be properly assessed by determining the level of a scientist's creative attitude towards a certain activity consisting of various kinds of professional situations, the solutions to which are the equivalent of a scientist's potential to achieve goals, and, consequently, his professional culture level.

The first pedagogical condition for scientific personnel professional culture development is a teacher's readiness to organize this process during

FL teaching. Taking into account the fact that the basis for a teacher's readiness is creativity it is necessary to understand the multi-level nature of this phenomenon. While some type of creativity is characterized by the use of the already existing knowledge and the expansion of its application scale, another type of creativity lies in a completely new approach to changing the common view on the subject matter.

Some scientists (K. V. Gavrilovets, A. I. Zhuk, O. L. Zhuk, V. T. Kabush, V. A. Kan-Kalik, E. Rangelova, A. P. Smantser, etc.) suggest that the creative potential of a teacher is characterized by a number of abilities: 1) to identify and formulate a problem; 2) to avoid superficial conclusions and judgements; 3) to foresee the perspective; 4) to quickly and freely switch to new ideas; 4) to evoke images in the mind and create new combinations of them; 5) to value other people's judgments and critical thinking, share them during performance. Consequently, the implementation of a creative approach to developing scientific personnel professional culture is possible if an educator masters the experience in forming different types of culture in educational institutions.

Traditionally texts serve as the main source for the study on pedagogical experience. They stand out as a cognitive tool for mastering cultures, professional culture in particular. Authentic cinema texts as a kind of texts allow revealing the differences in bearers of mentality, the distinctive features of professional culture in a certain society⁷.

The comparative analysis of pedagogical mentality in different cultures by means of authentic cinema texts is not by far exploited in science. Authentic cinema text potential manifests itself in linguistic pragmatics, cognitive linguistics and FL teaching in order to study and organize communication.

In a teacher's pedagogical culture speech acts are a formative factor of communication. A teacher is seen as the organizer or the "manager" of communication. Thus, the most important component of pedagogical culture is competence, especially communicative competence. Being a

⁷ N. A. Yahorava, *Analysing Vocationally-oriented Authentic Texts* (Baranovich, 2011).

significant and relatively independent subsystem in the structure of professional competence, communicative competence manifests itself in the ability to interact with other people in accordance with certain conditions.

Communicative competence is a complex concept; therefore, it is not limited only to pedagogical abilities or a teacher's awareness in terms of pedagogy and psychology. In fact, communicative competence is a combination of worldview, value orientations, knowledge, practical skills and behavior affecting pedagogical communication. Therefore, there have been singled out two basic components in the structure of professional communicative competence. The first component predetermines the manifestation of communicative abilities in interaction. It includes two sublevels: direct actions (skills) and knowledge about the patterns of verbal and non-verbal interaction. The second component is communicative values, orientations and specifics of motivation from the didactic standpoint.

In FL instruction, a language is, on the one hand, a linguistic form of didactic information transfer, and on the other, a didactic tool for monitoring learning. A language of instruction is characterized by the features of didactic discourse. The "procedural" nature of pedagogical communication is represented by a sequence of discursive-speech situations of scientific and professional orientation, which can be called "didactic frames" (scenarios with sustainable patterns). A didactic frame, first of all, is a repository of information. It provides feedback in class.

We regard the term "frame of a didactic situation" from a linguistic standpoint, it can be shaped into a schematized-visualized view of the "state of affairs" consisting of a generalized "framework" reproducing the stable characteristics of a learning situation which can be transformed in accordance with external conditions (the profiles of scientists, their emotional manifestations, educational resources, curriculum, etc.).

The mental basis for a didactic frame is largely due to the specialty mentalities of communicators. The “mentality” of a teacher⁸ in its all diversity is crucial for effective learning. The “mentality” of a teacher embraces common speech culture and a “feeling” of a language which presuppose the use of specific communicative strategies and tactics.

A teacher’s speech actions within the frame of a didactic situation are supposedly intentional and well-structured. A teacher’s inconsistent or broken speech may lead to the disruption of a frame structure, especially the loss of one or several parameters (focus, feedback, management and evaluation of communication, etc.).

Thus, the discursive space of an authentic cinema text allows a teacher to study the specifics of a didactic situation frame, which includes various components: 1) communicants (a teacher, academic staff); 2) the subject of communication (scientific and professional content); 3) organizing communication; 4) the “code” (realization of language competence in speech); 5) the “key” (assessment of a speech act effectiveness); 6) spheres of communication (professional and scientific); 7) space-time features of communication; 8) the unity of the objectives, tasks of scientists as a system/group; 9) forms and types of communication; 10) kinds of communication acts; 16) communication strategies and tactics. Consequently, an authentic cinema text appears to be an effective means to shape both a teacher’s readiness for scientific personnel professional culture formation, and a scientist’s readiness for problem-solving in scientific and professional spheres (situations).

Professional situations and problem-solving skills development

An effective tool for scientific personnel professional culture formation is a professional situation, which is the unity of facts and

⁸ Н. А. Егорова, “Профессионально-педагогическая ментальность как социально-философский феномен,” in *Проблемы и перспективы подготовки педагогических кадров в условиях модернизации системы образования Республики Казахстан*, Караганда (2014): 336-337.

phenomena that arouse an intellectual difficulty and, thus, conditions for scientist individual and group problem-solving activity.

We have set forth the following features common in professional situations: 1) integrative nature (it combines the specifics of various types of scientific and professional activities of a specialist); 2) the existence of a problem (a contentious issue containing an implicit contradiction which results in different, conflicting views during problem-solving); 3) an urgent need and, consequently, the ability to solve a problem; 4) the necessity of the existing problem-solving principles, methods, techniques and tools adjustment and modification according to a situation.

The specifics of a scientist's activities call for mastering the ability to pass out decisions in *diverse* professional situations. We suggest 5 criteria for the classification of professional situations: 1) thematic and ideological focus; 2) specifics of a professional phenomenon and facts; 4) the nature of scientific and professional problems; 5) the type of contradictions that are supposed to be overcome by scientists; 6) scientific and professional environment peculiarities.

The basis for the thematic introduction of professional situations in classroom is presented in the following provisions: 1) types of scientific and professional activities; 2) the personality of a scientist; 3) a scientist as the subject of scientific and professional activities.

In accordance with the results of professional activity content analysis and the main types of situations that a specialist has to cope with, a group of scholars (M. I. Dyachenko, L. A. Kandybovich, V. A. Ponomarenko, A. I. Zhuk) single out: a) standard situations – oft-repeated or replicated professional facts and phenomena in the activities of scientists; b) critical situations - atypical facts and phenomena that do not live up to the initial expectations, estimation or planning of a scientist, thus, lead to stepped-in intervention; c) extreme situations – one-of-a-kind professional facts and phenomena that have no comparisons with the past, they frequently cause negative changes.

A professional situation can be polyvalent and monovalent. A monovalent situation is for one-time problem-solving activity. The educational resources of a polyvalent situation enable scientific staff to discuss its content for several classes.

Professional problems that lie in a situation may be of general, private or special nature. The problem of general nature reflects systematic, holistic issues of professional activity (scheduling, scientific concept employment, scientific and professional communication, etc.). The problems of private nature are the issues related to certain aspects of professional communication, scientific activity management, the establishment of scientific contacts and business relations, etc.). The problems of special nature are devoted to a range of issues relating to the actions of the subjects of scientific and (or) professional communication, the peculiarities of their worldview, ideals, personal qualities, attitudes, etc.

The result of problem-solving is the overcoming of the contradiction between:

- available knowledge and new facts that blow the theory;
- acknowledgement of the scientific problem importance and the lack of the theoretical basis for its solution;
- a variety of concepts and the lack of a reliable theory to substantiate these facts;
- practically accessible ends and the lack of theoretical foundation;
- theoretically conceivable solution and impracticality;
- a sufficient amount of evidence and the lack of a method to process and analyze it.

A professional situation is aimed at teaching scientists to differentiate various types and subtypes of professional and scientific problems; identify scientific truths and pseudo truths; determine the content, forms, methods and means of resolving the situation in their optimal combination; choose various types of activity and performance assessment; accept the humanistic principles of relations as a standard of

professional activities; respond to changes in a professional and scientific situation, improvise.

Study on the specifics of problem-solving

During problem-solving the specifics of a scientist's actions stand out as an indicator of their creativity level, as well as mechanisms reflecting the ability to pass out non-standard decisions. We have employed the method of observation. Scientists learned to solve problems of scientific and professional nature. Academic staff of the State Educational Institution "Graduate School of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus" took part in the research.

The study on the specifics of problem-solving by scientists revealed the fact that the decrease in creative activity is caused by cognitive distortions. Cognitive distortions are thinking errors or professional stereotypes which are exhibited by experts throughout passing out decisions. We have fixed the following cognitive distortions.

First, an emotional explanation is typical of 56% of scientists. It is a position based on a strong belief in certain phenomena, objects, which affects decision-making area, the nature of ideas and solutions in a certain scientific and professional situation.

28% of scientists used mental filters which resulted in focusing on one detail and overlooking other facts and phenomena that design a professional situation in general.

6% of respondents resorted to labeling. These are the positions based on prejudice, conscious and unconscious bias, stereotyping.

5% of respondents employed the technique "reading thoughts". It borders on the confidence that they possess the ability to find out or foresee what other people bear in their minds. This was the determining factor in resolving the situation.

2% of the experiment participants excessively generalized facts and phenomena shaping a professional situation. It is a way of positioning which

lies in some general conclusion drawn previously and introduced into a current situation.

1% of scientists displayed personalization (the explanation of behavior, intentions depending on the previous judgements relating to the fact or phenomenon), block vision (seeing the negative aspects of a situation only and disregarding all positive facets), hyperbolization or minimization (overestimation or underestimation of facts and phenomena).

Therefore, we can draw the following conclusion: decision-making area is greatly influenced by the peculiarities of cognitive distortions generated by scientists in a professional situation. They impede the development of creative, adequate solutions. The results show the interconnection between creative activity and the spiritual culture of scientific personnel. Shaping the creative attitude of scientists to scientific and professional activity presupposes the mastering of problem-solving experience that contributes to the effective development of scientific personnel professional culture overall.

Conclusion

Mastering and manifesting creativity in scientific and professional activities come part and parcel throughout scientist training. This requirement stands true for scientists of any generation, including the new one. One of the perspective trends of scientific personnel creative abilities formation is the building up of problem-solving environment where situations are tailored to meet the scientific and professional needs of experts. The study helped find out and generalize the peculiarities of the scientist's readiness to work out non-standard decisions (in particular, the factors that hinder their application). The interlinks between creative activity and professional culture amplify the idea that the educational space of the Graduate School of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus serves as a productive platform for creating special psychological and pedagogical conditions for researcher professional culture and mentality formation via FL. One of the determining factors in scientific personnel

education is the development of problem-solving skills and, thus, the acquisition of experience in dealing with various vocationally-oriented situations that enhance the growth and positive changes in a scientist at professional, scientific and personal level.

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La Crise de l'Éducation. Indicateurs d'Etat et Solutions

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Abstract. Today, even in countries that have carried out education reforms in due time, new reforms are being conceived. New reforms start from claims of major shortcomings in the present state of education. And if the US, Germany, and France, which have geared the world's education, signal a crisis, then we realize how serious the situation is in other countries. Under the term "education crisis" some consider the fact that education no longer builds up free, responsible and creative individuals. Others think that the adaptation of education to the industrialized society based on digitization and nanoscience has not taken place. There are some others who perceive the deepening of the moral crisis in society and the fact that education has no response to it. The author considers that, historically, the deterioration of the formation of individuality brought about both the decrease in creativity and the deepening of the moral crisis. Of course, not every deadlock is a crisis, although change may often be taken as a crisis. Strengthening the position of science in the curriculum or strengthening liberal disciplines is not a crisis. There is no crisis either when teaching and learning methodologies are changed. But if we try to express in accurate terms what is going on in Europe and the arguments that are being weighed by experts and citizens, then it becomes evident that we are dealing with a crisis. It is, one may say, a "crisis of sense" consisting in the increasingly confusing goal of education today. It is a "motivation crisis" expressed in the decreasing confidence in the knowledge taught at school. It is a "content crisis" since there is almost no one willing to embark upon deciding what should be necessarily learned and how the teacher should proceed about it. It is a "conception crisis" that lies in the fact that there are few experts able to approach education as a system. The article first briefly looks into the current education crisis, then points to the indicators for Europe and Romania and, finally, concludes with the outline of a solution.

Keywords: education, crisis, indicator, solution.

Les performances humaines – de celles technologiques et économiques, passant par celles cognitives et institutionnelles, aux

performances civiques, sociales et morales – dépendent de l'éducation. Elles ne dérivent pas l'une de l'autre – le civisme ne résulte pas uniquement de la connaissance, ni la morale des institutions ou la démocratie de l'économie de marché. Elles ne vont pas toujours ensemble. Mais chacune dépend de la qualité de l'éducation.

Cette dépendance est en double sens. La réfection rapide de certaines sociétés (telles celles d'après-guerre, de l'Allemagne et du Japon) – a tenu du niveau d'éducation de la population. Le retard d'autres sociétés a, à son tour, des racines dans l'éducation.

Aujourd'hui, même dans des pays qui ont parcouru à temps des réformes de l'éducation, on conçoit de nouvelles réformes.

Par exemple, le président américain préconisait le renoncement à l'actuel système quantitativiste d'évaluation scolaire, qui a mené dans l'impasse les systèmes d'éducation de différents pays, l'arrêt de «la politique des standards unitaires», le passage de l'enseignement au «niveau local» et l'encouragement de la compétition dans l'éducation.¹ Les enfants doivent être «éduqués, non endoctrinés»! L'horizon est que chaque élève et étudiant puisse se développer conformément à son potentiel.

En Allemagne, de hauts dignitaires disent que «la tendance actuelle mène vers une nouvelle catastrophe».² Toute une série de compétences cruciales dans la vie des gens, «la compétence du pouvoir de jugement», «la compétence de la décision», «la compétence de la coopération» sont sacrifiées par l'éducation.³ Il ne faudrait pas que l'orientation exclusive de l'éducation vers la composante cognitive,⁴ qu'OECD prend comme prémisses

¹ Voir Donald Trump, *Great Again! Wie ich Amerika retten werde* (Kulmbach: Börsen Medien, 2016), 69.

² Julian Nida-Rümelin, Klaus Zierer, *Auf dem Weg in eine neue deutsche Bildungskatastrophe. Zwölf unangenehme Wahrheiten* (Freiburg im Breisgau: Herder, 2015), 147.

³ *Ibid.*, 95.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 106.

indiscutable, décide. En fait, les tests et les hiérarchisations que l'on cultive créent «de fausses motivations et un éthos pédagogique dangereux».⁵

En France, l'actuel ministre de l'éducation dit que «le modèle français doit aujourd'hui faire face à de multiples mises en cause, liées à l'inquiétude devant le progrès technologique, devant les risques de déclin économique et d'implosion de la société, le danger de réaction fondamentaliste devant la modernité, sans oublier les blocages inhérents à la société même, qui s'expriment avec clarté au sein du système scolaire».⁶ Il faut laisser au musée les expériences faites sous la pression de la globalisation, qui ont généré de véritables «catastrophes pédagogiques». Jean-Michel Blanquer attire l'attention sur le besoin «de prendre conscience du fait que les sciences cognitives ne sont pas la boussole absolue de tout ce qu'il faut faire en matière d'éducation».⁷ L'école même s'assume la construction de la société autour de l'idéal d'une nation avancée.

Et si ces pays, qui ont orienté l'éducation du monde, signalent la menace de «catastrophe», qui est plus d'une crise, alors nous nous rendons compte à quel point la situation est grave dans d'autres. Là surtout où le mimétisme est en fleur, et la réflexion au moyen de la propre tête a presque abdiqué.

Sous le terme de «la crise de l'éducation» certains envisagent la circonstance que l'éducation ne forme plus l'individualité libre, responsable et créative. D'autres pensent au fait que n'a pas eu lieu l'adaptation de l'éducation à la société industrialisée basée sur la digitalisation et les nanosciences. Il y a encore d'autres qui ont en vue l'approfondissement de la crise morale de la société et le fait que l'éducation n'a pas de réponse. Je suis d'avis que, du point de vue historique, en même temps que la détérioration de la formation de l'individualité se sont résultats également la diminution de la créativité et l'approfondissement de la crise morale.

⁵ Ibid., 73.

⁶ Jean-Michel Blanquer, *L'École de demain. Propositions pour une Education nationale renouvelée* (Paris: Odile Jacob, 2016), 7.

⁷ Ibid., 11.

Le terme de crise nous vient du langage médical. Un organisme est en crise lorsque, pour différentes raisons, les ressources dont il dispose ne sont plus suffisantes pour assurer sa survie. La crise ne dépend pas de la conscience de celui qui en est atteint, qui peut même jubiler.

Je suis d'avis que nous n'avons pas une crise de l'éducation dans le sens médical. L'éducation a encore beaucoup de ressources non utilisées. Mais il y a beaucoup d'indicateurs de crise profonde.

Conformément à la compréhension classicisée, l'éducation (*Bildung*) réunit, dans son but, son contenu et ses moyens, à la fois l'individualité et les valeurs de la vie en commun, la liberté et la responsabilité, l'intégration dans le présent et la mémoire du passé, la profession et la perception de son importance dans la communauté (Humboldt, *Theorie der Bildung des Menschen*, 1793). Aujourd'hui, on est arrivé dans une telle situation où l'éducation se réduit en fait à une sorte d'apprentissage, à une manière de diffuser les connaissances, même de propagande et de commerce et cesse d'être de l'éducation.

Je veux montrer dans cet article en quoi consiste la crise actuelle de l'éducation (1) évoquer des indicateurs pour l'Europe (2) et la Roumanie (3) et esquisser ce qu'il faut faire (4).

1. La crise actuelle de l'éducation

L'éducation n'est pas un but en soi, comme ne le sont ni l'économie, ni la politique. Un indicateur de crise de l'éducation est le fait qu'aujourd'hui on se pose trop peu la question: qu'est-ce que l'éducation a à créer?

C'est-à-dire l'éducation crée-t-elle des gens disciplinés, qui respectent les valeurs engagées par une société? Ou des individus relativement professionnalisés, qui ne s'intéressent qu'à eux-mêmes? Ou des velléitaires qui se faufilent, mais ne laissent pas grand-chose derrière eux? Ou des imposteurs qui plaisent aux régimes, car ils peuvent être instrumentalisés? Ou de la main d'œuvre qui se vend, mais qui n'a que des intérêts pécuniers? Ou des gens qui peuvent se débrouiller en trouvant un emploi dans n'importe quelles conditions? Ou des personnes compétentes

et responsables, capables de promouvoir leurs vues? Ou des personnalités capables de concevoir des solutions d'intérêt public et d'assumer des responsabilités dans la société. Chacun de nous peut répondre à ces questions et dresser un score. Ce score nous indiquera les dimensions de la crise de l'éducation.

Après beaucoup d'indices, on est passé, en fait, de l'éducation à la «non-éducation (Unbildung)» organisée.⁸ Celle-ci crée des individus dans le meilleur des cas utiles, mais non éduqués (gebildete). Elle est séparée de «l'aspiration à la connaissance fondée, à la réflexion critique, à la rencontre avec sa propre tradition et avec des cultures étrangères et à une puissance de jugement aigüe».⁹ L'éducation ne produit plus davantage que «l'actuelle culture média».

La situation est cependant encore plus difficile. Même dans des sociétés européennes développées, la pauvreté, soit-elle-même relative, monte plus haut que le milieu de la société.¹⁰ Le professionnalisme européen est en déclin.¹¹ Le chômage des licenciés et des mastérants acquiert de l'ampleur. Dans certains pays l'abandon scolaire continue. L'illettrisme est un fait incontestable. L'opportunisme moral est un mode de vie.

Il est clair que les carences existantes d'éducation laissent en arrière des êtres dans le meilleur des cas robotisés. Max Weber écrivait qu'avec l'expansion des «gens modernes spécialisés (moderne Fachmenschentum)»,¹² la culture produirait «des spécialistes sans esprit et des gens des plaisirs sans cœur» sur une échelle jamais rencontrée auparavant. L'avertissement de Husserl d'il y a un siècle – la connaissance à

⁸ Konrad Paul Liessmann, *Theorie der Unbildung. Die Irrtümer der Wissensgesellschaft* (München, Zürich: Piper, 2006).

⁹ Id., *Bildung als Provokation* (Wien: Paul Zsolnay, 2017).

¹⁰ Reinhard Marx, Arnd Küppers, *Das Kapital: Ein Plädoyer für den Menschen* (Munich: Knauer-Taschenbuch-Verlag, 2008).

¹¹ Alan Greenspan, *The Age of Turbulence: Adventures in a New World* (London: Penguin Books, 2003).

¹² Max Weber, *Die protestantische Ethik und der Geist des Kapitalismus* (Hamburg: Siebenstern, 1975), 172.

bas horizon donne des gens à humanité réduite – est plus actuel que jamais. En définitive, les signes d'une dégradation culturelle d'aujourd'hui sont liée aux lacunes de l'éducation.

Ces problèmes réapparaissent aujourd'hui dans l'éducation même. Le plus important pédagogue de notre jours a montré qu'«être reconnu comme membre d'une profession n'est pas la même chose qu'agir en spécialiste».¹³ J'ajoute la distinction entre «avoir fini une spécialisation» et «être bon dans sa spécialité». Combien de gens ne portent pas de titres, mais leur préparation pour faire quelque chose important est médiocre? À l'époque du commerce avec des places d'étude, la fiabilité des diplômes est devenue un problème.

L'éducation existante prépare insuffisamment pour l'administration et l'auto-administration et entraîne la faible compréhension de la société. Les expériences attestent que l'on n'atteint pas de performances durables là où il n'y a que de l'égoïsme, de l'opportunisme, de la ruse.

Sans doute, l'éducation de notre temps a généré aussi des personnes compétentes et responsables, capables de promouvoir leurs vues et de concevoir des solutions d'intérêt public. Mais l'effectif de ceux-ci est surclassé par l'effectif des mal préparés, des semi-doctes, des débrouillards, des velléitaires, des imposteurs. Cette disproportion synthétise la gravité de la crise éducationnelle actuelle.

2. L'Europe

Une série d'organisations traditionnelles dans l'éducation de l'Europe réclamaient la réforme. Celle-ci a été conçue et lancée dans beaucoup de pays dans les années 1990. Pise et Bologne sont ses symboles. Qu'est-ce qu'il en est sorti?

En 2000, on a mis en application le plus ample programme d'évaluation internationale du niveau des élèves – *Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA)* – pour la lecture, les mathématiques, les sciences, auquel s'est ajoutée ultérieurement la

¹³ Howard Gardner, *Five Minds for the Future* (Boston: Harvard Business Press, 2008), 129.

résolution de problèmes. Le programme reste opportune et important comme composante de l'évaluation scolaire. Mais l'enseignement pré-universitaire s'est transformé peu à peu dans beaucoup de pays dans un instrument d'obtention des points PISA.

En 1999, les ministres de l'éducation des pays européens ont signé *La Déclaration de Bologne*, qui se proposait de compatibiliser les systèmes d'enseignement supérieur et d'accroître la compétitivité des universités. Ces objectives sont restées réalistes. Puisqu'ils se renseignent peu, beaucoup des gens pensent que cette *Déclaration* aurait réduit la durée des études, aurait modifié les spécialisations, auraient changé les programmes d'étude, aurait créé la bureaucratie des évaluations, en un mot, aurait défiguré l'enseignement supérieur. Pas question! *La Déclaration* ne pouvait modifier l'enseignement supérieur d'un pays, car l'éducation est maintenant encore un domaine de souveraineté nationale.

Il est vrai pourtant que, depuis 2001, sont intervenues des décisions erronées des ministres de l'éducation et des gouvernements, qui ont conduit *La Déclaration de Bologne* à une application acéphale. La bureaucratie de l'éducation pense aujourd'hui encore que l'on est arrivé à la dernière phase de l'évolution de l'enseignement sur la Terre. De même que dans le cas PISA on décourage tout doute, dans le cas de Bologne certains refusent toute réflexion.

Nous ne pouvons ne pas noter qu'aussi bien PISA que Bologne ont été mal comprises non comme stratégies, comme elles l'étaient en fait, mais comme une conception sur l'éducation, ce qui est faux. Et qu'après 2001, la réforme a été pratiquement abandonnée dans certains pays, en faveur d'une adaptation à la globalisation.

Fait point surprenant, beaucoup de spécialistes¹⁴ ont eu des réactions à la situation qui s'est créée après 2001. À mon tour, j'ai réagi.¹⁵

¹⁴ Richard Münch, *Globale Eliten, lokale Autoritäten. Bildung und Wissenschaft unter den Regime von Pisa*, McKinsey & Co (Frankfurt am Main: Suhrkamp, 2003); Stefan Collini, *What Are Universities for?* (London: Penguin, 2012), etc.

¹⁵ Voir Andrei Marga, *Speranța rațiunii. Interviu* (Cluj-Napoca: EFES, 2006); Theodor Berchem, Andrei Marga, Jan Sadlak (eds.), *Living in Truth. A Conceptual Framework for a*

J'ai montré que la législation de l'application de *La Déclaration de Bologne* en Roumanie (2004) était erronée et que les décisions de gouvernement concernant le master et le doctorat (2005) étaient fautives. Ce que l'on voit aujourd'hui pleinement! Avec le président de l'American Council on Education¹⁶ j'ai montré que l'affectation de la structure des études était inadéquate – ce que l'on sent maintenant partout. J'ai également montré la différence entre *La Déclaration de Bologne* et son application,¹⁷ qui a été faite dans le langage spécifique – employability, accountability, workload, outcomes, human capital, university teacher etc. – et dans l'optique étroite d'une vision néolibérale.

Ce que l'on teste dans PISA ce sont des cibles importantes de l'éducation, mais quelque chose ne pourra jamais être réalisé – le développement du système d'enseignement. Entre ce que les Grecs antiques appelaient *idiotes*, c'est-à-dire les gens absorbés par eux-mêmes, et *polymates*, les gens qui s'éparpillent dans beaucoup de choses, mais sans pouvoir le systématiser, seraient préférables les personnes qui arrivent à juger de leur propre tête les faits.¹⁸ Aussi l'éducation devrait-elle être placée dans le cadre du «développement», non au service de «la croissance», dans le sens restrictif d'aujourd'hui. Il est besoin, sans doute, que l'on mesure les résultats, mais non que l'on transforme la mensuration en doctrine du développement.

On a très bien observé qu'à lieu une «académisation» forcée de la préparation au lieu que l'on travaille à adapter les études aux besoins de la société et aux affinités des jeunes.¹⁹ On crée des hiérarchies artificielles

Wisdom Society and the European Construction (Cluj-Napoca: Cluj University Press, 2008); Andrei Marga, *Profilul și reforma universității clujene. Discursuri rectorale* (Cluj-Napoca: Ed. Presa Univ., 2011).

¹⁶ Voir David Ward, Andrei Marga, Roxana Gâz, Eunicia Trif, *The Bologna Process: An American Perspective* (Cluj-Napoca: Editura Fundației pentru Studii Europene, 2008).

¹⁷ Andrei Marga, "Implementing Bologna Declaration: the Need for a Change of Direction," *Donauraum*, Wien, nr. 3 (2011).

¹⁸ Julian Nida-Rümelin, Klaus Zierer, *Op. cit.*, 124.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, 51.

d'institutions d'enseignement, au lieu de procéder à leur «différenciation»²⁰ et à la différenciation de leurs opportunités. Les spécialisations se fragmentent; l'égoïsme de chacune triomphe,²¹ au prix de l'avancement dans une direction dont personne ne répond.²² Le discours public est toujours plus pauvre²³ et se traîne derrière les événements. La globalisation est mal comprise comme quelque chose qui devrait annihiler des traditions nationales et des valeurs locales.²⁴

Des analyses européennes²⁵ accusent que l'on est arrivé dans une situation grave: l'autonomie décisionnelle du professeur est remplacée par l'intégration dans des programmes; les agences d'évaluation et d'accréditation deviennent des instances de consécration professionnelle; la bureaucratie de l'audit prend l'ascendant sur les professionnels; la déprofessionnalisation du personnel enseignant est légitimée par l'accomplissement de paramètres mesurables, l'idéal professionnel devient la satisfaction des standards ou l'obtention des subventions; une bureaucratie du contrôle de la qualité guette des standards, mais ne prend pas de responsabilité pour ce qui résulte; la relation éducative professeur-étudiant est remplacée par le rapport offreur-client; et l'avenir s'enferme dans cet horizon.

Dans beaucoup d'universités des pays européens on vit en mimant ce qui s'innove – sur le plan technologique, scientifique, culturel – ailleurs. Les universités sont plutôt tournées vers elles-mêmes. Il y a trop peu de souci pour la sélection des sommets créatifs. Bien des universitaires enseignent des disciplines, mais n'ont pas de réponse pour les besoins pratiques des alentours. Les universités sont plus nombreuses que jamais dans l'histoire, mais l'avenir est plus opaque que jamais.

²⁰ Ibid., 53.

²¹ Ibid., 137.

²² Ibid., 160.

²³ Ibid., 165.

²⁴ Ibid., 182.

²⁵ Richard Münch, *Op. cit.*

Si nous essayons de capter dans des termes précis la signes de crise de l'éducation d'Europe, il devient clair qu'elle s'est étendue. C'est une «crise de sens»: le but de l'éducation est obscurisé. C'est une «crise de contenu»: personne ne décide plus ce qu'il faut apprendre. C'est une «crise de motivation»: la confiance dans les connaissances enseignées diminue. C'est une «crise de conception»: trop peu de gens peuvent encore dire ce qu'il y a à faire. C'est une «crise de créativité»: de nouvelles solutions et idées apparaissent trop rarement.

3. La Roumanie

On observe vite qu'en Roumanie l'on construit beaucoup, mais sans systématisation durable, que l'administration n'a pas d'efficience, que l'on ne sait argumenter sans erreurs une sentence, que l'on ne peut relater les événements sans fausser la vérité, que l'on ne peut pas écrire l'histoire contemporaine du pays, que l'on ne comprend pas le monde environnant. Certaines statistiques publiées les dernières années sont cependant plus concrètes:

a) La Roumanie d'aujourd'hui a la plus grande émigration d'un pays en temps de paix – il y a plus de 90 000 enfants restés à la maison, avec les parents partis travailler hors du pays;

b) A dramatiquement baissé l'inscription des citoyens roumains aux bibliothèques. Si en 1990 étaient inscrits 5,8 millions de citoyens, le record des inscriptions sera atteint en 1998 et 2003 avec plus de 6,1 millions, pour que l'effectif des inscriptions s'écroule sans cesse depuis 2004;

c) Récemment, certaines publications²⁶ ont signalé que seulement 19,2% des citoyens parlaient une langue étrangère (la Roumanie, avec 7% de ses citoyens appartenant aux minorités ethnique et immigrants, étant dépassée seulement par la Hongrie, avec 17,6%). Par comparaison, parlent une langue étrangère dans la Chine actuelle plus de 29% des citoyens, en Autriche (60%), en Chypre (59,3), en Grèce (44,8), en France (35,9), en Pologne (39), en Tchéquie (34,6), en Bulgarie (30);

²⁶ Voir Mathieu Duchatel, *Le monde vue d'Asie* (Mas de Vert: Philippe Picquier, 2013).

d) Les générations plus récentes arrivent à enfreindre régulièrement les règles de grammaire. En outre, est excessive la présence des sophismes dans la communication publique.²⁷ Et les erreurs de pragmatique accablent: aux constatations on réagit par de la rhétorique, à des questions par indifférence, etc.;

e) En 2016 l'entreprise qui produit les voitures Mercedes-Benz a décidé la construction de nouvelles usines en Hongrie et en Pologne. En Roumanie on ne créera qu'une usine pour le reconditionnement des boîtes de vitesse. Plus clairement que jamais, une firme de référence a montré du doigt «la faible qualité de la main d'œuvre»! La Commission Européenne a remarqué en 2019 un «persistant manque de compétence en Roumanie»;

f) On a publié World University Ranking 2016 – une hiérarchisation des mille premières universités, où l'on a voulu inclure chaque pays avec quelque chose. Mais même ainsi, aucune université de Roumanie ne monte plus parmi les premières 970 universités, d'après ce critère convenable. Après que, dans le classement Shanghai on était arrivé, en 2011, à candidater parmi les 500 premières, maintenant cela n'entre plus en discussion!;

g) Aux Jeux Olympiques de Rio de Janeiro la Roumanie est arrivée en 2016 aux plus faibles résultats olympiques des cinquante dernières années. Des sports entiers où la Roumanie comptait – le handball, le volleyball, le canotage, la gymnastique, la boxe, les luttes, etc. – se sont effondrés;

h) Chez nous lorsqu'on discute de la préparation on ne fait pas suffisamment de distinction entre le souvenir et la compréhension des connaissances, puis entre la compréhension et l'habileté de faire quelque chose des connaissances en question et entre l'habileté et le désir et entre l'action personnelle et le changement de ce qui nous entoure. Par conséquent, toute une mentalité de la suffisance de soi occupe le terrain;

²⁷ Andrei Marga, *Schimbară lumii. Globalizare, cultură, geopolitică* (București: Editura Academiei, 2013).

i) Comme l'observait un historien américain,²⁸ l'historiographie de Roumanie se rend particulièrement vulnérable dans les débats internationales par «la combinaison de forme non-démocratique avec un contenu populaire».²⁹ Aussi, les écrits professionnalisés d'histoire, qui donnent le ton à propos de l'histoire des Carpates, sont écrits ailleurs – États-Unis, Allemagne, France et d'autres.

On a enregistré aussi des situations plus graves. Les doctorats se sont compromis (par l'extension du plagiat, la nomination de directeurs de thèses incompetents, les carences des programmes). Le niveau des professorats universitaires est devenu discutable (suite à la sélection et aux mauvais critères). Sur une grande échelle les directions d'unités et d'universités (suite au système de sélection) sont paroissiales. Quelque «coupure» que l'on fasse dans le courant des nouvelles, elle suggère la compétence aproximative et le deficit de culture, qui ne sont pas étrangers à l'éducation.

Chez nous, aux crises européennes mentionnées s'ajoute la crise de la capacité administrative dans l'éducation. Depuis des années ne montent plus sur la scène des decisions des gens capables de concevoir l'éducation comme un tout. Deviennent ministres des personnes qui n'ont pas travaillé en education et non publie pas même cinq pages de leurs propres vues. D'autres sont arrivés par hasard dans cette fonction. En même temps, les indicateurs de la crise spécifique de l'éducation en Roumanie se multiplient: le décalage de la qualification par rapport aux besoins; la prolifération des diplômes sans couverture; la pauvreté de l'innovation technologique; l'état critique du débat démocratique; l'état aussi critique de la moralité publique.

4. Solutions

Ne donne pas de résultats une discussion sur la crise de l'education qui ne montre pas ce qui est à faire. Je synthétise mon opinion en quatre idées.

²⁸ Tony Judt, Timothy Snyder, *Thinking Twentieth Century* (London: Vintage Books, 2013).

²⁹ *Ibid.*, 265.

Il faut clarifier de nouveau la psychologie avec laquelle on opère dans l'éducation. On mise toujours sur «l'efficience de l'éducation» partant, comme on le voit aussi dans la loi de l'éducation de 2011 de Roumanie, d'une psychologie sommairement acquise.

Rappelons-nous qu'Ulrich Neisser³⁰ a tracé la psychologie cognitive, et John R. Anderson³¹ lui a donné une formulation qui a fait carrière dans le monde. Aucun n'a jamais dit que la psychologie est épuisée par le cognitivisme.

En tout cas, c'est le temps d'une rénovation de l'éducation en faisant appel à des approches psychologiques qui évitent l'étroitesse. La théorie des «intelligences multiples»³² a créé, comme on le sait, une brèche dans les attentes que de la cognition résulte toute la configuration de la personne. D'autres ont passés à la ré-interrogation de la nature humaine³³ sous l'aspect de la relation entre la conservation de soi et l'empathie. Entre temps, les recherches consacrées à l'apprentissage ont montré que celui-ci dépend de facteurs multiples, cognitifs et extra-cognitifs.³⁴ Récemment, on a proposé l'élargissement de la perspective, en projetant sur l'éducation l'observation du phénomène de «l'autopoïèse».³⁵

Mon opinion est, cependant, que dans une approche étendue non seulement un, mais au moins trois aspects doivent être englobés dans la discussion sur les buts de l'éducation. Par exemple, les «compétences» doivent être assumées dans le but de l'éducation, autrement l'éducation devient rhétorique. «La formation de la personne (Bildung)» doit être

³⁰ Ulrich Neisser, *Cognitive Psychology* (New York: Appleton-Century-Crofts, 1967).

³¹ John R. Anderson, *Cognitive Psychology and Its Implications* (New York: W.H. Freeman and Company, 1995).

³² Howard Gardner, *Frames of Mind. The Theory of Multiple Intelligences* (New York: Basic Books, 1983).

³³ Dacher Keltner, Jason Marsh, Jeremy Adam Smith, *The Compassionate Instinct. The Science of Human Goodness* (London: W. W. Norton and Company, 2010).

³⁴ Knud Illeris (ed.), *Teorii contemporane ale învățării, Autori de referință* (București: Trei, 2014).

³⁵ Humberto R. Maturana, Francisco J. Varela, *Autopoiesis and Cognition, Realisation of the Living* (Dordrecht: D. Reidel, 1980).

récupérée, si les sociétés ne veulent pas seulement des «spécialistes», mais aussi des gens de spécialité. Une nouvelle réponse à la question cruciale «que forme l'éducation» doit être donnée. Je défends l'idée d'un triptyque – «compétences», «habiletés de base (basics)» et «la formation pour les valeurs»³⁶ – à la base de l'éducation.

Il faut repenser «le but de l'école». Les analyses européennes attirent l'attention sur le fait que 40% des élèves ont de l'angoisse à l'école. Un quart des jeunes n'arrivent pas à une formation mûre.³⁷ Les expériences de l'école détournent de la quête et du plaisir de la découverte personnelle vers le conformisme. L'éducation pour la citoyenneté reste négligée, de sorte que l'engagement civique de la jeunesse diminue³⁸ la formation se fait *obsessivement* pour le présent, l'avenir sortant en fait de la discussion. On pense de façon égoïste, «l'intégration et l'inclusion étant des mots étrangers».³⁹ Un professeur qui rencontre chaque jour environ cent élèves ne peut pas s'occuper de leur motivation et fait une activité en quelque sorte formelle d'enseignement et d'examen. Les récentes recherches sur le cerveau attestent que l'enthousiasme est une prémisse fondamentale de l'apprentissage durable⁴⁰ et de la créativité. Dans nos sociétés la corrélation entre l'origine sociale et l'achèvement des études est trop étroite.

En Europe il devient toujours plus clair que «la réparation» du système d'éducation existant ne donne pas de résultat. Il est besoin du «courage de la vision»⁴¹ et de changements. La meilleure proposition de jusqu'à présent vise la réorientation de la préparation des jeunes sur trois directions corrélées: «apprendre à agir», «apprendre à acquérir des connaissances» et «apprendre à vivre avec les autres». L'école passerait

³⁶ Voir Andrei Marga, *Anii reformei. 1997-2000* (Cluj-Napoca: EFES, 2002).

³⁷ Margret Rasfeld, Peter Spiegel, *EduAction. Wir machen Schule* (Hamburg: Murrmann, 2012), 23.

³⁸ *Ibid.*, 53.

³⁹ *Ibid.*, 123.

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, 195.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*, 26.

ainsi de «la livraison de connaissances (*unterrichten*)» à «la construction du jeune homme»; de l'enseignant comme «applicateur du curriculum» à l'enseignant comme «développeur de potentiel»; de «motiver» le jeune à «l'enthousiasmer»; de «l'enseignement (*Unterricht*), à «l'apprentissage»; de «l'instruction» à «l'auto-organisation»; de «l'uniformité centrée sur le plan» à «la multiplicité centrée sur l'apprentissage»; de la mise en valeur de «la tête» à «la tête, le cœur et la main»; de «l'intelligence cognitive» aux «intelligences multiples»; de la «reprise d'une perspective» à «la capacité de changer de perspective»; de «l'évitement du risque» à «l'esprit entrepreneur». ⁴² Seulement ainsi l'école pourra accueillir le monde qui se préfigure – où la première rencontre est celle avec l'incertitude.

Nous ne pouvons ne pas remarquer, avec les spécialistes américains, le processus d'apprentissage qui a lieu au niveau de l'éducation en Chine. Sous trois aspects.

Le premier est celui que dans chaque enfant ou adolescent chinois se trouve un être, à savoir Confucius, qui gouverne le trajet éducationnel ⁴³ à commencer par le «respect filial» des devanciers. ⁴⁴

Le deuxième se réfère à des faits caractéristiques. Par exemple, la route par laquelle avance l'élève et l'étudiant en est une «très étroite», ⁴⁵ «la discipline et l'étude intense» prévalent, ⁴⁶ «le curriculum est rigoureusement respecté», les enfants, y inclus ceux avec des handicaps, suivent le même programme, ⁴⁷ chaque écolier suit avec ténacité ses qualificatifs aux vérifications, ⁴⁸ le système cultive des vertus citoyennes, ⁴⁹ le patriotisme est la valeur centrale. ⁵⁰

⁴² Ibid., 27-29.

⁴³ Lenora Chu, *Little soldiers. An American Boy, a Chinese School, and the Global Race to Achieve* (New York: Harper, 2017), 24.

⁴⁴ Ibid., 26.

⁴⁵ Ibid., 36.

⁴⁶ Ibid., 82.

⁴⁷ Ibid., 93.

⁴⁸ Ibid., 100.

⁴⁹ Ibid., 144.

⁵⁰ Ibid., 146.

Le troisième est que le changement est à l'ordre du jour dans les écoles chinoises, et «l'individualité et le choix sont également dans le menu».⁵¹ Plus rapidement que n'importe où dans le monde, en Chine a lieu une assimilation d'idées neuves et leur combinaison efficace avec des idées d'une vénérable ancienneté dans une période de «changements sans précédent».⁵²

Je considère qu'il est temps que l'on adopte *La Déclaration PostBologne*.⁵³ En rapport avec la configuration défendue dans *La Déclaration de Bologne* (1999), l'accent devra être déplacé de la durée des études sur leur but et leur contenu. La flexibilisation, y inclus de la durée, doit prendre la place de l'uniformisation et l'on mettra fin à la tendance d'imitation dans les universités, y inclus par la réorganisation des spécialisations.

Il s'agit ensuite d'assumer une nouvelle division des sciences non seulement en-deçà d'Hegel et en-deçà de Carnap, mis aussi en-deçà de la chute actuelle dans la rhapsodie, parfois dans l'anarchie épistémologique. Il s'agit d'assumer de nouveau la mission de l'université comme formatrice de spécialistes au plus haut niveau de la connaissance et des fonctions diverses de l'université, y inclus de centre de diffusion de la connaissance, de formation de spécialistes, de centre de recherche, d'instance critique argumentative, de promoteur des droits et de la justice.

L'Université PostBologne doit viser, dans le contexte de la réaffirmation des identités dans le monde d'aujourd'hui, l'augmentation de l'impact social. L'Universalité, à laquelle les universités restent liées, commence par des réalisations concrètes pour les communautés déterminées, donc, en rapport avec le cadre national. Une université doit examiner comment – dans le contexte de l'économie de marché, de l'État de droit, de la démocratie, de l'internationalisation, de l'augmentation de

⁵¹ Ibid., 300.

⁵² Ibid., 302.

⁵³ Pour les détails voir Andrei Marga, "The PostBologna University," dans Andrei Marga, *The Sense of our Days History*, en cours d'apparition.

l'importance de la réflexivité – elle peut soutenir la marche vers une société plus avancée.

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Latent Political Practices in Ukraine: the Research by Analytical Secret Service Instruments

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Abstract. The nature and mechanisms of latent political processes manifestations are revealed. Inefficient government work and management is becoming the main cause of corruption as a socio-political and legal reality. The main attention is drawn to the cases of political corruption after the Revolution of Dignity among the ruling elite of Ukraine. The most significant brakes on the way of social and political modernization of our country, remains the political corruption that mimicked to the new institutional and procedural practices. The chosen topic is relevant in the theoretical aspect giving the possibility to explore new conceptual approaches to the essence of the latent political practice phenomena and suggest new methodological principles of information and analytical investigation by means of general scientific and special scientific methods of political science, psychology and law as well as in the practical aspect as a provision of options of the society's influence on the limitation of political corruption in Ukraine under conditions of "hybrid war" launched by the Russian Federation and lack of actual results of the social and political modernization of the country.

Keywords: analytical intelligence, latent political practices, Ukraine.

Introduction

The goal of this work is an attempt of scientific analysis of the causes and nature of latent political practices implementation in the modern Ukraine on the basis of the interdisciplinary approach and updated methodological framework. The following research tasks must be completed according to the target goal: to define the essence and interrelations of analytics, information analytics and analytical intelligence; to reveal

characteristic features of latent political practices in Ukraine in 2014-2016; to describe the most common manifestations of political corruption and existence of patron-client relationships in the ruling political class of Ukraine detected according to the results of the information and analytical investigations; to point out the necessity of the formulation of strategy and tactics to counteract latent political practices as one of the main internal threats to the existence of the independent Ukraine.

The theoretical and methodological principles of the research by means of the analytical intelligence tools in general and the countermeasures against threats of criminogenic nature are suggested in the works of national researchers (1-7), however there are no comprehensive studies of the indicated problems which could be useful to the foreign academic community, in particular, for better understanding of the substance of latent political practices as a characteristic feature of the modern political process in Ukraine.

As a working hypothesis of the proposed study, it may be assumed that the degree and nature of the destructive impact of individual events, phenomena and processes in the domestic political sphere, the economy, the social sphere, information activities, the fight against organized crime and corruption in Ukraine are not only conditioned by the corresponding undisguised intervention of the country-aggressor, but also have an intra-Ukrainian nature, caused by the implementation of the latent interests of prominent representatives of the post-war political ruling class in Ukraine (Bloc Poroshenko / Popular Front Yatsenyuk, A. Avakov and A. Turchinov / "Vinnytsia" group of Prime Minister of Ukraine, V. Groisman). In the proposed work develop the issues posed in previous publications¹.

The following statement can serve as a working hypothesis of this research: the use of the modern interdisciplinary methods of detection,

¹ V. Gulay, Zaostrzenie kryzysu politycznego w Ukrainie w roku 2016 jako wyzwania wewnętrzne i zagrożenie bezpieczeństwa narodowego Ukrainy oraz perspektywy stosunków z państwami sąsiednimi, *Studia Społeczne*, № 18 (2017): 11-17; V. Gulay, Utajone praktyki korupcji politycznej na Ukrainie (2014-2016 rr.), *Forum Politologiczne*, vol. 21 (2017): 309-333.

resistance and prevention of latent political practices spread allows solving strategic objectives of Ukraine more efficiently under conditions of “hybrid war” launched by the Russian Federation in political, economic, legal and security spheres.

Main Part

In the broadest possible sense of the term, analytics is an integrated set of principles for methodological, organizational and engineering provision of the individual and collective intellectual activity which allows processing information efficiently for the purpose of improving the quality of current and newly acquired knowledge as well as database provisioning for the best management decision making. The information and analytical activity in its turn is a special area of information activity connected with the detection, processing, storage and dissemination of the processed data mainly in the management, political, legal or economic spheres.

The following basic levels of the information and analytical work are distinguished: information level (search, collection, storage) and analytical level (integration, classification of data). The next stages of the information and analytical activity can be specified, including in the field of analytical intelligence: acquisition of raw data; selection of required data; processing and accumulation of raw and other data; storage of data; transfer of data to a consumer. When viewing in detail, for example, the collection of data is performed by means of getting acquainted with the scientific and technical, political and diplomatic, social and political, military, economic, financial and other information disseminated by mass media, libraries, archive institutions, internet, information agencies, etc.

Data mining is a secret conspiratorial procedure of a secret retrieval of a storage device containing confidential, secret and other important data, i.e. misappropriation, theft. Data acquisition is a procedure of receiving confidential, secret and other important data or a storage device containing it from a particular natural or legal person for temporary or permanent use on a fee basis. The analytical intelligence in its turn is the way to perform an

operational search the essence of which lies in the system of actions possessing characteristics of technologies and information cycle that allows receiving operational investigative information by detecting and analyzing messages and data from different sources.

Information analytics is not only another new organizational kind of the above agencies. Its essential and basic function differs principally from the tasks set on the above agencies in information domain. Its key goals, among others, are: analytic transformation of information and its structural systematization (informational analysis, generalization, reduction; consolidation of huge information spaces in the form of databases and their expansion). Information analytics' primary task is to qualitatively and contently transform the information, functionally intersecting in this respect with scientific (producing new knowledge) and administrative (working out options of decisions, scenarios) activity, employing all the opportunities of such intelligence agencies, operating actively their information products and services. Thus, information analytics as an integral part of information activity covers certain processes of analytic and information activity predetermines completion of certain stages and procedures qualified information analysts have to master².

When considered as an activity, the information analytics can be identified to some extent with the information and analytical activity and from the perspective of a process approach – as a set of intellectual processes and engineering procedures focused on a particular object, the execution of which in a certain consequence guarantees the solution to the task in hand³.

The backbone of information-and-analytic activity (IAA) is to apply, on the stage of systematization, methods of analytic processing of information (information ingredient) and methods of analysis basing on the

² L. Filipova, I. Zakharova, "Analitichna skladova informatsiynoyi diyal'nosti: utochnennyya sutnosti, oznak i protsesiv," www.nbu.gov.ua/old_jrn/soc_gum/...28/V28-2-01.pdf (accessed 28 May 2019).

³ A. Mytko, *Politychna analityka: navchal'nyy posibnyk*, Skhidnoyevropeys'kyy natsional'nyy universytet imeni Lesi Ukrainky, Luts'k, 2015.

information knowledge received in the result of processing of information spaces (analytic ingredient). It evidences two stages of IAA, on the phase of forming structural information and on the phase of performing system analysis of particular practical activity aimed at decision making. Development of information-and-analytic maintenance of different spheres facilitates more effective use of information in administrative processes⁴.

The information and analytical activity in its turn is a special area of information activity connected with the detection, processing, storage and dissemination of the processed data mainly in the management, political, legal or economic spheres.

The need for information and analytic activity in general and analytic intelligence in particular resulted in appearance of Information Analysis Organizations. Their task is to continuously collect information, both published and unpublished, on the significant and long-term problems of state, sphere of activity, or just individual organization; also, they have to select, analyze, estimate and classify data according to the problem structure and provide interested customers with these data, etc.

All and any kind of intelligence (analytic, strategic, competitive, etc.) is cyclic in its nature and takes the following stages:

- 1) Setting the task and carrying out the survey;
- 2) Action plan which defines means and forces to achieve the goal;
- 3) Collection of data and other important information;
- 4) Analysis of the received information and making predictions;
- 5) Preparation of outcoming analytical documents;
- 6) Sending out the analytical product to consumers;
- 7) Approbation of results of the survey and hypothetical return to the first stage to specify primary task setting⁵.

⁴ L. Filipova, I. Zakharova, *Op. cit.*

⁵ O. Busol, "Analitychna rozvidka v Ukraini yak samostiyyny napryam diyal'nosti derzhavnykh orhaniv i nederzhavnykh pidpryemstv," *Naukovyy visnyk Kyivivs'koho natsional'noho universytetu vnutrishnikh sprav*, vypusk 2, Kyiv, 2010.

It should be pointed out that term “analytic intelligence” first appeared in regulatory documents of the Ministry of Home Affairs (MHA) of Russia in 1992 to determine special form of activity of response investigation team. Analytic Intelligence was defined as intelligence investigation, technique intelligence, complex investigation of the results of covert observation, operative instructions, notifications from the undeclared members of intelligence agency, data captured from numerous canals of communication, as well as analysis of notifications, publications, speeches made both before public and in mass media, statistic data and information from state and non-state computerized databases and information systems⁶.

In the course of time, analytic intelligence tended to mean new (undefined yet) data received on the basis of complex analysis of response investigation information. In other words, “analytic intelligence” implies solving the problem of classification.

Russian scientist S. Ovchynskyi defined “analytic intelligence” as “intelligence within information environment” and, on the other hand, as “receiving new knowledge concerning the investigating object on the basis of analytic processing of the already obtained investigation data and evidences”⁷. Of similar opinion is O. Dolzhenkov who regards “analytic intelligence” as intelligence in information domain which aims to investigate phenomena and objects on the basis of analytic data and facts processing⁸. According to O. Busol, the major task of the analytical intelligence is

⁶ A. Movchan, “Ponyattya ta sutnist’ analitychnoyi rozvidky yak osoblyvo formy informatsiyno-analitychnoyi roboty v ORD,” *Naukovyy visnyk L’vivskoho derzhavnoho universytetu vnutrishnikh sprav*, № 3, L’viv, 2012.

⁷ F. Oryshchuk, “Heneral’nyy i yoho komanda. Kym «onovlyuye» prokuraturu Lutsenko,” <http://glavcom.ua/publications/generalniy-i-yogo-komanda-kim-onovlyuje-prokuraturu-lucenko-361019.html> (accessed 28 May 2019).

⁸ O. Dolzhenkov, “Innovatsiyi – chynnyk optymizatsiyi operatyvno- rozshukovoyi diyal’nosti,” *Aktual’ni problemy operatyvno-rozshukovoyi diyal’nosti*, Visnyk LAVS MVS im. 10-rychchya nezalezhnosti Ukrainy, Spetsial’nyy vypusk № 2, Luhans’k, 2003.

detection and prevention of external threats as well as forecast of situations in certain spheres⁹.

The informal political practices penetrate into legitimate state institutions in the transitional societies to which, it should be noted with regret, Ukraine is referred taking into consideration the reliable results of the previous years concerning the modern state building of Ukraine. At the same time the system of patron-client ties that control the access of the participants of political and economic field to various resources is established based on the relations of personal dependence.

The political mimicry is, among other, a consequence of predominance of conformity values; conformity is understood to mean a type of social action resulting in the aspiration of a person to conform to the opinion of majority. At that, it is believed that conformity is conditioned by two main reasons: a social action i.e. caused by a sense of social identity, desire to fit in with a group or society as well as need for approval of others; personal influence when it is caused by the lack of self-confidence of a person and its desire to act in the right way. Interpreted by the foreign researchers the conformity is determined as a change in behavior due to the real or imagined influence of other people and is considered to be a response of an individual to an information or normative social influence¹⁰.

As it is known, on February 27, 2014, the European Choice parliamentary coalition consisting of 250 deputies was formed in Ukraine represented by three former opposition parties (All-Ukrainian Union "Batkivshchyna", All-Ukrainian Union "Svoboda", "Ukrainian Democratic Alliance for Reform" (UDAR) and two deputy groups ("Ekonomichniy rozvytok" and "Suverenna yevropeiska Ukraina") consisting mainly of the former members of the Party of Regions. As advised by this coalition, Arseniy Yatsenyuk was appointed the Prime Minister of Ukraine by the majority of people's deputies and formed a new government.

⁹ O. Busol, *Op. cit.*

¹⁰ S. Harkavets', *Psykhohohiya politychnoho vyboru: navchal'nyy posibnyk*, vydavnytstvo Skhidnoukrayins'koho natsional'noho universytetu imeni V. Dalya, Luhans'k, 2006.

The removal of V. Yanukovych from power by the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine with the participation of the deputies who severed themselves from the former ruling Party of Regions and a further formation of the government authorities and administration bodies from among the representatives of “Batktivshchyna”, “Svoboda” and “UDAR” under the so called quota principle convincingly demonstrated the continuing latent political practices in the Ukrainian political elite, which they themselves opposed from the parliament’s rostrum in 2010-2014 and which are not perceived by the Ukrainian civil society as a new driving force of social development.

It is our belief that the results of the voting in the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine for the Prime Minister Volodymyr Groysman (“for” 131 deputies of the “Petro Poroshenko Bloc” faction and 75 deputies of the “Narodnyi front” faction (total 206 deputies) and 16 deputies of the “Volia narodu” deputy group, 23 of “Vidrodzhennia”, 11 unaffiliated) showed that there is no coalition in the Verkhovna Rada since it was able to provide only 206 deputies’ votes, while the minimum of 226 votes was required, and the rest ones were received thanks to the votes of 40 former members of the Party of Regions and thus the statement of the President Petro Poroshenko that the parliamentary-governmental crisis is over and a new Cabinet of Ministers is professional and politically responsible is premature.

In the middle of April 2016 the President of Ukraine P. Poroshenko made a number of personnel changes in the steering apparatus of the Security Service of Ukraine. In particular, the head of the state signed the decree on the dismissal of the first deputy head of the Security Service of Ukraine, the head of the Main Directorate for Combating Corruption and Organized Crime (“K” Directorate) Viktor Trepak. According to the sources of the leading analytical Ukrainian publication “Dzerkalo Tyzhnia Ukrayina” / DT.UA, in the presidential administration Trepak was offered to retain the post of the first deputy head of the Security Service of Ukraine under condition that the management of the “K” Directorate to be transferred to Pavlo Demchyna. But the general Trepak rejected this offer. Pavlo

Demchyna (who was awarded the major general rank by the President on March 25, the Day of the Security Service of Ukraine) performed the duties of the “K” Directorate head during these five months. Demchyna is a protégé of Ihor Kononenko, the deputy of the “Petro Poroshenko Bloc” parliament faction and one of the President’s closest allies. The fact of the close ties of Kononenko and Demchyna was also confirmed by Viktor Trepak in his interview to DT.UA. Moreover, it is known that Demchyna is a godfather of the children of Mykola Herasymyuk (the first deputy head of the Prosecutor General’s Office of Ukraine with Vitaliy Yarema being the Prosecutor General) and Oleh Zalisko (the current deputy head of the Prosecutor General). As Demchyna received the leading position in “K” Directorate of the Security Service of Ukraine the jokes appeared that now the main department fully justifies its name since “K” is the first letter in Kononenko’s surname¹¹.

The article of F. Oryshchuk “Prosecutor General and His Team. Who Lutsenko “Renews” the Prosecutor’s Office With” in the online newspaper “Glavkom” became one of the most comprehensive researches which using the tools of analytical intelligence studies the personnel policy of a new Prosecutor General of Ukraine Yuriy Lutsenko who makes big comments on a number of criminal proceedings opened in June-July 2016 against some senior officials. In particular, the author recalls, not without reason, that after having taken charge of the Prosecutor General’s Office of Ukraine Yuriy Lutsenko, the former leader of the “Petro Poroshenko Bloc” faction, appointed Dmytro Storozhuk, the “Narodnyi front” deputy, as his first deputy head. Anton Herashchenko, the “Narodnyi front” deputy, was quite explicit in his comment to journalists about such parity being a manifestation of coalition agreement. The second post in the Prosecutor General’s Office for Storozhuk was the main condition of supporting Lutsenko’s candidacy by the “Narodnyi front” during the voting in the parliament¹². As it turned out, Lutsenko sticks to such balance during the

¹¹ O. Kukhareno, “Osoblyvo tsinni kadry,” *Dzerkalo tyzhnya-Ukrayina*, № 14, 260 (2016).

¹² F. Oryshchuk, *Op. cit.*

personnel purges on other levels as well. For instance, according to the sources of the “Glavkom”, the appointment of Roman Hovda to the post of the Prosecutor of Kyiv was patronized by Serhiy Pashynskiy and Andriy Ivanchuk, deputies of the “Narodnyi front”. At the same time Dmytro Chybisov, who was recommended by the entourage of Lutsenko himself, got the post of the Prosecutor of Kyiv Region.

The appointment of Vitaliy Tryhubenko as the Prosecutor of Kherson Region can hardly be called a non-political one. Vitaliy Tryhubenko is a younger brother of Serhiy Tryhubenko, the deputy of the “Petro Poroshenko Bloc”. The latter is believed by mass media to have close ties with Ihor Kononenko, the influential deputy head of the “Petro Poroshenko Bloc” faction. In 2015 there were rumours about the appointment of Tryhubenko-senior as the Minister of Agrarian Policy. Prior to that, he held a post of the head of the State Inspection of Agriculture of Ukraine. The name of Serhiy Tryhubenko has recently appeared in a headline-making journalist investigation of “Nashi hroshi” TV program. It stated that the deputy held control over some income generating state-owned energy assets – Centrenergo PJSC and Krasnolymanska coal mine.

As to the new personnel, Oleh Nechyporenko is worth mentioning – the head of the first investigation division of the Department for Investigation of Crimes Committed by the Officers of the Prosecutor General’s Office. O. Nechyporenko is a son of Valentyn Nechyporenko, a deputy of the “Vidrodzhennia” party (former “Partiia Rehioniv”) controlled by Vitaliy Khomutynnyk. Nechyporenko-junior was appointed to this post not long after the successful parliamentary voting for the election of Yuriy Lutsenko as the Prosecutor General. As the people’s deputy Serhiy Leshchenko later remarked, this appointment was a political “settlement” for supporting Lutsenko as the Prosecutor General. It should be recalled that the “Vidrodzhennia” party, including Valentyn Nechyporenko himself, had prior promoted the law which allowed the former head of the Ministry of Internal Affairs to become the Prosecutor General and supported Lutsenko’s appointment as the head of the Prosecutor General’s Office of Ukraine.

In our opinion, a twofold increase in gas, electricity and utility tariffs during May-July 2016 will have negative effects on the social and political situation in Ukraine in autumn and winter this year considering the lack of the proper calculations and “contractual” nature of the actions of the members of the National Commission for State Regulation of Energy and Public Utilities. The head and 6 members of the National Commission for State Regulation of Energy and Public Utilities are appointed at the sole discretion of the President Petro Poroshenko although under the Constitution he has no right to create bodies of executive power.

Let’s briefly review the patron-client ties in the above-mentioned commission. Prior to the post of the head of the National Commission for State Regulation of Energy and Public Utilities Dmytro Vovk worked in the “Roshen” corporation owned by Petro Poroshenko where he was responsible for the increase in sales of production in Russia; Borys Tsyhanenko was an official in the structure of the Russian businessman Kostyantyn Hryhoryshyn and in “Kyivenergo” of Rinat Akhmetov; Volodymyr Yevdokimov is a business partner of Arseniy Yatsenyuk’s ally; Yuriy Hollyak is connected with the magnate Dmytro Firtash; Viktoriya Morozova is connected with the structures of Hryhoryshyn. The income and benefits from the increase in tariffs will be reaped by: 7 regional power distribution companies owned by VS Energy controlled by the Russian Babakov, Hiner and Voyevodin; 4 companies of DTEK holding (oligarch Akhmetov); 3 regional power distribution companies – the company from the orbit of the oligarchs I. Kolomoyskyi and Russian Hryhoryshyn; 2 regional power distribution companies owned by Hryhoryshyn through ICU company where the head of the National Commission for State Regulation of Energy and Public Utilities D. Vovk used to work; 2 regional power distribution companies owned by Surkis brothers; 2 regional power distribution companies owned by S. Lyovochkin and Yu. Boyko of the “Opozytsiinyi Blok” party¹³.

¹³ Yuriy Derevyanko, “Yuriy Derevyanko,” <https://www.facebook.com/derevyanko.yuriy/posts/1041591379241936:0> (accessed 28 May 2019).

We share the same views with one of the most authoritative Ukrainian journalists Yuliya Mostova that the society must make major efforts during this year and a half. It has to learn to distinguish a real opposition from the imitators; to find the sources of political parties financing which will be alternative to the existing non-alternative oligarchic ones; to transfer from the politics of the exposure of government to the creation of instruments able to build a brand new politics; to go from the Facebook parties to real state building, from self-admiration to self-irony, from confidence of anyone who receives thousand Facebook likes that they can “show everyone how to rule the state” to the ability to control their ambitions as well as the worthlessness of these ambitions compared to an incredibly hard work awaiting for everyone who disagrees with the statement that Ukraine is a failed state¹⁴.

The coalition shareholders do not hide their long-term shared control over the Ministries, even after their ministers dropped out of the government. Competitions to fill the vacancies of high state positions have underwent recently severe critics. Even government officers claimed complete profane of this idea. Head Ministers of the Ministry of Infrastructure and Ministry of Healthcare, Volodymyr Omelian and Uliana Suprun respectively, have argued strongly against results of the competitions to fill the posts of state secretaries of these two Ministries. Omelian and Suprun claim the competitions to be non-transparent, and candidates chosen by the competition commission – to be either not qualified enough or the representative of “semi-criminal business groups”. It is worth mentioning that Prime Minister Volodymyr Hroismann is not going to take into consideration the whims of the conflicting ministers and is likely to appoint the above chosen state secretaries by all means. At the same time, situation around the competition to fill the post of the Chief of State Intelligence Bureau becomes tougher and tougher: observers are close to come to the conclusion that the commission tends to be favorable to the candidates recommended by the President Administration. Leaving alone

¹⁴ Y. U. Mostovaya, “Tymchasovyy uryad,” *Dzerkalo tyzhnya-Ukrayina*, № 14, 260 (2016).

the corresponding competitions to fill the posts of heads of region administration, won exclusively by the Bankova candidates (or President candidates). Recently, the competition to fill the posts of the head of Odessa Region Administration has been won by the candidate of Arsenii Yatseniuk circle, but it may be viewed as a result of a deal¹⁵.

One of the latest examples of application the methods of analytic investigation to the interests of society is the publication of the article "Yanukovych' Coal Factories to be transposed to Kononenko Ownership" which appeared on the site "Our Money". Coal factories such as "Ukraina", "Komsomolska" and "Rossia" once owned by Oleksandr Yanukovych, the elder son of ex-president Viktor Yanukovych, now became property of Vitalii Kropachov. Kropachov also plans to become the owner of the coal factory "Chervonohradska", which is an integral part of the two West-Ukrainian state complexes, "Lviv Coal" and "Volyn Coal". For the present time, coal factory "Chervonohradska" is under control of Nataliia Korolevska, state deputy from "Opposition Bloc" and her business-partner Oleksandr Isaiev, the resident of Moscow. It was revealed in November that General Prosecutor's Office has opened criminal case against illegal privatization of the daughter company coal factory "Chervonohradska". Kropachov is the creation of Ihor Kononeko, the first Vice-head of the fraction of Bloc of Petro Poroshenko (BPP) and business-partner of Petro Poroshenko. Kropachov is involved in creation the "Shakhtarsk" and "Tornado" volunteer battalions. In August he pretended to substitute state deputy Serhii Trehubenko (BPP) as a non-official supervisor of the coal industry within Ihor Kononenko group. The latter is believed to get acquainted with Kropachov through Anton Herashchenko, Minister of Home Affairs' assistant. Kropachov is also a

¹⁵ P. Vuyets', "«Ty meni – ya tobi». Kadrovi konkursy chy profanatsiya," <http://glavcom.ua/publications/ti-meni-ya-tobi-kadrovi-konkursi-chi-profanatsiya-389578.html> (accessed 28 May 2019).

minority shareholder of state enterprise “CentreEnergo”, Oleksandr Visir, Kononenko’s former assistant, being the Head of Board there¹⁶.

President Petro Poroshenko, to the view of some experts, and the author shares this view in general, appears not to have political allies by the end of 2016, and performs his activity basing exclusively on his close business circle, military forces and occasionally – on oligarchs’ neutral position. State power structures have stuck in political corruption and personal fighting to get access to financial flows. Most of political player and oligarchs do not like Poroshenko’s enforcement and concentration of power in his hands, because he seems to perform simultaneously functions of a political referee, president and oligarch. That is why formation of anti-president coalition is likely to take place in the year to come, and this may cause potential additional risks to national security¹⁷.

At the same time, the character and level of destructive influence of certain events, phenomena and processes in both external and internal spheres as well as economy, social sphere, information activity, anti-criminal and anti-corruption activity should also be taken into consideration, as they are caused not only by unhidden intervention of the conquering state, but are also of typical internal Ukrainian nature and grew from latent interests of current individual and group representatives of Post-Maidan ruling class in Ukraine as a dominant vector of social, political, information and social-economic activity of state institutions.

One can not ignore the fact that the current political system in Ukraine is characterized by such special features of kleptocracy as corruption, lobbying, lack of long-term goals. This process generates public divisions, impedes the development of the country, relations with neighboring states. Ukraine has formed a kind of political and economic

¹⁶ “Vuhil’ni fabryky Yanukovycha pereyshly u vlasnist’ protezhe Kononenka,” <http://nashigroshi.org/2016/12/26/vuhilni-fabryky-yanukovycha-pereyshly-u-vlasnist-protezhe-kononenka/> (accessed 28 May 2019).

¹⁷ A. Oktysyuk, “Oliharkhy proty prezidenta: shcho chekaye na Poroshenka v 2017 rotsi,” <http://apostrophe.ua/ua/article/politics/government/2016-12-16/oligarhi-protiv-prezident-a-chto-jdet-poroshenko-v-2017-godu/8930> (accessed 28 May 2019).

unity of oligarchic clans and party leaders, and business empires have a significant influence on the state of the economy and the political reputation of the state leadership.

Clientelism of modern Ukrainian government is an obstacle to the progress of Ukrainian society. This process has a parasitic nature, since it focuses on distribution, rather than on the production of public wealth. This leads to the spread of cynicism, which offset social morality. The ruling political regime in Ukraine is increasingly becoming threatening, destructive features, since the negative influence of the subject of power on the consciousness, behavior and actions of people leads to a violation of the normal structure or destruction, destruction, removal of the object (institutions, traditions, living conditions, etc.).

The specifics of the ruling political class of Ukraine are manifested in the implementation of strategies for self-enrichment, which obviously leads to neglect of public interests and uncontrolled and permissiveness. The inevitable aggravation of the political crisis in Ukraine allows us to talk about the problem of political pseudo-realism as a result of the perception of virtual political representations and images that have nothing (or very few) in common with objective political reality. The formation of political pseudo-reality is directly influenced by political zombies through political fake, political cyberprotection, political trolling, and so on. When forming a political pseudoreal reality in modern Ukrainian realities, the task of constructing simple, attractive, consistent and accessible for perception of images, which usually have little in common with real political reality, aimed at the formation and meeting the expectations and needs of the masses, the construction of political values-semantic spaces.

Separately, consideration should be given to the issue of legalizing the latent influence of political and business groups in the process of decentralization. The author's assumption of the prerequisites, results and implications of the first elections of the respective councils, heads and parishes in the united territorial communities suggests that during the 2015-2018 period transparency and equality of conditions were not always

ensured, the risk of seizing power by irresponsible populist political forces and / or representatives of interested business structures. In this case, the shortcomings of the electoral system will lead to the formation of ineffective, corrupt local authorities, which by their actions will increase social tension and undermine the credibility of the state.

The inevitable aggravation of the political crisis in Ukraine further exacerbates the problem of destructive socio-psychological influence of the implementation of strategies of diverting attention from the problems of political corruption into the national security of Ukraine at the present stage through the formation of social and communicative pseudo-realities, where massive propaganda, ideological, manipulative activity is reduced to the formation of deformed value, symbolic, ideological and behavioral systems introduced into the mass public consciousness for distortion with idomosti certain groups or Ukrainian society.

Conclusions

Summing up the preliminary results of the consideration of this problem we have to emphasize that the widespread corruption modified to new forms, simulation of economic and legal reforms typical of the modern stage of the development of Ukraine constitute the most serious internal threat to the existence of the Ukrainian state under conditions of the undeclared “hybrid war” of the Russian Federation in general and to the implementation of the EU-Ukraine Association Agreement in the first place. The political corruption that assimilated to new institutional and procedural practices remains the major impediment to the social and political modernization of Ukraine. The recent demonstrational promotional events concerning the detection and punishment for corruption crimes of separate senior officials took over the mass media of Ukraine but neither the majority of the Ukrainian society able to think critically nor a civilized world waiting for the urgent and efficient steps towards the modernization of Ukraine can be deceived by such actions. The clientarism of the modern Ukrainian authorities impedes the progress of the Ukrainian society. Besides, the

assistance in creating the parallel shadow structures and hindering the formation of the independence of citizens and free development and functioning of citizens and society should be distinguished among the faults of political practices in general. This process has parasitic nature because it is focused on the allocation of social wealth instead of its production. The social and political inefficiency is typical of it since it leads to the spread of cynicism which levels down public morals. The ruling political regime in Ukraine acquires more and more threatening destructive features when a negative influence on the part of the subject of power on the consciousness, behavior and actions of people leads to the violation of the normal structure or elimination and destruction of the object (institutions, traditions, living condition, etc.). Under these conditions the new techniques of detection, prevention and counteraction to latent political practices dominant in the Ukrainian political-institutional and political-cultural space, such as analytical intelligence in the public interests, become of particular importance.

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Protection of Intellectual Property Rights in the European Union in the Process of Harmonization

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Abstract. The article analysis protection of intellectual property rights within the EU as one of the important factors in the development of an innovation-oriented economy. It is noted that a number of features of the national legislations of the EU Member States regarding intellectual property rights create obstacles for harmonization in this area. At the same time, the processes of harmonization and unification of intellectual property rights in the EU are developing at different rates depending on the specific type of these rights. The article raises the question of the existence at the moment of specific principles and common grounds that contribute to the harmonization of EU intellectual property rights. In this regard, the relevant EU legislation of both primary and secondary levels is considered.

Keywords: European Union; intellectual property law; principles; harmonization.

The European Union (EU) is today one of the largest regional organizations, which can be characterized as a supranational association of countries with mechanisms of direct influence on national legislation. These features of the EU law, arising from the fundamental goal of creating a single economic and political space, have led to the fact that the legal regulation of intellectual property within the framework of this union has anticipated many international universal and regional mechanisms in this area. From this point of view, it can indeed be argued that the system of “legal protection of intellectual property in the EU is currently more modernized, including areas of protection that are currently not adequately regulated at the international universal level within WIPO”.¹

¹ Adel Abdullin, “Intellectual property law in the European Union: genesis, unification, development prospects” (Ph.D. diss., Russian State University of Justice, 2006), 12.

As known, the EU is committed to achieving the highest level of integration of its Member States. At the same time, the states within the EU before the integration association had sufficiently developed national legal institutions, including those covering the protection of intellectual property rights. However, in the conditions of the emergence and development of a common market, single European economic space, the development of cumulative intellectual property rights has become particularly important.

The issue of creating a single intellectual property right has been significantly updated within the framework of the European Union since the beginning of the 21st century, when the organization faced significant internal and foreign policy problems. As known, during this period, the EU accepted ten members of central and Eastern Europe at once, which could not but affect the economic situation and legal regulation mechanisms of the union as a whole. New states significantly lagged behind the rest of the Member States in terms of integration and the level of economic development. In these conditions, it was necessary to develop and improve the mechanisms for general regulation of business activities and alignment the legal field throughout the entire space of the European Union. It should also be borne in mind that for Europe this was a period of some lag behind the United States and some other developed countries in the field of labor productivity. The development of knowledge-intensive production areas along the whole perimeter of European integration has become an obvious need and in this direction a number of steps have been taken, including such as increasing funding for research and development (R & D). That is why, the ten-year European strategy for the development of the economy, calculated until 2020, notes the protection of intellectual property, as a key factor for further scientific and technological progress and innovation, and says it is crucial for strengthening the EU's competitive position in the global economy.² Thus, the EU has set as its goal the development of an

² EUROPE 2020: A European strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth, http://eunec.vlor.be/detail_bestanden/doc014%20Europe%202020.pdf (accessed 7 May 2019).

innovation-oriented economy based on an advanced scientific and technological base. The starting point of this policy was “more effective protection of intellectual property, which gave impetus to the subsequent renewal and development of the entire chain of economic relations.”³

The main task of the EU as an exclusive integration association is to ensure a permanent and well-coordinated mechanism for the functioning of the internal market. In the process of creating this economic space, it was necessary to create a certain legal mechanism that would become common in the entire union. In areas such as monetary policy, customs and trade policy were prepared specific provisions in the Lisbon Treaty, in which these areas were assigned to the exclusive competence of the European Union. This means that in these areas, Member States transfer their powers to the bodies of the European Union and these bodies, in turn, have the right to issue regulations on these issues that have direct effect on the territory of the organization’s Member States. However, with intellectual rights, the situation was somewhat different. The territorial limitation of intellectual rights to the framework of one state has become a problem for the rapid unification of state legislations in this field. Intellectual property rights came into conflict with the original goals and objectives of the EU and became a factor hampering the process of creating a common market. Another obstacle was the unwillingness of states to relinquish their exclusive powers in the field of intellectual rights. The way out of this situation was found by expanding this restriction from the territory of one state to the territory of the whole association. For this, the principle of “communitarian exhaustion of rights to intellectual property” was introduced. This principle implies the free circulation of intellectual property within the EU without any restrictions. In order to achieve this result, first of all, harmonization and unification of the norms of the Member States in this area was required, which continues to this day.

³ Vladimir Likhachev, “The current state of intellectual property protection in the EU,” *Russian Foreign Economic Journal*, no 5 (2014): 83.

Speaking about the characteristic features of the protection of intellectual rights in the EU, it is also necessary to touch upon the question of the definition of these rights by modern European legal doctrine. There are two main approaches to the concept of intellectual property rights: moral and material. You can visually analyze these two approaches by the example of copyright. In copyright law there is the principle of “droit d’auteur”, which implies the priority primarily of the author’s personality and focuses precisely on the protection of his personal, moral rights to the result of his mental activity. This approach is mainly prevalent in the countries of the Civil law system. In common law countries, the concept of “copyright” dominates, considering objects of copyright in the plane of market relations. Proponents of this concept consider the results of creative activity as ordinary objects of market relations, and the authors as “creative workers”. The jump in the development of intellectual property rights within the framework of the supranational powers of the EU is carried out strictly in the economic plane and has a prerequisite of market relations. Perhaps in connection with this, at the moment of the development of the EU, it somewhat deviates from the definition of intellectual rights as primarily moral and gives preference to the legal protection of investments, the activity of video and film companies that manage the property rights of authors. In addition, at the moment in the process of development of legislation in the field of intellectual rights there is a tendency of the greatest integration in the newest areas of creative activity such as computer programs and databases, biotechnological inventions, satellite and cable broadcasting. One of the reasons for the special integration process in these areas, in addition to their relevance in the era of scientific and technical growth, is also the fact that these areas are more easily amenable to a single legal regulation. The reason is that in these new areas, Member States do not yet have a coherent traditional legal system.

From the foregoing, it can be concluded that EU intellectual property rights are developing in the direction of harmonization and establishing, in the end, a single mechanism for protecting these rights. However, given the

diversity of intellectual property rights from classical rights such as copyright, patent law, trademarks to more marginal ones (databases, geographical names), the question arises whether there are currently any specific principles and a common basis on which all intellectual property rights would hold. The EU law unites all rights associated with exclusive rights to intangible property under the general concept of intellectual property, which is already a positive factor because it inclines all these rights to common goals and results. However, in EU legislative practice, there is a tendency towards a more separate regulation of various intellectual property rights by way of *ad hoc*. Separate regulation of this kind comes primarily from the varying degrees of intensity of EU law involvement in various areas of intellectual property law. Before coming to conclusions about the general principles of intellectual property rights in the EU as a whole, it seems necessary to consider how far EU legislation has stepped in resolving its various types.

As you know, European law has many different legal sources and mechanisms for their implementation in the participating countries. Different legislative acts have different levels and methods of influencing the law of states, which is connected with the degree of harmonization and integration in this particular area. With regard to intellectual property rights, it can be said that they are also no exception in this case. On the contrary, the lack of a common approach to various types of intellectual property rights and disconnected attitude towards their regulation by the EU is explained precisely by the multi-level legislative activity of this organization. The most multilateral and in-depth regulation by the EU was given to such exclusive rights as trademark law, industrial designs, protection of new plant varieties. In these areas, the European Union adopted specific legislation on direct impact, which brought the regulation of these areas to a supranational level. These acts are respectively the Council Regulation (EC) No. 207/2009 of February 26, 2009, on the Community trademark, Council Regulation No. 6/2002 of 6/2002 of 12.12.2001 on Community Designs and Council Regulation No. 2100/94 of July 27, 1994, on the rights to Community

plant varieties. In addition to the above, geographical indications and appellations of origin can also be attributed to EU regulation in accordance with Council Regulation No. 510/2006 of March 20, 2006, on the protection of geographical indications and appellations of origin of agricultural products and foodstuffs. These measures create a unified system of protection of specific rights in the entire common market and create a common regime of EU intellectual property rights. Less intensive are the steps taken to harmonize and bring together state legislations in the field of intellectual rights, which are perceived as a kind of interference in the internal affairs of the state in connection with the principle of territoriality of the protection of exclusive rights. It should be noted that such areas as trademark law, protection of industrial designs, protection of databases also succeeded in this process.

Copyright protection (copyright) continues to remain largely under the control of the national regimes of the Member States, despite the impressive number of directives adopted by the European Union regarding this field. Since the copyrights themselves cover a fairly wide range of relationships, harmonization also occurs here separately, on certain specific issues. They are, for example, defining terms, protection criteria, ownership, exceptions and limitations to rights.

European patent law is also not yet developed as a separate branch. Attempts to create norms common for the entire union related to patent law are still ongoing. In addition, not a single directive was adopted aimed at approximation of the laws of the Member States in this area. However, states have certain general rules of patent law, since they are all parties to the European Patent Convention adopted in Munich in 1973.

Thus, in the search for certain general principles or standards regarding intellectual property rights regardless of the specific type, there is a real shortage of both the EU law itself in the form of so-called “*acquis communautaire*” (“community property”) and legal doctrine, and discussions on this topic. One of the few general principles concerning intellectual property rights is Article 17 of the European Union Charter of

Fundamental Rights, which consists of one sentence: “Intellectual property must be protected”. This rather laconic and somewhat abrupt position of the article can be interpreted in two directions. It can be assumed that the legislator defines the protection of IP rights as a general goal to be achieved, but at the same time does not see the point in any other norms justifying their protection. In accordance with this interpretation, intellectual property rights are given free interpretation, and the process of their regulation is in the hands of nation states. However, the most plausible version seems to be that intellectual property law is considered as one of the areas of property rights in general and is a continuation of the idea of the inviolability of property rights as one of the fundamental human rights. At the same time, there is no need to provide any further explanations and methods for regulating this particular branch of law.

Thus, the legal system for the protection of intellectual property in European law is difficult to imagine in the form of one holistic picture, perhaps because it has not been fully established today. But despite this, there are certain norms, legal provisions that create standards, general directions for the further direction of policy in this area. First and foremost is the focus on providing the necessary incentive to creativity and innovation. This goal is clearly expressed in Directive 2004/48/EC. The same Directive in subsequent regulations parallels the development of innovation and creativity with the prosperity of the single market, which can be achieved through a stable system of protection of intellectual property rights. This goal is also indicated in many other EU legal acts. In addition, the protection of intellectual property rights is also considered one of the providers of the necessary investment protection, which provides a certain material income to owners of creative or other IP rights. This applies to both copyright and patent rights and the right of industrial designs (industrial design). Directive 2001/29/EC in its Article 10 points to this aspect regarding copyright and related rights as one of the most important reasons for creating adequate legal protection of intellectual property. Another common goal of various areas of intellectual property rights in the EU is to

ensure the free movement of goods and services, as well as control over the observance of competition rules.

All this constitutes the general principles characteristic of the various branches of intellectual property rights operating within the EU. However, each of these branches regulates certain, one may say, special legal forms, with which each of them has auxiliary properties. Nevertheless, for the further development of innovation and creativity as the driving force of the modern economy, it is necessary to create a common legal framework for all types of intellectual property. This will lead to a more coherent regulation of relations in this area, and will facilitate the process of harmonization of state legislations and their cooperation on conflict issues arising in connection with the use of intellectual property rights.

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The Valorization of Professional and Educational Brand through the Tools of Digital Marketing Communication

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Abstract. In the digital era, the professional brand, the educational brand can be exploited through a variety of marketing communication tools: on the one hand, video marketing, scheduled advertising, voice marketing, virtual reality and augmented reality, artificial intelligence (AI), on the other hand, the website (blog, ebooks, infographics or online brochures), social media (Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter, Snapchat, Pinterest, Google+, etc.), the newsletter (email marketing), mobile applications, interactive digital entities (the chatbot), neuro-linguistic programming (NLP), etc. Alternatively, the digital marketing communication tools are based on neuromarketing elements to investigate how consumers / educational service users make decisions and the link between decision-making and human brain areas. When using the professional brand, the educational brand, it is advisable to consider the following factors (influences): psychographics / psychology / psychotechnology of the ad text, of the slogan and logo, of the illustrations etc. In addition, the ten principles of neuromarketing can stimulate digital marketing, also the professional brand, educational brand.

Keywords: professional brand, educational brand, contracting, provider, beneficiary, neuro-linguistic programming (NLP), VAKOG, neuromarketing, advertising message, digital triggers, sensory branding, PIES model, PQ, IQ, EQ, SQ.

Introduction

The technological development is currently one of the main goals of both companies and higher education institutions. Digital communication and marketing brings benefits to both sides in the supplier-beneficiaries partnership. Or, to meet customer needs or educational needs by offering

products with unique features or by offering educational offers and competitive jobs, it is important to capitalize on the professional brand, the educational brand.

In the digital era, the use of the professional brand, the educational brand obviously implies the application of marketing communication tools, and these need to be identified and applied according to the SMART principle, in order to finally satisfy all the parties involved in this integrated marketing communication process. Thus, the impact on beneficiaries will only be positive if appropriate marketing communication tools relevant to communication, sales, educational services, etc. are used.

Specialists with experience in marketing and business development say that in the top of digital marketing communication tools are:

- ✓ *Video Marketing*, with the following eloquent arguments:
 - most people prefer to watch a video rather than read a blog post;
 - brands publish live video clips in employer branding;
 - according to HubSpot¹, including a video in an email increases the response rate by 200-300%, and inclusion on a landing page increases the conversion rate by 80% (live video content will continue to be explored and will only be distinguished by their originality).
- ✓ *Scheduled advertising*, with the following eloquent arguments:
 - marketers use digital advertising budgets more effectively;
 - brands invest in scheduled advertising to increase value;
 - the digital display is about to become 100% programmable;
 - the traditional media follows the example and develops processes that can apply the mechanics of scheduled advertisements, transferring them in an adapted way to their specifics.
- ✓ *Voice marketing*², with the following eloquent arguments:

¹ HubSpot – software marketing, sales and customer service, to stimulate business growth.

² Voice Marketing – marketing search tool (voice search).

- according to estimates, by 2020, half of all search queries will be voice-based;
 - voice recognition technology helps consumers of all ages to ensure the convenience of searching for products / services;
 - benefits in sales, customer relations, purchasing assistance, after-sales assistance, etc.
- ✓ *Virtual reality and augmented reality*³, with the following eloquent arguments:
- virtual office / hall tours are “games” that allow customers to improve their “information-communication-request” experience at all stages of a product brand development cycle;
 - more and more campaigns include virtual reality and augmented reality (VR and AR) technologies, especially in Retail and FMCG.⁴
- ✓ *Artificial Intelligence (AI)*⁵ and machine learning (MI)⁶, with the arguments:
- following the global trend and experimenting with applications based on artificial intelligence and machine learning – from chatbots⁷ to automation of marketing processes – these technologies find applications to bring customer satisfaction;

³ Virtual reality and augmented reality – virtual tour of the firm’s offices.

⁴ FMCG – manufacturers, importers, distributors, products, brands, own brands, private brands, FMCG sales.

⁵ Initially, the creation and research of artificial intelligence took place in the field of psychology, with emphasis on linguistic intelligence, such as the Turing test, (ELIZEI method is called “does not understand, but fits in”, from “pattern matching”).

⁶ Top companies in artificial intelligence and machine learning such as: Amazon, Cisco, Imperial College London, OptioPay and Google – DeepMind.

⁷ Although the companies do not really use the chatbot, according to a study by Facebook Messaging Survey, 53% of consumers say they „would buy rather from a firm that may chat and 63% say that” today, send more messages to different brands than they sent 2 years ago.

- brands that, on the one hand, know how to recruit and therefore benefit from the excellent human capital of IT firms and, on the other hand, they are client-centered, are rapidly advancing in capitalizing on this trend at absolutely reasonable costs.⁸

In this context, the question arises: *How does artificial intelligence influence online marketing?*

Mihai Vinătoru, Managing Partner & Head of SEO @DWF, gives us an eloquent answer: “Automating marketing actions was a first step towards personalized communication. As the ability to interpret and learn from the collected data grows, marketers will be able to move from assumptions and hypotheses to intelligent campaigns.”⁹

Andreea Moisa, Managing Director & Founder of Beans United, mentions: “Today “intelligent cars” are among us, it integrates more and more into our everyday life, often without even realizing it. When we translate a text with Google Translate, we feed the system of “neural translation”, which attempts to “understand” human speech and adapt the context-based translation. Starting this year, Gmail tries to find emails whose content indicates urgency to remind the user to respond. Almost 400,000 Romanians actively use Instagram. Not everyone knows, however, that the network analyzes the emoji used to understand the feelings behind the text, or that Instagram studies the relationship between images and hashtags in an attempt to place the user in a demographic category useful for marketing. More than 250,000 Romanians use Uber, many considering that, unlike many taxi drivers, the application does not “adjust to humans” when making the price of a race. Probably, many would be surprised to learn that, in fact, Uber is studying history of past races to estimate the

⁸ HubSpot, <https://www.hubspot.com/> (accessed 7 June 2019): “Principalele 5 tendințe ale anului 2019 în digital marketing,” <https://valoria.ro/blog/principalele-5-tendinte-ale-anului-2019-in-digital-marketing/> (accessed 7 June 2019).

⁹ “Definiția noului marketer: Azi “doer”. Măine “thinker”,” <https://www.techcafe.ro/evenimente/definitia-noului-marketer-azi-doer-maine-thinker/> (accessed 7 June 2019).

value each passenger is willing to pay by manipulating the final amount individually.¹⁰

But what is the evolution in educational marketing?

A higher education institution does not have a chance to succeed on the market if it does not apply appropriate digital marketing communication tools. And the statement like “Marketing is not necessary in educational institutions” is a myth! Here are some *strong arguments in rebuffing this myth*:

- *The success achieved in fulfilling the mission of the institution can gain a greater share*: through valuation tools, communication, mission and objectives set; careful, detailed analyzes.
- *The basis for programs that address the real problems / needs / expectations of potential educational beneficiaries*: marketing helps identify problems and plan responses to help the institution fulfill its mission.
- *Increasing motivation and satisfaction of target audience*: higher education institutions must excel in developing satisfactory programs for the needs of potential and current students and other stakeholders involved; otherwise, negative impressions and reduced fund inflows will have negative effects. Higher education institutions that are insensitive to the needs of the market face more apathy and lower morality. For such institutions, it is difficult to attract new students and new financial resources.
- *Improves the attraction of market resources*: in an attempt to satisfy customers, students, teachers, higher education institutions need to attract diverse resources, including employees, financiers, other stakeholders. In addition, the level of attraction of these resources is directly proportional to the satisfaction offered in return.

¹⁰ Ibid.

- *Increasing market efficiency*: Marketing emphasizes the role of management and coordination of program development, price formation, communications and distribution. Some higher education institutions make decisions without taking into account market ties, which results in higher costs for the same result. Or there is a departure of many of those who were to be persuaded, attracted.¹¹

An additional argument is also the increase in the reputation of the institution: because of a good reputation, it improves performance (the performances of students / master students / PhD students / professors), morale, team spirit, pride, etc.

As tools and channels of communication in digital educational marketing can serve:

- ✓ The website. The website of any higher education institution needs to be thought of as a real estate that hosts its business. That is why the leadership and staff of the institution are the ones who decide how to present and how to “sell” the educational product. The design and products / services we provide are the ones that generate our reputation. These attract more visibility and demand for what we offer, and ultimately it reflects on the human capital portfolio and even on turnover. Strategies: blog, ebooks, infographics, or online brochures through which we actively inform and involve potential or current recipients in the academic community.
- ✓ The social media. It is the space in which we promote our brand and content relevant to educational services, educational products to convince potential beneficiaries. Strategies: Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter, Snapchat, Pinterest, Google+ etc.
- ✓ The newsletter. Let us keep close our existing beneficiaries and conquer the undecided ones by effectively communicating the

¹¹ Marketing educational, <https://www.scribd.com/document/73678799/Marketing-educational-2-manual-%D0%BA%D0%BE%D0%BF%D0%B8%D1%8F> (accessed 7 June 2019).

content we want to promote and inform them about our offers and events or redirect the audience to the institution's website. Strategies: opportunities offered by email marketing.

- ✓ Mobile applications. These applications allow users to connect to our institution.
- ✓ Interactive digital entities. In the digital era, it is worthwhile applying artificial intelligence as an argument in support of an educational brand, namely: provider of accounting expertise, financial-banking, communication and HR, etc. Strategies: chatbot – digital sales agent / digital service agent.¹²

So in order to maximize the efficiency of any communication step – as a key condition in the choice and use of digital marketing communication tools – it is imperative to develop, internally and externally, educational products, institutional image, ensuring that we monitor with perspicacity the achievement of institutional-educational objectives.

Digital marketing communication tools – well thought out, designed, monitored – create connections, shape communities and meet needs.

An advertising message, for example, regardless of the channel through which it is transmitted, has to defeat a series of barriers and neurological filters until it reaches the consciousness of potential consumers / beneficiaries. In addition, even its mere awareness and / or memorization does not assure passing to the desired action by the one who launched the message.

Let's reflect on the following questions: *How many songs that have been heard in the advertising spots do you over the course of a day? And how many times are you comparing a concrete situation with the one described in the „X” ad? And of those saved scripts, how much do you remember the promoted brand? And how much do you really use?*

¹² “Comunicarea în era digitală: instrumente de succes pentru afacerea ta,” <https://www.emiral.ro/blog/comunicarea-in-era-digital-instrumente-de-succes-pentru-afacerea-ta/#> (accessed 7 June 2019).

In this context, to establish a correct approach to professional brand and to add flavor to the experience that already has the target audience, it is recommended to build “bridge” that will provide unique services / products of a company by *Neuro Linguistic Programming*¹³ (NLP) – a communication tool that is based on various communication mechanisms, influencing attitudes, behavior, and human decisions.¹⁴

NLP means: *Model + Strategy + Attitude*. Or, communication and digital marketing tools are based on neuro-linguistic programming elements.

In this context, we also mention *neuromarketing*¹⁵ – a field that studies consumer responses to marketing stimuli using *neuroimaging techniques* (nuclear magnetic resonance, electroencephalography or magnetoencephalography) to investigate how consumers make decisions and the link between decision-making and brain areas human.

Not by chance, *the forms of advertising* have come to satisfy the human mind at both conscious and unconscious levels, because these are the ones that guide the behavior. Thus, *most advertisements contain* major and powerful triggers for the human unconscious.

With regard to *buyers’ attention and their willingness to buy*, PORSCHE has received 360% higher response rates for direct mailing, and BUICK has increased its customer conversion rate from 9% to 40%.

So the composition of the images, the placement of the text, the suggestion of an action – all these have proved to be the elements of a science that helps the creative specialists to optimize their ideas.

PROCTOR & GAMBLE has transformed the launch of new products from a poker game in a series of safe successes, as did DAIMLER-CRYSLER and BMW.

¹³ *Neuro-linguistic programming* (NLP) was created around 1976 by Richard BANDLER (mathematician) and John GRINDER (linguist) in order to discover the structure of human excellence. NLP – Synthesis of psychology, hypnosis, linguistics and cybernetics.

¹⁴ *Neuromarketing* – neurometric, biometric, psychometric decisions.

¹⁵ Sigmund Freud, the neurologist and founder of psychoanalysis, has brought important theoretical bases not only in psychology and psychotherapy, but also in neuromarketing.

Neuromarketing has highlighted a matter of utmost importance: the consumer makes decisions at the mental, emotional and instinctual level. Therefore, in order to be successful, any promotional action must address all three plans of the human mind. At the same time, we must realize that no trick of neuroscience will “hypnotize” the client / beneficiary and will not make him buy something / accept any educational offer against his will if we will not know how to use these channels according to organizational goals.

Professional brand can be exploited through *sensory marketing* (communication channels, systems of perception or VAKOG stimuli, namely *Visual, Auditory, Kinesthetic, Olfactory, Gustatory*). In Martin Lindstrom’s opinion, the incorporation of the five stimuli / senses in branding strategy is called *sensory branding*. For example, if the purchase process is accompanied by pleasant sounds, the desire to buy goods has increased by 65%, a pleasant taste increases this desire by 23%, a pleasant smell – by 40%, for articles pleasant to the touch – 26% and beautiful from the outside – 46%.¹⁶

The professional, educational brand can also be valued by:

*A. Digital stimuli: Self-centered, Contrast, Tangible input, The beginning and the end, Visual stimuli, Emotion.*¹⁷

Digital Project Manager Luminița Balaban says: “Few brands apply sensational marketing in offline activation, and few are able to integrate sensory marketing with digital.”¹⁸

¹⁶ “Marketing senzorial integrat cu digital – viitorul publicității,” <http://www.read-my-mind.ro/marketing-senzorial-digital/> (accessed 7 June 2019).

¹⁷ Digital Stimuli: 1) *Self-centered* (your message as a seller must focus on your audience, not on you), 2) *Contrast* (*before / after, risky / safe, with /out or rapid / slow*), 3) *Tangible input* (friendly message, concrete, immutable, well-known), 4) *The beginning and end* (placement of the most important content from the beginning is a necessity, as it is repeated at the end, anything in the middle of your message will be overlooked) 5) *Visual stimuli* (visual clarity and persuasion), 6) *Emotion* (according to neurobiology, emotions, and namely, responses, electrochemical reactions in the brain directly influence the way we process and store information).

¹⁸ “Marketing senzorial integrat cu digital – viitorul publicității,” <http://www.read-my-mind.ro/marketing-senzorial-digital/> (accessed 7 June 2019).

B. VAK facilitates the exertion of influence on the target audience and other mechanisms such as:

✓ *The key to synchronizing language (linguistic preferences):*

Visual: "Take a closer look at this product. Look how fine it is. You will see that we pay the same attention to the mechanism itself. Let me show you."

Hearing: "I can show you my reasons, but you probably prefer to hear what others have to say about us. It will be easy to understand that these assessments are the echo of rehabilitation."

Kinestezic: "The decision to buy is sometimes an instinctual feeling, a matter of trust. But I want to give you more than the simple feeling that will make you want our product."

✓ *Command encapsulation (hidden commands):*

A. *Negative encapsulation:* „I would not want to buy the Aztec mechanisms without having enough evidence to support your recommendation" or "Do not buy the Aztec mechanisms just because I tell you"

B. *Encapsulation by redirecting attention:* "Buying Aztec mechanisms can be an easy process"

Instead of: You can call us 86-00-00, encapsulate your order by: Call Customer Service, SunTV Digital, whenever you need.

Instead of: Waiting for news from you, we encapsulate the order by: I cannot wait to talk again.

When using the professional brand, it is also advisable to take into account the psychographic / psychological / psychothecnological / hypnotic influences of the product / service / message provided:

✓ *The ad text:* To be conceived by a spiritual formula + alert, reasoning, promoted brand, unique and new.

- ✓ *The slogan*¹⁹ and ad text: Designed in KISS style (Keep it Short and Simple, and namely “Be Simple and Concise”). The title is read 5 times more than the rest of the text.
- ✓ *The logo*²⁰: be clear, unique, relevant to the promoted product, inspired by the values of the organization, attractive and memorable. The most successful brands have amazingly simple *logos* and *slogans*. The *logo* and the *slogan* should not be all-encompassing, but promise (they will enter a fascinating world, because we cherish each citizen and individual, that the purpose of our existence is they) and respecting the promise!²¹
- ✓ *The illustrations*: the superiority of images in memory to words.
- ✓ *The colors and forms*: to influence people’s emotions.
- ✓ *The hypnotic influencing*: Influencing the buyer when he sees the product he / she intends to buy (sniffs, stops to blink or swallowing saliva, slows breathing, pupils grow), to create a *hypnotic trance-like effect*.

Therefore, the professional brand will become a guarantee as we realize that designing and managing communication goals are possible when using the digital marketing communication tools appropriate to the target group.

Here there are the 10 principles of neuromarketing that can stimulate, capitalize on the professional brand:

1) *Appeal to the public’s emotions!*

People do not buy what they need, they buy what they want.

According to research from OkDork and Buzzsumo, your content

¹⁹ The slogan is a memorable phrase that summarizes the way the public has to perceive a particular institution / firm / product. The slogan sends the (potential) beneficiary the unique attribute that our institution has.

²⁰ *Logo* – abbreviation from the logotype, in Greek: *logos* – word and *grama* – writing.

²¹ “Cum se construiește identitatea unei biblioteci (V). Logo și slogan,” <https://ec.europa.eu/epale/ro/blog/cum-se-construiește-identitatea-unei-biblioteci-v-logo-si-slogan> (accessed 7 June 2019).

will have the biggest impact if you try to get these emotions in your audience: worship, laughter, amusement, joy.

Start these four emotions in *marketing copy*, and your customers will have more chances to do what you ask for. Use pictures and stories to have a stronger emotional impact.²²

2) *Use faces in content to get emotions!*

Facial expressions are universal language. We will understand people wherever we are. Think about how you can use faces in content to make people feel certain emotions.²³

3) *Use colors to get emotions!*

Each color has certain associations. Use them in the content to reinforce the message. Identify how you want your audience to feel, then use the relevant colors in your content.²⁴

4) *Remove the pain instead of giving pleasure!*

Marketers are taught to talk about the benefits of a product. The description of the benefits triggers the desired part of the brain. But the answer to avoiding brain pain is three times stronger. You will often get better results, explaining how your product can eliminate the pain in your client's life. You need to understand what is associated with pleasure and pain. What are you most likely to influence? Your time management software will free up time (pleasure)? Or will they never lose a deadline (pain relief)?²⁵

5) *Focus on the reciprocity law!*

A 2002 study explored how people are in restaurants in three different scenarios: 1) they received the bill and a small candy; 2) have received several candies; 3) have not received any candy. Scientists have found that "the candy gift increased the average gain from 15% to just under 18%." The increase in earnings was

²² "Neuromarketing Hacks to Boost Your Digital Marketing," <https://davidblinov.com/10-neuromarketing-hacks-to-boost-your-digital-marketing/> (accessed 7 June 2019).

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Ibid.

the same regardless of the amount of candy. Allow people to feel indebted. This can be done through the following marketing communication tools: free ebooks, webinars, podcasts, infographics, host blogs for your customers, free tools or resources, etc. For example, Netflix offers free services. Few people cancel the service after enjoying movies for 30 days.²⁶

6) *Use the deficit principle as leverage!*

We are always attracted to things that are exclusive and difficult to overlook. The harder you get to them, the more we want them to. This is one of the *neuromarketing capsules*.

People bind quality to availability. We suppose that the things that are hard to achieve are usually better than those available to everyone. For example, a classic psychological study of 1975, by Worchel, Lee and Adewole, examined the effect of the deficit on people. It was a simple study involving cookies. The researchers put 10 cookies in a jar and two of the same cookies in another jar. The two cookies in the jar received higher ratings, even if cookies were exactly the same!

Therefore, we can apply the principle of marketing deficiency by verbal triggering like:

- ✓ *Limited stock!* For example, hotel booking sites such as Booking.com and so on.
- ✓ *Limited time!* For example, Amazon, with its daily transactions.
- ✓ *Oversubscription!* This principle works well with pre-orders or bidding. You can add an additional emergency note, making the number of interested customers available to the public. For example, 200 participants at a Facebook event that has only 100 seats.²⁷

7) *Use social proof!*

²⁶ Ibid.

²⁷ Ibid.

Have you ever been to a restaurant because it has excellent reviews and a long list of reservations? Of course. If everyone loves the place, it must be wonderful. We trust things popular or recommended by the people we trust. When your customers are not sure if they will buy from you, they are looking for someone to help them make a decision. They especially want to hear from people like themselves. Happy customer testimonials show your audience that people similar to them are happy with your product. Then they are likely to become customers.²⁸

✓ *Social expert tactic!* For example, Twitter used social glow in its early days. Every now would load a page with a whale, saying that Twitter is out of capacity and you should try again. Instead of being indignant, people thought Twitter should be the next big thing, because so many others are using it too. Klout, for example, measures your current online expertise. They invited 217 experts with high scores in design and luxury to test the new Audi A8. These experts produced 3500 tweets, reaching over 3 million people in just a few weeks.

✓ *Proof of social celebs!* For example, Supercell has paid \$ 9 million for Liam Neeson to play the role of “Clash of Clans.” It has been watched over 200 million times and has brought tens of millions of revenue. Starbucks does not need approvals, but celebrities are seen with their coffee all the time. If the stars go to Starbucks, it must be OK!

✓ *Social influences! Users’ testimonials!* And so on²⁹.

8) *Make people engage first in small things!*

We are forced to make hundreds of decisions every day. Because we make a mental effort, we prefer to make a single decision and then stay with it for all subsequent related choices. We use

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ Ibid.

mental shortcuts or rules that simplify decision-making. These rules focus on one aspect of the problem and ignore others. Often, this means attaching a past commitment. We tend to see coherence as an attractive social feature. Consistent people are perceived as more rational and more trustworthy. We want to be seen like others, forcing us to remain consistent. There are several ways to trigger these shortcuts through neuromarketing. Dr. Cialdini mentions that people judge others and themselves through their actions. Make them engage publicly!³⁰

9) *Be nice! Be attractive!*

Dr. Cialdini identifies 5 key factors behind the preference principle: We like people who are like us. For example, vendors of vague cars often try to make themselves more like their buyers. If you notice a Manchester United screensaver on your phone, you can count on him that they are also a lifelong fan. The world is more social than ever. Brands no longer want to be cold and distant. They want us to be our friends.

- ✓ *Pay the compliments!* We like to be praised. People who pay our compliments become more enjoyable. Brands like Daniel Wellington use this by encouraging his clients to post a photo of their watch with a #danielwellington hashtag. Every day, DW shares best instagram photo on their channel to 2.7 million followers.
- ✓ *Cooperate!* We like people who work for the same goals. We respect them because they have the same ideals. Show your customers that your final goals match theirs. Support what you think and help them along the way. We all try to protect the environment by reducing pollution and energy consumption. For example, Tesla gets a lot of love to do the same with electric cars. This chance of instant fame is an

³⁰ Ibid.

excellent sales tool, helping DW reach \$ 250 million every year.³¹

10) *Build authority!*

We trust people who look like experts. This is especially true in areas where we do not know too much. Content automatically becomes more reliable if it includes “research shows”. Dr. Cialdini identifies *three factors that make us more valid*:

- ✓ *Titles!* When you have no experience in a field, listen to someone who knows the field, practice it. In business, this principle also applies to job titles and social media followers. You may immediately consider someone as a marketing expert because his / her title says “marketing consultant,” with thousands of Twitter followers. Apple used this principle when they called their customer support agents for the Geniuses clients. While there may not be the current geniuses in a traditional sense, the title makes you have more confidence in them with your new expensive MacBook.
- ✓ *Clothes!* Research shows that people make the first impression of others in a fraction of a second. Online surveys also found that web site visitors also take a very short time to do their job on a website. How can you use your brand to evoke instant confidence? Improving the professional and relevant look for the industry, you represent. Rolex is the embodiment of this rule. Their pages are perceived as polished and fashionable, just like the demographic viewer.
- ✓ *Indirect instructions!* A Ferrari parked in front of a house tells you indirectly that anyone who lives there is successful. Give people the indicators of your company’s performance. Get clues about your product as enjoyable and trustworthy.

³¹ Ibid.

However, beware of the reaction if your product fails to deliver.³²

Conclusions

Currently, the evolution of digital marketing communication tools is unprecedented. It is difficult to imagine any “professional”, educational, non-web-based “contracting”. In this respect, digital natives and digital immigrants need to realize that digital marketing communication tools need to be conceived and applied through the *PIES model*, and namely: **PQ** – physical intelligence (musical, corporal kinesthetic), **IQ** – cognitive intelligence (verbal, logical, mathematical, spatial), **EQ** – emotional intelligence (intrapersonal, interpersonal relationships), **SQ** – spiritual intelligence (integrated) that amplifies IQ and EQ. In digital education (whether or not applied to *Kahoot*, *Biteable*, *Screencast-o-matic* or *Vocaroo*, *StoryJumper*, *ProProfs*, etc.), the educational brand also needs to be exploited through the *PIES model*. Today’s students are tomorrow’s employees. Not accidentally, Bob Gass said: “What we see and hear is what we think. What we think is what we feel. What we feel influences our reactions. Reactions become habits, and habits determine our destiny.”

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REVIEWS

Jozefina Cusnir: Updating the Dynamic Constants of Humanization of the Myth in the Twentieth Century Intellectual Prose

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The work of Dr. Hab. Jozefina Cusnir “The Phenomenon of Humanization of the Myth in the Twentieth Century Intellectual Prose” (Chisinau: Pontos, 2017) is a personal project that proposes a new approach to the essence of the relation between myth and literature in its perpetual forming. The work represents a serious research containing a number of discoveries and new extensions on dynamic correlation of the myth and the literature and on the prospects provided by these issues from the angle of compared literature. Revealing the obvious or less obvious survival of myths in the contemporary literary act, the author focuses on the humanization of mythicization process, on the perception of renewed myth and on the process of historical-literary mythicization.

The actuality of Dr. Hab. J. Cusnir’s monograph is determined by the fact that the humanization of myth in the 20th century intellectual prose is conceptualized for the first time in this work as a holistic and uniformly verifiable literary phenomenon. As it is known, the term of “humanization of myth”, introduced by Thomas Mann (1942), has entered into the scientific circuit long ago, and the correlation “myth-literature” is a significant subject of scientific thinking of the 20th-21st centuries. The examination of this issue requires a systemic approach that takes into account a large complex of systematically accumulated modern scientific achievements.

In order to ensure the necessary systemic approach, Dr. Hab. J. Cusnir has largely applied in her research the components of the concept of humanization of myth. This concept, elaborated by the author, represents the research experience of homonymous phenomenon and relies on a

number of the twentieth century discoveries. A special place amongst them occupies the works of N. Frye, Cl. Geertz, M. Bakhtin, V. Propp, O. Freidenberg, K. Jaspers, C.G. Jung, K. Kerényi, M. Eliade, A. Schweitzer, J. Ortega y Gasset, N. Berdiaev, Cl. Levi-Strauss, E. Meletinsky and other renowned scientists.

The first chapter of the research analyses from different prospects the situation in the field and different aspects of mentioned issues, including the essence of the concept of humanization of myth and some of its components, that are used subsequently as comparing literary comparative tools. In particular, starting from the ideas of Thomas Mann about the humanization of myth, realized in the biblical tetralogy about Joseph, and relying on the mentioned above findings of scientific thinking of the 20th century, the author defines the literary phenomenon of humanization of myth as ethicizing harmonization of the Universe (image of the world), created explicitly or implicitly in the literary text through the mythological structures. The phenomenon is verified by J. Cusnir through the use of dichotomy *totem/non-totem* coined by O. Freidenberg and extrapolated by the author from the prospect of “Axial Age” (by Karl Jaspers).

Identifying a number of archaic mythologems (of catabasis and others) that, as basic mythologems, form the humanization of myth in the 20th century intellectual prose, the author reveals the mythologems of the highest level of generalization, naming them “dynamic constants of humanization of myth”. They are: *totem / non-totem* dichotomy, myth of laughter, myth of the abolition of *non-totem*-death. The author elaborated a brief scheme of evolution of ancient mythological consciousness in the aspect of humanization of myth. The understanding of this evolution’s internal logics contributes to the identification and the perception of these basic mythologems in literary text where they are usually present implicitly.

The importance of the information contained in the first chapter for the research objectives’ realization becomes obvious in the next five chapters. The literary phenomenon of humanization of myth is contextually realized in a corpus of the 20th century intellectual prose, involving

renowned names as Th. Mann, H. Hesse, J. L. Borges, Fr. Durrenmatt, F. Kafka, R. Akutagawa, G. Stein, A. Camus, R. Walser, M. Sebastian, V. Nabokov, D. Harms, A. Bitov and others. Basing on their texts, the author not only identifies the existence of humanization of myth in intellectual prose as holistic literary phenomenon, verifiable through the dichotomy *totem/non-totem*, but she also empirically confirms her hypothesis: about the invariance of humanization of myth to variations of correlations of literary text and its basic mythologem (identity/non-identity of the chronotops of intellectual prose and its basic mythologem; linear/non-linear correspondence of their structures; interference of basic mythologems etc.); about the possibility of formation of humanization of myth through its dynamic constants.

A peculiar interest represents, probably, the invariance of humanization of myth to such a kind of basic mythologems' interference, when one of these mythologems doesn't form the humanization of myth and even opposes it in an obvious manner.

The efficiency of the approach used by the author is also confirmed by the fact that J. Cusnir identifies a new special type of basic mythologems in the twentieth century intellectual prose. The author identifies it within comparative literary analysis, related to the "central thesis" of Nortrop Frye, the founder of mythical-archetypal critics that postulated the dependence of literature of archetypal mythical structures, considering myth as "matrix of literature" and literature as "displaced mythology". J. Cusnir names this type "basic mythologems whose potential is realized within intellectual prose" and shows that it includes the mythologem about "temptation for good" and the mythologem about apocatastasis in its modified form, where the concept of "all" is global. We note that the latter was identified by the author as common basic mythologem in "The Accident" by M. Sebastian and "Lujin's Defense" by V. Nabokov. There are two writers contextually "saved" in apocatastasises formed by these texts: M. Proust in the novel by M. Sebastian, F. Dostoievski in the novel by V. Nabokov.

One of conclusions that emerges from the reading of this monograph is that the components of the concept of humanization of myth used by the author are an efficient literary analysis tool that can be recommended both for specialized and general use.

Following the axiological horizon of the artistic idea, Jozefina Cusnir proposes her own formula of joining of “axiology” of literature through the consistent and systemic highlighting its updated archetypal and mythological constants, as well as free, non-canonical creative structures designed by contemporary intellectual prose.

Hence, the awareness and the explanation of literary texts both from the mythological perspective, on the one hand, and through the typology, classification of archaic or new myths/ mythologems, on the other hand, leads to reveal new senses of mythological structures in literary texts studied or non-studied from this perspective.

The work of Dr. Hab. Jozefina Cusnir, characterized by a deep and efficient originality from the point of view of literary science, is of interest to a large circle of specialists from socio-humanities field.

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9772345104101

ISSN 2345-1041

ISSN-L 2345-1041